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A Stakeholder Map

Submission of Deliverable

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Executive summary

An overview is given of the stakeholders and end-users of EU-PolarNet. The stakeholder map will form the basis for the stakeholder engagement. We have identified the research communities, parliaments and policy, local inhabitants, polar organisations, NGOs, international networks and agencies, the media and business and industry sectors as the stakeholder groups of EU-PolarNet. The stakeholder groups are related to the key research questions, defined in deliverable 2.1. From all different stakeholder groups a large group of stakeholder organisations is addressed in a separate excel document. This document needs to be up-dated during the whole project, since it is possible that during the stakeholder engagement process that new stakeholder groups will emerge.

Introduction

An important objective of EU-PolarNet is to initiate, conduct and sustain an on-going dialogue and cooperation with all relevant stakeholders for the Polar Regions. EU-PolarNet wants to create and deliver a framework and implementation plan to facilitate mutually beneficial engagement and interaction between EU-PolarNet research programme participants and stakeholders. The identification of key stakeholders is critical for successful engagement [See deliverable 4.3 for the communication and engagement strategy]. The stakeholders are those who are potentially affected by or concerned about, interested in, important to, or having any power over the polar research agenda or will be end-users of polar research outcomes. Stakeholders form a wide variety of public and private sectors including policy, business, governmental and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and a wider society, including local and indigenous peoples. But also the polar research community itself is regarded as an important stakeholder group. In the stakeholder consultation process it is important to include minority and vulnerable groups as well as to pay attention to existing stakeholder coalitions, partnerships and working groups.

Mapping Key Stakeholder Groups

Different guides and reports have suggested a number of criteria for highlighting key stakeholders [e.g. The FRP Guide to Stakeholders Engagement - November 2007; The UNEP guidance manual 2009 -Integrated Assessment: Mainstreaming sustainability into policymaking]. With some minor variations in ordering the stakeholders, most come to similar stakeholder target groups.

The FRP Guide to Stakeholders Engagement - November 2007, suggests a number of criteria for selecting high priority stakeholders. Taking into consideration the EU-PolarNet target, the selection of eligible and credible Stakeholders should meet the following requirements [see also Deliverable 4.3]:

- stakeholders who are charged with legal, financial, and operational responsibilities of Polar scientific activity in the form of regulations, contracts, policies, or codes of practice.
- stakeholders who are substantially affected by Polar or Polar-related activities, products or services, or who closely interact with scientific activity, including those stakeholders that the European Polar facilities depend on in day-to-day operations.
- stakeholders who have influence on or decision-making power over scientific activities and/or their effect at societal, economic and environmental level.
- stakeholders who are legitimate recipients of policy and value statements, including early warning about emerging issues and risks, or who reflect a wide range of societal

expectations, impacted groups, and issue areas or legitimately represent (through regulation, custom, or culture) a relevant constituency, including those representing the "voiceless" (e.g., the environment, children, future generations)

As already stated in Deliverables 4.2 and D4.3 key stakeholders include the research communities, parliaments and policy, local inhabitants, polar organisations, NGOs, international networks and agencies, the media and business and industry sectors. For all key stakeholder groups, different stakeholder subgroups are identified. In some cases, groups of stakeholders are well structured and have good organisations that can be contacted to represent a stakeholder group by themselves. This is for instance the case with the different societies for indigenous peoples. More diverse to identify are for instance the industry and other business. A short description of the different stakeholder groups is proposed below.

Research communities

The research communities include a large group of research institutions, universities and national polar operators. The partners of EU-PolarNet represent largely these research communities. Each EU-PolarNet partner (except AMAP and WOC) is representing the research community of their country. The research communities are also addressed by mapping the important and relevant conferences and symposia.

Parliamentary and policy

For the EU-PolarNet project, the European Commission and the European Parliament are very important stakeholders. Besides that there are the national governments of the EU and Arctic countries, the Arctic Council and the countries that signed the Antarctic Treaty. There are also the governance organisations of regional and local communities in the Arctic.

European public

This group is very hard to address in the stakeholder identification. This target group will be reached through the three primary types of engagement:

- engagement for awareness (make user groups/audiences aware of the work of the project);
- engagement for understanding (make user groups/audiences to understand the work of the project);
- engagement for action (make user groups/audiences to adopt actions)

These ways of engagement are further described in deliverable 4.3.

Local Arctic communities; indigenous communities;

The indigenous peoples are well organised and can be reached by their different organisations. The key indigenous organisations are the six so-called permanent participants in the Arctic Council: Aleut International Association (AIA), Arctic Athabaskan Council (AAC), Gwich'in Council International (GCI), Inuit Circumpolar Council (ICC), Russian Association of Indigenous Peoples of the North (RAIPON) and Saami Council (SC). Some other organisations can be named here as well, like the Association of World Reindeer Herders, Sami Education and the International Workgroup for Indigenous Affairs.

The non-indigenous communities are not as well organised. They can be reached through the local, regional and national governments. For this group the above engagement strategies will be used as well.

Polar organisations

In both the Arctic and Antarctic there is a group of very well functioning organisations that are key stakeholder partners for the EU-PolarNet. These are organisations like IASC, SCAR, IASSA, Arctic Council, the Barents Council and the Antarctic Treaty Secretariat.

NGOs

The NGOs can be subdivided in those engaged in environmental issues and those that have a focus on the indigenous rights.

International networks and agencies

These include amongst others the Council of Managers of National Antarctic Programmes (COMNAP); the Forum of Arctic Research Operators (FARO), INTERACT; networks, like EUAIC, IASSA, SEARCH, APECS, Arctic Science Partnership and ArcticNet.

WOC as an industry partner in EU-PolarNet, GINR with its strong relation to residents in the Arctic and ESA will also be major contributors, and all other WP4 partners will contribute as well.

The media

The media can be used as a way to reach stakeholders, but is also a stakeholder in its own right.

Business and Industry sectors

This is a large sector of stakeholders. It can be divided in different stakeholder subgroups.

For the Antarctic the range of businesses and industries is limited. The most important are tourism, fishery and the infrastructure services. Also the military can be mentioned here. Note that there is also a lot of research done by the industry and the military.

Jóhannsdóttir and Cook¹ recently identified the economic opportunities in the Arctic region, presented in the table below. In red the additions of the World Ocean Council are added. These opportunities give us a good overview of the key stakeholder industries and other activities.

KEY INDUSTRIES IDENTIFIED	OPPORTUNITIES
Oil and gas	Exploitation of fossil-fuel energy resources, including onshore and offshore projects in shallow and deep water
Land-based mining / mineral resources	Exploitation of resources, e.g. gold, platinum, uranium, iron ore and diamond and improved shipping out from Arctic ports
Fisheries	Increased fishing productivity and increased access to ice free waters

¹ Lára Jóhannsdóttir & David Cook (2015). *AN INSURANCE PERSPECTIVE ON ARCTIC OPPORTUNITIES AND RISKS: Hydrocarbon exploration & shipping*. Reykjavik: Institute of International Affairs / The Centre for Arctic Policy Studies

Aquaculture	Increased fish farming in some northern coastal waters, e.g. Norway
Shipping	Shorter distances for transit shipping, cost savings in terms of time (days at sea) and fuel, saving of tolls For destination shipping, improved access and support services
Ports and infrastructure	Development and investment opportunities for coastal infrastructure to support the other industries
Logistics, maritime services	Development and investment opportunities to support the other industries
Tourism	Development of tourism in remote areas, increased frequency of cruises
Submarine cables	First ever transarctic cable, decreased latency in Asia-Europe telecommunications, increased web access for remote northern communities
OTHER ACTIVITIES	OPPORTUNITIES
Wind and hydro power production	Exploitation of wind and water resources
Consulting and advisory services	Need for specialised knowledge, e.g. on risk management and safety issues
Science, technology and data	Need for data collection, special technology withstanding Arctic conditions, e.g. satellite, gliders, ROVs, data analysis and software, etc.
Insurances	Growing markets for specialised insurance solutions Rising insurance capacity
Marine biotechnology	Potential for new biological materials for biotech, e.g. new genetic sources from Arctic marine species
Scientific research	Rising need for scientific research

This overlaps to a large extent with the focus of Arctic Economic Council:

- Infrastructure and related matters including maritime transportation, communications and IT and aviation;
- Energy, including oil, gas and renewable sources;
- Mining;
- Tourism;
- Fishing;
- Human resources investments and capacity building

Stakeholder identification

Following the defining of the stakeholder target groups, the identification of the individual organisations, businesses etc. needs to take place. As a starting point for the Arctic stakeholder identification the European Arctic Information Centre Preparatory Phase (EUAIC), EC DG Environment-funded, is used. It conducted a comprehensive survey (2012 and 2014) of the major Arctic Stakeholders. Although the focus of this study was different, e.g. considering the trends and

developments taking place in the European Arctic, the societal challenges addressed are largely overlapping. The analysis has been conducted on the basis of seven themes focused on change: climate change, maritime transport, fisheries, oil & gas, mining, activities affecting land use and social and cultural changes.

To add Antarctic organisations and more relevant Arctic organisations in the private sector and civil society realm, the most influential polar conferences and other events like the Arctic Circle, Arctic Frontiers, Arctic Shipping Conference, Arctic Energy Summit, SCAR conference were scanned. See for a complete list the stakeholders' overview document. Also several experts were and still are consulted to help expand this already large list (more than 700 entries). The stakeholder identification will be an on-going process during the whole EU-PolarNet project and after the end of the project. The stakeholder dialogue will start based on research topics drawn out of existing projects. During the stakeholder consultation these topics will be further shaped and changed. In this process it is possible that new stakeholder groups will emerge.

Stakeholders related to the key research topics

In deliverable 2.1 (D2.1) the key research topics are being identified based on a list of about 146 documents describing the polar research priorities of the EU countries and other relevant organisations. Since these research topics are not final yet a preliminary list is being addressed in annex 1. For each of these topics the societal challenges are also described in D2.1. Based on these descriptions, the key stakeholders need to be identified for each topic. The willingness to engage and the related reasoning need also be addressed. The willingness to engage depends also on the capacity of EU-PolarNet to convince the stakeholders group of the critical importance to participate. But the willingness to participate will also greatly depend on how much a stakeholder group has to gain from their engagement. For the local communities this is clearer than, for instance, for the European public or the media.

A few things need to be considered:

- The long-term results of the engagement of stakeholders can make it more challenging to engage them;
- More and more projects are trying to increase the stakeholder involvement. These means that stakeholders are increasingly asked to engage in different projects. Not only is there a risk of stakeholder fatigue, there is also a need to coordinate the process of engaging stakeholders in different projects, especially in the (upcoming) EU calls;
- In general it can be said that the indigenous peoples' organisations and some NGOs have capacity problems to address their involvement in many different projects and working groups;
- The research community is a key stakeholder by itself and will not be addressed separately.

Annex 1

For a list of preliminary research-topics, the stakeholder groups are identified.

Key Research topics	Key stakeholder groups (other than researchers)	Likelihood to engage	Reasoning (position, influence, impacts etc.)
Polar climate systems	Local communities and governments	Medium	Directly impacted
	Governments and communities outside polar regions affected by changes in weather patterns	Medium	Directly impacted
	Insurance and reinsurance companies	High	Economic interest
	Oils and gas, Shipping, Fisheries, Tourism, Ports	High	Directly impacted
Cryosphere	Oils and gas, Shipping, Fisheries, Tourism, Science and research	High	Changing ice conditions; Data collection and analysis opportunities
	Terrestrial Infrastructure	High	Changing permafrost, seasonally frozen ground and snow conditions
	Coastal non-Arctic countries	Medium	Influence from sea level rise
Solid earth and its interactions	Mining, Oil and gas; Ports and infrastructure	Medium	Economic interest
	National governments	Medium	Intrinsic value
Palaeoclimate and Palaeo Environment	Oil and gas	Medium	Economic interest
	National and regional government (i.e. National Park service's Nature Reserves)	Medium	Intrinsic value
Astronomy, Astrophysics and Space	National government; Science and technology	Medium	Data collection and analysis opportunities
	Space agencies/ Business	High	Economic interests/communications
Human impacts	Local communities and governments	High	Directly impacted
	Industry operating outside the region	Low	Distant pollution
	Oil and gas, shipping, tourism	High	Local pollutions sources and potential pollution emergencies

Key Research topics	Key stakeholder groups (other than researchers)	Likelihood to engage	Reasoning (position, influence, impacts etc.)
	NGOs	High	Intrinsic values
Polar ecosystems and biodiversity	Fishery industry	High	Economic interest in resource use
	Oil and gas, shipping, tourism	High	Potential impacts
	Indigenous peoples organisations	High	Depend on living natural resources
	Non-polar communities with cultural tradition related to the polar regions ¹	High	Traditions depend on living national resources
	Tourist industry	High	Nature interest
Ecosystem Services and Sustainable management of resources	Fishery industry and aquaculture	High	Economic interest in resource use; Potential impacts
	Agriculture / forestry	High	Economic interest
	Living resources industry	High	Economic interest
	Mining, oil and gas and tourism	High	Economic interest
	NGOs	High	Intrinsic values
People, Societies and Cultures	Indigenous peoples organisations	High	Directly impacted
	Local communities and governments	High	Directly impacted
	All industries	High	Concerns about impacts local and indigenous people
	Non- Arctic people	High	Intrinsic values associated to conservation of a common Earth
	NGOs	High	Intrinsic values
Human health and Wellbeing	Arctic Communities	High	Directly impacted
International relations and legal dimension	National governments	Low	Ensure national interests
	All trans-boundary industries	Medium	Concerns about governance
	Multinational corporations	Medium	Economic interest
New technologies	Industry	Medium	Economic interest
	Engineering	Medium	Economic interest

Annex 2

An extended overview of stakeholders [see excel file]. This excel file is a so-called *living file*. This means that it will be updated during the whole project based on developments in the stakeholder consultation process.

Annex 3

As an extra annex we have compiled an overview of research projects with stakeholder engagement [see excel file].

ⁱ For example, Portugal has a hugely important tradition linked to codfish consumption, largely dependent on North Atlantic and Arctic fisheries. This is more than only the fishery industry, since these are deeply embedded traditions.

Annex2: EU-PolarNet stakeholder map, as of April 5, 2016 (11:38)

Target group	Type	Specific stakeholder	Rank	Region of interest	Base of operations	Confirmed EU-PolarNet contact person + email address	Possible EU-PolarNet contact person + email (need a double check)	General home page	Generic email	"Polarness" - i.e. at which events was the stakeholder active? (key to abbreviations under the sheet)	Target group
Mining	private sector	Mawson Resources	.	Nordic countries	Finland	.	.	http://www.mawsonresources.com/s/Home.asp	.	A. Business Forum 15; Noora Raasakka (environmental leader)	Mining
Mining	private sector	Anglo American	.	Circumpolar	Finland	.	.	http://www.angloamerican.com	.	.	Mining
Mining	private sector	Northland Resources Finland	.	Finland	Finland	.	Jukka Jokela <jjokela@northland.eu>;	http://www.northland.eu/	.	.	Mining
Mining	private sector	Northland Resources Sweden	.	Sweden	Sweden	.	Jonas Lundström <jlundstrom@northland.eu>;	http://www.northland.eu/en-us/home	.	.	Mining
Mining	private sector	Gold Fields Arctic Platinum	.	Finland	Finland	Mining
Mining	private sector	First Quantum Minerals Ltd.	.	Worldwide	Finland	.	.	info@fqml.com	.	.	Mining
Mining	private sector	Yara Suomi Oy	.	Finland	Finland	Mining
Mining	private sector	Agnico Eagle Mines Ltd	.	Circumpolar	Finland	.	Seppo Voutilainen <seppo.voutilainen@agnicoeagle.com>;	.	.	A. Frontiers 16; Canada's North Summit 13; James Nasso (chairman of board) and others	Mining
Mining	private sector	Dragon Mining Oy Kuusamo gold mine	.	Finland	Sweden	Mining
Mining	private sector	Jokkmokk Iron Mines	.	Sweden	Sweden	Mining
Mining	private sector	Boliden	.	Sweden	Sweden	Mining
Mining	private sector	Hannans Reward Ltd.	.	Sweden	Sweden	Mining
Mining	semi public	LKAB	.	Sweden	Sweden	.	Anders Lundkvist <anders.lundkvist@lkab.com>;	http://www.lkab.com	.	Mining and Mineral Industry of the Future 16; Bo Krogvig (senior vice-pres.)	Mining
Mining	private sector	Tertiary Minerals	.	unknown	Sweden	.	.	http://www.tertiaryminerals.com/contact-us	info@tertiaryminerals.com	.	Mining
Mining	private sector	Axactor (formerly Nickelmountain)	.	Sweden	Sweden	.	.	http://www.axactor.com/	siv.farstad@axactor.com	.	Mining
Mining	private sector	Rana Gruber	.	Norway	Norway	Mining
Mining	private sector	Nussir	one mine	Norway	Norway	.	.	http://www.nussir.no/	info@nussir.no	A. Summit 15: Øystein Rushfeldt (chief executive officer)	Mining
Mining	private sector	Norilsk Nickel	.	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	3rd Int. A. Forum	Mining
Mining	private sector	PanaGM	.	unknown	Russian Federation	Mining
Mining	private sector	Sotkamo Silver Oy	.	Finland	Finland	Mining
Mining	private sector	Skaland Graphite AS	secondary	Norway	Norway	.	.	http://www.graphite.no/	.	Artic Frontiers 15	Mining
Mining	association	Mining & Mineral Cluster Norway (Energiklyngen)	.	Norway	Norway	.	.	http://mineralklyngenorge.no/home	susanne@hjh.no	Artic Frontiers 15	Mining
Mining	private sector	Baffinland Iron Mines	.	Canada	Canada	.	.	http://www.baffinland.com/	contact@baffinland.com	A. Age 15; Tom Paddon (CEO); A. Summit 15: idem Tom ; A. Summit 14: idem Tom ; A. Circle 14: idem Tom; Poles Apart 13: idem Tom;	Mining
Mining	private sector	TMAC Resources	.	Canada	Canada	.	.	http://www.tmacresources.com/Home/default.aspx	info@tmacresources.com	A. Age 15	Mining
Mining	network	Arctic Cluster of Raw Materials	.	Greenland	Greenland	.	.	http://acrm.dk/	nikt@dl.dk	A. Circle 15: Niels Tanderup-Kristensen (director)	Mining
Mining	semi public	Nunaoil AS	.	Greenland	Greenland	.	Hans Kristian Olsen <hko@nunaoil.gl>;	http://nunaoil.gl/en/	nunaoil@nunaoil.gl	A. Summit 14: Hans Kristian Olsen (managing director); A. Energy Summit 15: Peter Christiansen (CEO);	Mining
Mining	private sector	Greenland Minerals and Energy Ltd	.	Greenland	Australia	.	.	http://www.ggg.gl/	online form http://www.ggg.gl/contact/	Poles Apart 13: Rod McIlree (CEO);	Mining
Mining	private sector	Northern Iron	.	Norway	Australia	.	.	http://www.northerniron.com.au/	online form http://www.northerniron.com.au/contact	.	Mining
Mining	private sector	Prominvestsa	.	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	.	.	http://www.prominvestsa.com/en/	prominvest@prominvest.ch	.	Mining
Mining	council	International Council on Mining and Metals (ICMM)	.	Worldwide	International	.	.	http://www.icmm.com/	info@icmm.com	A. Circle 14: Anthony Hodge (president) and others;	Mining
Mining	private sector	Tech	.	Worldwide	Canada	.	.	http://www.teck.com/	art@teck.com	A. Circle 14: Don Lindsay (CEO)	Mining
Mining	private sector	Stornoway Mining Corporation	.	Canada	Canada	.	.	http://www.stornowaydiamonds.com/English/home/default.aspx	online form http://www.stornowaydiamonds.com/English/contact/request-information/default.aspx	A. Circle 14: Patrick Godin (vice-pr.)	Mining
Mining	private sector	Dominion Diamonds	.	Canada	Canada	.	.	http://www.ddcorp.ca/	ddc@ddcorp.ca	A. Circle 14: Bob Gannicott (CEO)	Mining
Mining	private sector	Fortescue Metals Groups	.	Circumpolar	Australia	.	.	http://fmgl.com.au/	fmgl@fmgl.com.au	A. Circle 15: Damien Ardagh (manager Aboriginal Dev.)	Mining
Mining	association	FinnMin Finnish Association of Extractive Resources Industry	.	Finland	Finland	.	Pekka Suomela <pekka.suomela@techind.fi>;	.	.	.	Mining

Target group	Type	Specific stakeholder	Rank	Region of Interest	Base of operations	Confirmed EU-PolarNet contact person + email address	Possible EU-PolarNet contact person + email (need a double check!)	General home page	Generic email	"Polarness" - i.e. at which events was the stakeholder active? (key to abbreviations under the sheet)	Target group
Mining	private sector	FQM Kevitsa Mining Oy	-	Finland	Finland	-	Ulla Syrjälä <ulla.syrjala@fqml.com>	-	-	-	Mining
Mining	private sector	Mireko Mining Company	-	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	-	Igor Derevyanko <priem@mireko.komir.ru>	-	-	-	Mining
Mining	private sector	Endomines	-	Finland, Sweden	Finland, Sweden	-	Markus Ekberg <markus.ekberg@endgmines.com>	-	-	-	Mining
Mining	private sector	SveMin	-	Sweden	Sweden	-	Tomas From <tomas.from@svemin.se>	http://www.svemin.se/	info@svemin.se	-	Mining
Mining	association	Norsk Bergindustri	-	Norway	Norway	-	Elisabeth Gammelsæter <eg@norskbergindustri.no>	http://www.mth.com	-	-	Mining
Mining	private sector	MTH Højgaard	-	Circumpolar	Denmark	-	Jøannes Niclassen <jin@mth.dk>	http://mth.com/projects/mining.aspx	mail@mth.dk	-	Mining
Mining	association	NordMin Nordic Network of Mining Expertise	-	Nordic countries	Nordic countries	-	-	dead link	unknown	-	Mining
Mining	association	Euromines European Association of Mining Industries	-	Worldwide	Europe	-	-	http://www.euromines.org/	secretariat@euromines.be	-	Mining
Mining	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Mining
Mining	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Mining
Mining	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Mining
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	Statoil	-	Worldwide	Norway	-	Jarle Husebø <jahuse@statoil.com>; Anupama Mohan <anum@statoil.com>;	-	-	A. Forum 15: Anne Cavendish (EU Affairs coordinator); Morten Karlsen (Manager for A. Technology Program); A. Frontiers 15 [*]; several attendees; A. Futures 15; idem Morten.; A. Futures 14, 16; Rini M. Hansen (head A. unit) and others; A. Circle 15; Erik Haaland (statoil Norway); A. Frontiers 16 [*]; High North Dialogue 15; idem Rini; A. Energy Summit; Ella	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	Royal Dutch Shell (1)	-	Worldwide	International	-	Robert Blaauw <robert.blaauw@shell.com>; Phil Dyer <Phil.Dyer@shell.com>;	-	-	A. Forum 15: Robert Blaauw (Senior A. Advisor) and Peter Webb (Government Relations Advisor); A. Circle 14: idem Robert; A. Energy Summit 13: idem Robert (also sponsor); 3rd Int. A. Forum: Pavel Galaktionov (Russian contact person for Shell Exploration and production Services) and Sean Rooney (pres. for government relations); A. Circle 14; A. Frontiers 16: various [*]; A. Energy Summit 15: Mitch Winkler (head of Arctic Techn. Progr.) and idem Peter; Poles Apart 13: idem Blaauw; A. Open-water Meeting 13; A. Observing Summit 16: Michael Macrander; A. Observing Summit 16: Michael Macrander	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	Royal Dutch Shell (2)	-	Worldwide	International	-	Bas Maase <bas.maase@shell.com>;	-	-	see (1)	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	Total	-	Worldwide	Norway	-	-	-	-	A. Frontiers 15, 16 [*]; 3rd Int. A. Forum: Eugene Berg (head of Murmansk office);	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	Gazprom	-	Worldwide	Russian Federation	-	-	-	-	-	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy	private sector	DONG Energy	-	Worldwide	Denmark	-	-	www.dongenergy.com/en	info@dongenergy.com	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Energy
Energy	private sector	International Energy Agency (IEA)	-	Worldwide	International	-	Fath Birol <fath.birol@iea.org>;	-	-	High North Dialogue 15: Nathan Frisbee	Energy
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	ExxonMobile	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	-	-	A. Energy Summit 13: Gary Isaksen; 3rd Int. A. Forum: Glenn Waller (president of Russian dep.); A. Energy Summit 15: Mark Brundage (community relations lead) and James Hall (chairman); A. Observing Summit 16: Eric Febbo;	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	Rosneft Oil Company	-	Worldwide	Russian Federation	-	-	-	-	A. Summit 15: Artur Chilingarov (board of directors member) (also Russian Geographical Soc.); High North Dialogue 16: Emmerson Milensky;	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy	private sector	Kemijoki Group	-	Finland	Finland	-	Kari Anttila <kari.anttila@kemishipina.fi>;	-	-	-	Energy
Energy	private sector	Pohjolan Voima	-	Finland	Finland	-	-	-	-	-	Energy
Energy	private sector	Oulun Energia	-	Finland	Finland	-	-	-	-	-	Energy
Energy (oil/gas)	association	International Petroleum Industry Environmental Conservation Association (PIECA)	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	http://www.iecea.org	-	A. Forum 15: Artemis Kostarell (Fellow)	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	association	Norwegian Oil and Gas Association	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	https://www.norskoljeoggass.no/en/	firmapost@norog.no	A. Forum 15: Erling Kvadsheim (Director); A. Futurus 16: Karl E. Schjøtt-Pedersen (director general)	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	Eni	-	Worldwide	Italy	-	-	http://www.eni.com/en_IT/home.html	-	A. Forum 15: Giorgia Manno (European government affairs); 3rd Int. A. Forum: various mid-priority participants	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	Wasco Energy	-	Worldwide	Italy, Malaysia	-	-	-	-	-	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	association	Canadian Association of Petroleum Producers (CAPP)	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.capp.ca/	communication@capp.ca	A. Oil and Gas Symposium 16: Aaron Miller (director)	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	Norterminal	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	-	-	-	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy	private sector	Varanger Kraft AS	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	https://www.varanger-kraft.no/	-	A. Forum 15: Stein Mathisen (COO); A. Futures 15: idem Stein	Energy
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	Repsol	-	Worldwide	Spain	-	-	http://www.repsol.com/us_en/	-	A. Forum 15: Vega Tapia (EU Affairs)	Energy (oil/gas)

Target group	Type	Specific stakeholder	Rank	Region of Interest	Base of operations	Confirmed EU-PolarNet contact person + email address	Possible EU-PolarNet contact person + email (need a double check!)	General home page	Generic email	"Polarness" - i.e. at which events was the stakeholder active? (key to abbreviations under the sheet)	Target group
Energy (oil/gas)	association	International Association of Oil and Gas Producers (IOGP)	.	Worldwide	International	.	.	http://www.iogp.org/#	.	.	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy	semi public	Rosatom	.	Circumpolar	Russian Federation	Energy
Energy (oil/gas)	network	INTSOX	.	Worldwide	Norway	.	.	http://www.intsox.com/	.	A. Frontiers 15, 16 [*]; A. Dialogue 13;	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	Lundin Norway AS	second ary	Circumpolar	Norway	.	.	post@lundin-norway.no	.	A. Frontiers 15 [*]; High North Dialogue 15: Thorstein Sanness (managing director)	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	Subsea 7	.	Worldwide	Norway	.	.	http://www.subsea7.com/en/index.html	.	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	Aker Solutions	.	Worldwide	Norway	.	.	http://akersolutions.com/	online form http://akersolutions.com/contact/	A. Frontiers 15 [*]; A. Futures 16: Anders Storstenvik (engineering maanger);	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	GDF SUEZ E&P Norge	.	Norway	Norway	.	.	http://www.gdfsuezep.no/?sc_lang=en	.	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy	private sector	Petro Arctic (supplier network to oil industry)	.	Norway	Norway	.	.	http://www.petroarctic.no	.	A. Frontiers 15, 16 [*]; A. Business 16: organised workshop;	Energy
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	ConocoPhillips	.	Worldwide	International	.	.	http://go.econocophillips.com	online form http://www.conocophillips.com/Pages/contact-us.aspx	A. Frontiers 15, 16 [*]; A. Futures 16: Trond Erik Johansen (pres. Europe & N-Africa); A. Frontiers 16: very many attendees!; High North Dialogue 15: Johan S. Røe (gas revenue consultant); A. Open-water Meeting 13: Mike Faust (Chukchi program manager);	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	BP	.	Worldwide	United Kingdom	.	.	http://www.bp.com/	.	A. Frontiers 15 [*]; A. Open-water Meeting 13: Bill Strevler (environ. Studies leader);	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	semi public	China National Petroleum Corporation (CNPC)	.	Worldwide	China	.	.	http://www.cnpc.com.cn/en/	admin_eng@cnpc.com.cn	A. Frontiers 15 [*]; A. Circle 15: Huang Xuchun (head of contract and legal affairs);	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	NGO	World Petroleum Council	.	Worldwide	International	.	.	http://www.world-petroleum.org/	WPCSecretariat@world-petroleum.org	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	Norsk Olje og Gas AS	.	Norway	Norway	.	.	http://www.detnor.no/en/	jonas.gamre@detnor.no	High North Dialogue 15: Erling Kvadsheim (director)	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	Det Norske oljeselskap ASA	.	Norway	Norway	.	.	http://www.detnor.no/en/	detnor@detnor.no	A. Frontiers 15, 16 [*]	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy	private sector	Vitus Energy	.	United States	United States	.	.	http://vitus-energy.com/	info@vitumarine.com	.	Energy
Energy	semi public	National Power Company of Iceland (Orknustofnun)	.	Iceland	Iceland	.	.	http://www.landsvirkjun.com/	landsvirkjun@landsvirkjun.com	A. Energy Summit 13	Energy
Energy (oil/gas)	semi public	LUKOIL JSC	.	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	.	.	http://www.lukoil.com/	shareholder@lukoil.com	3rd Int. A. Forum: Vahid Alekperov (president); A. Frontiers 16: various participants	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	semi public	Surgutneftegas OJSC	.	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	.	.	http://www.surgutneftegas.ru/en/main/	invz@yandex.ru	3rd Int. A. Forum: Vladimir L. Bogdanov (general director)	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy	semi public	RusHydro JSC	second ary	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	.	.	http://www.eng.rushydro.ru	contact@gidrooigk.ru	3rd Int. A. Forum: Evgeny Dod (board's chairman)	Energy
Energy (oil/gas)	semi public	Gazprom Neft	?	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	.	.	http://www.gazprom-neft.com/	info@gazprom-neft.ru	3rd Int. A. Forum: Alexander Dyukov (general director)	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	semi public	Novatek	tertiary	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	.	.	http://www.novatek.ru/en/	novatek@novatek.ru	3rd Int. A. Forum: Gennaday Timchenko (board of dir. Member)	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	Rystad Energy	.	Worldwide	Denmark	.	.	http://www.rystadenergy.com/	info@rystadenergy.com	A. Summit 15: Jarand Rystad (maaging partner)	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	Eykon Energy	.	Northern Europe	Iceland	.	.	http://www.eykonenergy.com/	eykonenergy@eykonenergy.com	A. Circle 14: Heiðar M. Guðjónsson (chairman) ; A. Circle 15: idem Heiðar	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	CNOOC Limited	.	Worldwide	China	.	.	http://www.cnoocld.com/#1	IR@cnooc.com.cn	A. Circle 14: Li Fanrong (CEO) ;	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	British Petroleum (BP)	.	Worldwide	United Kingdom	.	.	http://www.bp.com/	.	A. Circle 14: Chuck Guderjahn (head of exploration) ;	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy	research centre	Alaska Center for Energy and Power, University of Alaska Fairbanks	.	United States	United States	.	.	http://acep.uaf.edu/	ACEP.info@alaska.edu	A. Circle 15: Gwen Holdman (director)	Energy
Energy	private sector	National Power Company of Iceland (Landsvirkjun)	.	Iceland	Iceland	.	.	http://www.landsvirkjun.com/	landsvirkjun@landsvirkjun.com	A. Circle 15: Hörður Arnarson (CEO) and others	Energy
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	Gaz Metro	.	Canada	Canada	.	.	http://www.gazmetro.com/en/	unknown	A. Circle 15: David Vincent (director of business development and renewable energies)	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy	governmental agency	SEV Faroe National Power Company	.	Faroe Islands	Faroe Islands	.	.	http://www.sev.fo/	sev@sev.fo	A. Circle 15: Håkan Djurhuus (managing director)	Energy
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	Chevron	.	Worldwide	United States	.	.	http://www.chevron.com/	online form http://www.chevron.com/contact/emailchevron/	A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy	semi public	Qulliq Energy Corporation	.	Canada	Canada	.	.	http://www.qec.nu.ca/home/ndex.php?option=com_frontpage&Itemid=1	customerservice@qec.nu.ca	A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Energy
Energy	private sector	Northern Cross Yukon	.	Canada	Canada	.	.	http://www.northerncrossyukon.ca/	feedback@northerncrossyukon.ca	A. Oil and Gas Symposium 16: Richard Wyman (president)	Energy
Energy	private sector	Lumos Energy	tertiary	Canada	Canada	.	.	http://www.lumosenergy.com/	chenderson@lumosenergy.com	Canada's North Summit 13: Chris Henderson (president); multiple A. Energy Summits	Energy
Energy	private sector	Yukon Energy Corporation	tertiary	Canada	Canada	.	.	http://www.yukonenergy.ca/	communications@yukonenergy.ca	Canada's North Summit 13: Michael Brandt (vice-pres.)	Energy
Energy (oil/gas)	private sector	Galp Energia	.	Worldwide	Portugal	.	.	http://www.galpennergia.com	galp@galpennergia.com	.	Energy (oil/gas)
Energy	Energy
Energy	Energy
Renewables	private sector	Tuuliwatti Oy	.	Finland	Finland	A. Energy Summit 15	Renewables
Renewables	private sector	UPM	.	Finland	Finland	Renewables
Renewables	private sector	Tuulikolmio Oy	.	Finland	Finland	Renewables
Renewables	private sector	Innower Oy	.	Finland	Finland	Renewables
Renewables	private sector	Fred. Olsen Renewables AS	.	Norway	Norway	Renewables
Renewables	private sector	Wpd Finland Oy	.	Finland	Finland	Renewables
Renewables	semi public	Vattenfall	.	Sweden	Sweden	Renewables

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Renewables	private sector	Svevind	-	Sweden	Sweden	-	-	-	-	-	Renewables
Renewables	private sector	Statkraft	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	-	-	-	Renewables
Renewables	private sector	Nordkraft	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	-	-	-	Renewables
Renewables	private sector	UMOE	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	http://www.umoe.com/	umoe@umoe.com	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Renewables
Renewables	association	European Wind Energy Association (EWEA)	-	Europe	Europe	-	-	http://www.eweae.org/	eweae@eweae.org	A. Circle 14: Thomas Becker (CEO)	Renewables
Renewables	private sector	Arctic Green Energy	-	Iceland	Iceland	-	-	http://www.arcticgreencorp.com/	info@arcticgreencorp.com	A. Circle 15: haukur Harðarson (chairman, founder)	Renewables
Renewables	semi public	Hydro Québec	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.hydroquebec.com/en/	unknown	A. Circle 15: Gaétan Lantagne (general manager)	Renewables
Renewables	private sector	TDX Power	tertiary ?	United States	United States	-	-	http://www.tdxpower.com/renewables	info@tdxpower.com	A. Energy Summit 15: Kord Christianson	Renewables
Renewables	private sector	Enercon	?	Europe	Germany	-	-	http://www.enercon.de/home/	vertrieb@enercon.de	A. Energy Summit 15: Bernard Moulines (commercial analyst)	Renewables
Renewables	private sector	Ocean Renewable Power Company (ORPC)	tertiary	United States	United States	-	-	http://www.orpc.co/	info@orpc.co	A. Energy Summit 15: Chris Sauer	Renewables
Renewables	private sector	Pembina Institute	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.pembina.org/	online form http://www.pembina.org/contact/ed-whittingham#contact	Canada's North Summit 13: Shauna Morgan (lead Northern programs)	Renewables
Renewables	private sector	EDP Renewables	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	http://www.edpr.com	-	-	Renewables
Renewables	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Renewables
Fisheries	government	Fisheries and Oceans Canada	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	-	-	-	Fisheries
Fisheries	private sector	Akvaplan-Niva (2)	-	Bipolar	Norway	-	-	http://www.akvaplan.niva.no/en/	-	A. Forum 15: Salve Dahle (Director); A. Frontiers 15, 16 [*] (large delegation)	Fisheries
Fisheries	association	Norwegian Fishermen's Association	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	http://www.fiskarlaget.no/index.php/english/details/473/36-welcome-to-norges-fiskarlag	-	A. Forum 15: Julian Vangen (Advisor)	Fisheries
Fisheries	NGO	The Pew Charitable Trust (1)	-	Worldwide	United States	-	-	http://www.pewtrusts.org/en	partnerships@pewtrusts.org	-	Fisheries
Fisheries	commission	North East Atlantic Fisheries Commission (NEAFC)	-	North Atlantic	International: Europe	-	-	http://www.neafc.org/	info@neafc.org	-	Fisheries
Fisheries	commission	Northwest Atlantic Fisheries Organization (NAFO)	-	North Atlantic	International	-	-	http://www.nafo.int/	info@nafo.int	Int. A. Fisheries Symposium 09: Kjartan Hoydal	Fisheries
Fisheries	commission	North Pacific Fishery Management Council (NOAA)	-	North Pacific	International	-	-	http://www.npfmc.org/	npfmc.comments@noaa.gov	Int. A. Fisheries Symposium 09: Bill Wilson, A. Open-water Meeting 13; A. Observing Summit 16: David M Kennedy;	Fisheries
Fisheries	association	Groundfish Forum	-	North Pacific	International	-	-	http://groundfishforum.org/	chrisw@seanet.com	Int. A. Fisheries Symposium 09: Lori Swanson	Fisheries
Fisheries	private sector	Norwegian Fishermen's Sales Organization (Norges Råfisklag)	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	http://www.rafisklaget.no/	firmapost@rafisklaget.no	A. Futures 15: Julien Vangen (analyst)	Fisheries
Fisheries	association	Association of Responsible Krill Harvesting Companies (ARK KRILL)	-	Antarctic	International	-	-	http://www.ark-krill.org/	info@ark-krill.org	-	Fisheries
Fisheries	private sector	Insung Seafood	-	Antarctic	South Korea	-	-	http://www.insungnet.co.kr/main.php	johnlee@insungnet.co.kr	-	Fisheries
Fisheries	association	Coalition of Legal Toothfish Operators (COLTO)	-	Antarctic	International	-	-	http://www.colto.org/	contact@colto.com	-	Fisheries
Fisheries	private sector	AkerBioMarine	-	Antarctic	Norway	-	-	http://www.akerbiomarine.com/	post@akerbiomarine.com	-	Fisheries
Fisheries	council	Marine Stewardship Council	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	https://www.msc.org/	online form https://www.msc.org/about-us/offices-staff/email-us	-	Fisheries
Fisheries	private sector	Iceland Ocean Cluster	-	Iceland	Iceland	-	-	http://www.sjavarklasinn.is/en/	sjavarklasinn@sjavarklasinn.is	A. Circle 14: Thor Sigusson (CEO) ;	Fisheries
Fisheries	private sector	Codland (research and development)	-	Iceland	Iceland	-	-	http://codland.is/	tomas@codland.is	A. Circle 14: Erla Ó. Pétursdóttir (CEO)	Fisheries
Fisheries	semi public	Royal Greenland	-	Greenland	Greenland	-	-	http://www.royalgreenland.com	online form http://www.royalgreenland.com/uk/Our-company/Contact-us.aspx	-	Fisheries
Fisheries (aquaculture)	institute	NCE Aquaculture	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	http://nceaquaculture.com/english/	ilk@kpb.no	A. Circle 14: Stal Heggelund (managing director); A. Business 16: workshop partner;	Fisheries (aquaculture)
Fisheries	private sector	HB Grandi	-	Iceland	Iceland	-	-	http://www.hbgrandi.com/	online form http://www.hbgrandi.com/	A. Circle 15; Svavar Svavarsson (business dev.) ;	Fisheries
Fisheries	private sector	Marine Harvest Group	-	Worldwide	Norway	-	-	http://www.marineharvest.com/	unknown	A. Futures 16 and A. Frontiers 16: Alf-Helge Aarskog (CEO)	Fisheries
Fisheries	association	Fisheries Iceland	-	Iceland	Iceland	-	-	unknown	unknown	A. Futures 16: Kolbeinn Arnson (CEO); A. Frontiers 16: idem Kolbeinn	Fisheries
Fisheries (aquaculture)	private sector	AKVA group	-	Worldwide	Norway	-	-	http://www.akvagroup.com/home	pahjetland@akvagroup.com	A. Futures 16: Trond Williksen (CEO)	Fisheries (aquaculture)
Fisheries (aquaculture)	private sector	NOFI	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	http://www.nofi.no/en/	post@nofi.no	A. Futures 16: Dag Nilsen (business dev. Director)	Fisheries (aquaculture)
Fisheries	private sector	Nergård	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	http://nergard.no/about-us	morten.hermansen@nergard.no	A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Fisheries
Fisheries	association	Norwegian Seafood Federation (Sjømat Norge)	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	http://sjomatnorge.no/norwegian-seafood-federation/	firmapost@sjomatnorge.no	High North Dialogue 15, 16: Geir Ove Ystmark (CEO);	Fisheries
Fisheries (aquaculture)	private sector	Russian Aquaculture	-	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	-	-	http://russaquaculture.ru/index.php?id=1&L=2	invest@russaquaculture.ru	-	Fisheries (aquaculture)
Fisheries	private sector	Samherji	-	Iceland	Iceland	-	-	http://www.samherji.is/en	samherji@samherji.is	-	Fisheries
Fisheries	private sector	Polar Seafood	-	Greenland	Denmark	-	-	http://www.polarseafood.dk	polar@polarseafood.dk	-	Fisheries
Fisheries	private sector	Lofoten Seafood	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	http://www.lofotenseafood.com/	post@lofotenseafood.com	-	Fisheries
Fisheries	private sector	Petuna Seafood	-	Antarctic	Australia	-	-	http://www.petuna.com.au/	office@petuna.com	-	Fisheries

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Fisheries (aquaculture)	private sector	MacAlister Elliott & Partners consultants	tertiary	Kerguelen; Worldwide; Antarctic	UK	-	-	http://www.macalister-elliott.com/contact.php	mep@macalister-elliott.com	-	Fisheries (aquaculture)
Fisheries	private sector	Olympic Seafood	-	Antarctic	Norway	-	-	http://www.olympicseafood.com	bjornar.kleiven@olympic.no, inge.brueheim@olympic.no	-	Fisheries
Fisheries	institute	Instituto Português do Mar e da Atmosfera (IPMA)	-	Portugal	Portugal	-	-	http://www.ipma.pt	info@ipma.pt	-	Fisheries
Fisheries	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Fisheries
Fisheries	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Fisheries
Shipping	NGO	International Maritime Organization (IMO)	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	-	-	A. Summit 15: Koji Sekimizu (secretary-general); A. Futures 16: Ashok Mahapatra (director of maritime safety division); 5th/7th A. Shipping Summit: Sandra Allnut (head marine technology); ShipArc 15: various speakers; Poles Apart 13: Heike Degelm.	Shipping
Shipping	NGO	World Ocean Council (WOC)	-	Worldwide	International	Paul Hothus <@woc.org>;	-	http://www.woc.org	-	A. Circle 14; ShipArc 15: Christine Valentine (Europ. Liaison officer); A. Business 16: organised workshop; A. Observing Summit 16: Paul Hothus;	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Eimskip	-	Circumpolar	Iceland	-	-	-	-	-	Shipping
Shipping	semi public	COSCO	-	Worldwide	China	-	-	-	-	A. Circle 14: Ye Weilong (vice-pr.) ; A. Circle 15: Cai Meijiang (general manager) ;	Shipping
Shipping	association	Danish Shipowners' Association	-	Denmark	Denmark	-	-	-	-	A. Forum 15: Morten Glamsø (Senior Adviser); Anne H. Steffensen (General Director); A. Futures 15: Anne H. Steffensen (CEO); A. Futures 16: idem Anne; A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Shipping
Shipping	association	Norwegian Shipowners Association	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	https://www.rederi.no/en/	post@rederi.no	A. Forum 15: Ingrid Kystad (Brussels representative); A. Business Conference 14: Sturla Hendriksen (CEO) [workshopper]; High North Dialogue 15: Hanna L. Behrens (director security, environm., innov.); Poles Apart 13: idem Sturla; A. Business 16: idem Sturla;	Shipping
Shipping	association	Chamber of Shipping America	-	America; Circumpolar	United States	-	-	http://www.knowships.org/	-	6th A. Shipping Summit 15: Joe Cox (President);	Shipping
Shipping	association	Company of Master Mariners of Canada	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	-	-	A. Shipping Summit 15: Jack Gallagher (National Executive)	Shipping
Shipping	association	Petro-Nav, Groupe Desagnés	-	Canada	Canada	Christopher King <christopher.king@petro.nav.desagnes.com>;	-	-	-	A. Shipping Summit 15: Jack Gallagher (National Executive)	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Tschudi	-	Circumpolar	Norway	-	-	http://www.tschudiarctic.com/	uh@tschudiarctictransit.com	A. Frontiers 15, 16 [*]; 3rd Int. A. Forum: Felix Tschudi (owner, CEO); A. Futures 16: idem Felix; High North Dialogue 15: idem Felix; The Alaskan Arctic 15: idem Tschudi; Poles Apart 13: idem Tschudi; A. Business 16: idem Tschudi; High North Dialogue 16: idem Tschudi;	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Arctia Shipping	at least secondary	Circumpolar	Finland	Tero Vauraste <Tero.Vauraste@arctia.fi>;	-	http://arctia.fi/en/	rekry@arctia.fi	A. Frontiers 15 [*]; A. Encounter 16; 3rd Int. A. Forum: Tero Vauraste (CEO); A. Summit 14: idem Tero ; A. Circle 14: idem Tero ; A. Circle 15: idem Tero ; A. Shipping Forum 16: Juka Salminen (chartering engineer); 5th A. Shipping Summit: idem Tero; ShipArc 15: idem Tero	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Maersk	-	Worldwide	Denmark	-	Toby Croucher <toby.croucher@maersk.com>;	http://www.maersk.com	-	-	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Splithoff	-	Worldwide	Netherlands	-	-	http://www.splithoff.com/	online form http://www.splithoff.com/	-	Shipping
Shipping	semi public	Royal Arctic Line (RAL)	-	Bipolar	Greenland	-	Jens Boye <jbo@ral.dk>;	http://www.ral.gl	-	A. Futures 14	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Tactical Marine Solutions Ltd.	-	Circumpolar	Canada	-	-	http://tactmarine.com/arctic-expertise.php	info@tactmarine.com	A. Energy Summit 13: Dermot Loughane; A. Circle 14: idem Dermot; A. Shipping Forum 16: idem Dermot (CEO) and others	Shipping
Shipping	committee	Arctic Waters Safety Committee	-	United States	United States	-	-	http://www.arcticwaterways.org/g/attorneys-1.html	online form http://www.arcticwaterways.org/contact.html	A. Encounter 16	Shipping
Shipping	government(al)	Atomflot (Rosatomflot)	-	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	-	-	http://www.rosatomflot.ru/index.php?menuid=25&lang=en	online form http://www.rosatomflot.ru/index.php?menuid=24&lang=en	A. Energy Summit 13; 3rd Int. A. Forum: Vyacheslav Ruksha (general dir.); 5th A. Shipping Summit: Mikhail Belkin (assist. Director) and others; A. Dialogue 13: Mikhail Belkin (assist. Director General);	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Aker Arctic	-	Circumpolar	Finland	Reko-Antti Suojanen <reko-antti.suojanen@akerarctic.fi>;	-	http://akerarctic.fi/en/	info@akerarctic.fi	A. Energy Summit 13; 3rd Int. A. Forum: Mikko Niemi (general dir.); Arctic Energy Summit 15: Reko-Antti Suojanen (managing director); A. Shipping Forum: idem Reko-Antti and others; A. Exchange 15: Arno Keinonen	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	SEVMASH	-	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	-	-	http://www.sevmash.ru/en/	smp@sevmash.ru	A. Energy Summit 13: Valery Borodin	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Viking Supply Ships AS	-	Sweden	Sweden	-	-	http://www.vikingsupply.com	info@vikingsupply.com	3rd Int. A. Forum: Anders Backman (president of the ice committee)	Shipping
Shipping	semi public	Safety Comes First (SCF) (Sovcomflot JSC)	-	Circumpolar	Russian Federation	-	-	http://www.scf-group.com/en/	info@scf-group.ru	3rd Int. A. Forum: Sergey Frank (director general); 7th A. Shipping Summit: Vladimir Udalov (general manager) and others	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Nordic Bulk Carriers	-	Circumpolar	unknown	Mads Boye Peterson <m@nordic-bulk.com>;	-	http://www.nordicbulkcarriers.com/	ops@nordic-bulk.com	A. Summit 15: Christian Bonfils (CEO); A. Summit 14: idem Christian;	Shipping
Shipping	association	International Chamber of Shipping	tertiary?	Worldwide	International	-	-	http://www.ics-shipping.org/	info@ics-shipping.org	5th A. Shipping Summit: Alistair Hull (technical manager); ShipArc 15: Peter Hitchcliffe	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Daewoo Shipbuilding and Marine Engineering (DSME)	-	Worldwide	South Korea	-	-	http://www.dsme.co.kr/epub/main/index.do	-	A. Summit 15: Ohyig Kwon (vice-pr.); A. Circle 14: idem Ohyig	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Fednav Arctic Operations	-	Worldwide	United States	Marie-Andrée Giguère <MGiguere@fednav.com>;	-	http://www.fednav.com/en/about-us	-	A. Summit 14: Tom Paterson (senior vice-pr.); A. Shipping Forum 16: Tim Keane (senior manager)	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Portnews (1)	-	Worldwide	Russian Federation	-	-	http://en.portnews.ru/about/	snitko@portnews.ru	-	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Martech Polar Consulting	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://martechpolar.com/about-us	info@martechpolar.com	A. Shipping Forum 16: David Snider (CEO)	Shipping

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Shipping	private sector	Nautical Institute Ice Navigator Working Group	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	A. Circle 14: David Snider (vice-pr. NI) and Victor Gronmyr (working group member)	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Marorka (nautical consultancy) [1]	-	Worldwide	Iceland	-	-	http://www.marorka.com/	marorka@marorka.com	A. Circle 14: Jón Á. Þorsteinsson (chairman) ; A. circle 15: idem Jón	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Larsen Marine Oil Recovery (LAMOR)	-	Worldwide	Finland	-	-	http://www.lamor.com/es/	info@lamor.com	A. Shipping Summit 1x; A. Shipping Forum 16: Arune Hogstrom (COO)	Shipping
Shipping	union	International Union of Marine Insurance (IUMI)	??	Worldwide	International	-	-	http://www.iumi.com/	lars.lange@iumi.com	-	Shipping
Shipping	union	Nordic Association of marine Insurers (Cefor)	??	Nordic countries	Nordic countries	-	-	http://www.cefor.no/	cefor@cefor.no	A. Shipping Forum 16: Helle Hammer (managing director)	Shipping
Shipping	association	German Association for Marine Technology (GMT)	tertiary ?	Worldwide	Germany	-	-	http://www.maritime-technik.de/en-index.php	gmt@maritime-technik.de	A. Circle 15: Walter L. Kuehnlein (chairman)	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Bremenports GmbH	-	Germany	Germany	-	-	http://www.bremenports.de/en/company	online form http://www.bremenports.de/en/company/contact/contact-form	A. Circle 15: Robert Howe (managing director) ;	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	North Japan Port Consultants	tertiary ?	Circumpolar	Japan	-	-	http://white-sapporo.sakura.ne.jp/index2e.html	online form http://white-sapporo.sakura.ne.jp/form_e.html	A. Circle 15: Natsukiko Otsuka (management planning manager)	Shipping
Shipping	NGO	Clean Shipping Coalition	-	Worldwide	Belgium	-	-	http://www.cleanshipping.org/	info@cleanshipping.org	A. Circle 15: John Maggs (president)	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Olympic Shipping	-	Worldwide	Norway	-	-	http://www.olympic.no/	-	A. Futures 16: Stig Remøy (CEO)	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Sevan Marine	-	Worldwide	Norway	-	-	http://www.sevanmarine.com/	post@sevanmarine.com	A. Futures 16: Fredrik Major; A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Damen Shipyards	-	Worldwide	Japan	-	-	http://www.damen.com/	info@damen.com	A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Crowley Maritime	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	http://www.crowley.com/	online form http://www.crowley.com/Contact-Us/List-of-Offices	A. Energy Summit 15: Bruce Harland	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Arctech Helsinki Shipyard Inc.	-	Circumpolar	Finland	-	-	http://arctech.fi/	info@arctech.fi	A. Shipping Forum 16: Marrku Kajosaari (SVP sales)	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Ice Advisors	-	Circumpolar	Finland	-	Kari Kosonen	http://www.iceadvisors.fi/	info@finnpilot.fi	A. Exchange 15: Erik Almkvist and Jan Persson	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Polaris ERT	-	Circumpolar	Malta	-	-	http://polaris-ert.com/	info@polaris-ert.com	A. Exchange 15: Arron Rawdings (managing director)	Shipping
Shipping	governmental agency	Danish Maritime Authority (DMA)	-	Denmark, Greenland	Denmark	-	-	http://www.dma.dk/Sider/Hom_e.aspx	sfs@dma.dk	A. Cruise Conference 14: Farnis Zachariae (dep. Direct. General) and others	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	A. J. Gonçalves de Moraes, S.A.	-	Worldwide	Portugal	-	Vitor Salazar	http://www.moraes.pt/	vs@mail.moraes.pt	-	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	L.Branco – Navegação e Tránsitos	-	Worldwide	Portugal	-	Luis Branco	http://www.l-branco.com/	info@l-branco.com	-	Shipping
Shipping	private sector	Associação David Melgueiro	-	Worldwide	Portugal	-	-	http://davidmelgueiro.org.webnode.pt/associacao/	davidmelgueiro14@gmail.com	-	Shipping
Shipping	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Shipping
Shipping	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Shipping
Shipping	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Shipping
Mixed oil, engineering, shipping, logistics	private sector	Kongsberg Group (1)	-	Worldwide	Norway	-	-	http://www.kongsberg.com/	office@kongsberg.com	A. Futures 16: Walter Quam (CEO) and Sören Themann (vice-pres. Of subea monitoring); A Frontiers 16: various attendees; A. Business 16: Christian Hauglie-Hanssen (EVP Space & Surveillance) [blogger for event] and idem Walter (CEO);	Mixed oil, engineering, shipping, logistics
Mixed oil, engineering, shipping, logistics	private sector	National Oilwell Varco (NOV)	-	Worldwide	United States	-	-	-	-	A. Futures 16: Hege Kverneland (vice-pres.)	Mixed oil, engineering, shipping, logistics
Mixed oil, engineering, shipping, logistics	private sector	GCE NODE	-	Worldwide	Norway	-	-	http://gcenode.no/	unknown	A. Futures 16: various speakers; A. Frontiers 16: various attendees	Mixed oil, engineering, shipping, logistics
Mixed oil, engineering, shipping, logistics	private sector	Nuka Research consultancy	-	United States	United States	-	-	http://www.nukaresearch.com/	-	The Alaskan Arctic 15: Tim Robertson (general manager)	Mixed oil, engineering, shipping, logistics
Mixed oil, engineering, shipping, logistics	private sector	Sembcorp Marine	-	Worldwide	Singapore	-	-	http://www.sembcorpmarine.com.sg/	-	A. Business 16: Wong Weng Sun (President & CEO);	Mixed oil, engineering, shipping, logistics
Mixed oil, engineering, shipping, logistics	private sector	Fugro	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	http://www.fugro.com/	holding@fugro.com	A. Observing Summit 16: Rada Khadjinova;	Mixed oil, engineering, shipping, logistics
Mixed oil, engineering, shipping, logistics	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Mixed oil, engineering, shipping, logistics
Transport and logistics; energy	semi public	Gassco	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	-	-	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Transport and logistics; energy
Transport and logistics	private sector	Pole Position Logistics	-	Norway	Norway	-	Terje Aunevik <Terje@pole-position.no>;	http://www.pole-position.no/	mail@pole-position.no	-	Transport and logistics
Transport and logistics	private sector	NorSeaGroup	-	Norway	Norway	-	Kenneth Bjorholm <Kenneth.Bjorholm@norseagroup.com>;	http://www.norseagroup.com	norseagroup@norseagroup.com	-	Transport and logistics
Transport and logistics	private sector	DNV GL (Det Norske Veritas)	primary	Worldwide	Norway	-	Knut Orbeck-Nilsen <Knut.Orbeck-Nilsen@dnv.com>;	http://www.dnv.com/moreondn v/profile/about_us/	-	A. Energy Summit 13; A. Summit 15: Elisabeth Tørstad (CEO) ; A. Summit 14: Knut Orbeck-Nilsen (maritime president) ; A. Circle 14: Bruno Ferreyra (CEO of Industry&Facilities Business) ; A. Futures 16: idem Elisabeth; A. Frontiers 16: various participants; High North Dialogue 15: Børre Paaske (leader of Safety Risk Manager); A. Shipping Forum 16: various speakers; A. Business 16: A. Business 14: Elisabeth Tørstad (CEO Oil & Gas) [workshopper]	Transport and logistics
Transport and logistics	network	Northern Dimension Partnership on Transport and Logistics (NDPTL)	-	Northern Europe	International	-	-	http://www.ndptl.org/	ndptl@ndptl.org	-	Transport and logistics

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Transport and logistics	private sector	Centre for High North Logistics (CHNL)	-	Circumpolar	Norway	-	-	http://www.chnl.no/	post@chnl.no	A. Circle 14: Tschudi (chairman); A. Shipping Forum 16: Sergey Balmasov (head of NRS info office); A. Business 16: organised workshop; A. Dialogue 13: Bjørn Gunnarsson (ARCTIS project);	Transport and logistics
Transport and logistics	private sector	Arctic Marine Solutions (AMS)	-	Bipolar	Sweden	-	-	http://www.arcticmarinesolutions.com/about-ams.html	info@arcticmarinesolutions.com	-	Transport and logistics
Transport and logistics	semi public	Air Greenland	-	Greenland	Greenland	-	-	http://www.airgreenland.gl	-	A. Circle 15: Hans Peter Hansen (director)	Transport and logistics
Transport and logistics	private sector	First Arctic	tertiary	Circumpolar	Denmark	-	-	http://firstarctic.com/	cb@firstarctic.com	A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Transport and logistics
Transport and logistics	private sector	Bureau Veritas	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	http://www.bureauveritas.com/	online form http://www.bureauveritas.com/footer/contact/	6th/8th A. Shipping Forum: Philippe Cambos (technical director)	Transport and logistics
Transport and logistics	private sector	Antarctic Logistics	-	Antarctic	United States	-	-	http://antarctic-logistics.com/	info@antarctic-logistics.com	-	Transport and logistics
Transport and logistics	private sector	Arctic Services	-	Iceland	Iceland	Elva Gunnlaugsdóttir <elva@afe.is>;	-	http://www.arctic-services.is/en/our-service	http://www.arctic-services.is/en/our-service	-	Transport and logistics
Transport and logistics	private sector	Kaukokiito Oy	-	-	-	-	Juha Korpikari <juha.korpikari@kaukokiito.fi>;	http://www.kaukokiito.fi/eng#p/kaukokiito/paivin	-	-	Transport and logistics
Transport and logistics	private sector	Arctic Corridor	-	Barents Region	Barents Region	-	-	http://www.arcticcorridor.fi/	online form http://www.arcticcorridor.fi/contact-us/	A. Business 16: Timo Lohi (Project manager Sodankylä municip.) [blogger for event];	Transport and logistics
Transport and logistics	private sector	Polar Field Services	-	Worldwide	United States	-	-	http://polarfield.com/	info@polarfield.com	A. Business 16: Bill Ewing (COO);	Transport and logistics
Transport and logistics	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Transport and logistics
Transport and logistics	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Transport and logistics
Transport and logistics	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Transport and logistics
Transport and logistics	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Transport and logistics
Forestry	private sector	Metsähallitus Forest Management	-	Finland	Finland	-	Kirsi-Marja Korhonen <kirsi-marja.korhonen@metsa.fi>;	www.metsa.fi/web/en	-	-	Forestry
Forestry	private sector	Stora Enso	-	Finland	Finland	-	-	http://www.storaenso.com/	-	A. Mining	Forestry
Forestry	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Forestry
Forestry	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Forestry
Food and agriculture	association	International Centre for Reindeer Husbandry (AWRI) (1)	-	Circumpolar	Norway	-	-	-	-	3rd Int. A. Forum: various; A. Frontier 15: A. Energy Summit 15: Anders Oskal; A. Observing Summit 16: Anders Oskal (Exec. Director)	Food and agriculture
Food and agriculture	association	Circumpolar Agriculture Association (CAA)	-	Circumpolar	International	-	-	http://www.bioforsk.no/kb/viewer/page/prosjekt/forside?p_dimension_id=19718&p_menu_id=19722&p_sub_id=19717&p_dim2=19717	ulrike.naumann@bioforsk.no	Circumpolar Agricultural Conference 13: Torfi Jóhannesson (Vice-pres.)	Food and agriculture
Food and agriculture	international organisation	Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the UN	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	http://www.fao.org/home/en/	fao-hq@fao.org	-	Food and agriculture
Food and agriculture	association	Yukon Agricultural Association	tertiary	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.yukonag.ca/	admin@yukonag.ca	Circumpolar Agricultural Conference 13: Kirsten Scott	Food and agriculture
Food and agriculture	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Food and agriculture
Engineering (architecture)	private sector	Lateral North	tertiary	Circumpolar	United Kingdom	-	-	http://lateralnorth.com/	office@lateralnorth.com	A. Circle 15: Tom Smith (director); A. Frontiers 16 [*]; A. Energy Summit 15: Graham Hogg	Engineering (architecture)
Engineering (architecture)	private sector	Lateral Office	-	Circumpolar	Canada	-	-	http://lateraloffice.com/	studio@lateraloffice.com	-	Engineering (architecture)
Engineering (architecture)	private sector	70°N Arkitektur	-	Circumpolar	Norway	-	-	http://www.70n.no/	firmapost@70n.no	-	Engineering (architecture)
Engineering (architecture)	private sector	Danish Architecture Centre (DAC)	-	Denmark, Greenland	Denmark	-	-	http://www.dac.dk/en	ch@dac.dk	-	Engineering (architecture)
Engineering (architecture)	private sector	Design Alaska	tertiary	United States	United States	-	-	http://www.designalaska.com/	mail@designalaska.com	A. Energy Summit 15: Lyle Axelarris	Engineering (architecture)
Engineering (architecture)	association	Arctic Design Group	-	Circumpolar	International	-	Matthew Hull <mj5kh@virginia.edu>;	http://arcticdesigngroup.org/	office@kutonotuk.com	-	Engineering (architecture)
Engineering (architecture)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Engineering (architecture)
Engineering (architecture)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Engineering (architecture)
Engineering	private sector	Ramboll (Rambøll)	-	Worldwide	Denmark	-	-	-	-	Mining and Mineral Industry of the Future 16: Franciska Herodes (Business Area Manager); A. Frontiers 15, 16 [*]; A. Circle 14, 15: nils A. Johnson (A. director); A.	Engineering
Engineering	private sector	Rambøll Greenland	-	Greenland	Greenland	-	-	-	-	A. Circle 15: Henrik Fenger Jeppesen (CEO)	Engineering
Engineering	private sector	Grontmij	-	Worldwide	Netherlands	-	-	-	-	-	Engineering

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Engineering	private sector	Sweco	.	Sweden	Sweden	.	.	http://www.swecogroup.com/en/Sweco-group/Solutions/	.	Mining and Mineral Industry of the Future 16: Martin Sandberg (Traffic and Infrastr. Strategist, Bothnian Corridor);	Engineering
Engineering	private sector	Royal HaskoningDHV	.	Worldwide	Netherlands	Coco Smits <coco.smits@rhdhv.com>	.	http://www.royalhaskoningdhv.com/	online form http://www.royalhaskoningdhv.com/en-eb/contact	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Engineering
Engineering	private sector	Mannvit (1)	.	Circumpolar	Iceland	.	.	http://www.mannvit.com	mannvit@mannvit.com	.	Engineering
Engineering	private sector	ABB	.	Worldwide	Switzerland	.	.	http://new.abb.com	?	A. Business 14: J Nergard (VP Business Dev.) [workshopper]; A. Energy Summit 15: William Galton (microgrid project manager)	Engineering
Engineering	private sector	Boskalis	.	Worldwide	Netherlands	.	.	http://www.boskalis.com/	online form http://www.boskalis.com/nc/about-us/contact/contact-details.html	.	Engineering
Engineering	private sector	EFLA Consulting Engineers	.	Iceland	Iceland	.	.	http://www.efla-engineers.com/	efla@efla.is; gudmundur.thorbjornsson@efla.is	A. Circle 14 and 15: various speakers	Engineering
Engineering	private sector	LNS (Leonhard Nilsen & Sønner)	.	Circumpolar	Norway	.	.	http://eng.lns.no/	firmapost@lns.no	A. Circle 14: Frank Jabobsen (LNS Spitsbergen director); High North Dialogue 16: Frode M Nilsen (CEO);	Engineering
Engineering	private sector	NR Europe	tertiary	Europe	unknown	.	.	http://nreurope.com/	info@nreurope.com	A. Circle 14: Irina Tchoumatchenko (president)	Engineering
Engineering	private sector	SE2T	.	Worldwide	France	.	.	http://se2t.fr/contact/	online form http://se2t.fr/contact/	A. Circle 15: Sergio C. Trindade (pres.)	Engineering
Engineering	private sector	Verkis	.	Circumpolar	Iceland	.	.	http://www.verkis.com/	online form http://www.verkis.com/contact-us	A. Circle 15: Sveinn I. Ólafsson (CEO) and others	Engineering
Engineering	private sector	AECOM	.	Worldwide	United States	.	.	http://www.aecom.com/	online form http://www.aecom.com/contact-us/	A. Energy Summit 15: Jon Isaacs	Engineering
Engineering	private sector	Michael Baker	tertiary	United States	United States	.	.	http://www.mbakertnt.com/Regions	online form http://www.mbakertnt.com/Contact	A. Energy Summit 15: Suzanne Ban	Engineering
Engineering	private sector	Ahma Engineers Group Oy	tertiary	Finland	Finland	.	Antti Kuivalainen <antti.kuivalainen@ahma-group.com>	.	.	.	Engineering
Engineering	private sector	Tekever	.	Worldwide	Portugal	.	.	http://www.tekever.com	info@tekever.com	.	Engineering
Engineering	Engineering
Engineering	Engineering
Engineering	Engineering
Industry (other)	semi public	Stora Enso Oyj	.	Circumpolar	Finland	Industry (other)
Industry (other)	private sector	Manga LNG Oy	.	Bipolar	Finland	Industry (other)
Industry (other)	semi public	Outokumpu Stainless Steel	.	Bipolar	Finland	A. Business Forum 15: martti Sassi (senior vice-pres.)	Industry (other)
Industry (other)	private sector	Microsoft	.	Circumpolar	United States	Industry (other)
Industry (other)	private sector	Akzo Nobel	.	Bipolar	Netherlands	Industry (other)
Industry (other)	private sector	Facebook	.	Worldwide	International	Industry (other)
Industry (other)	private sector	SSAB	.	Sweden	Sweden	Industry (other)
Industry (other)	private sector	Steeldone Group	.	Finland	Finland	.	.	http://www.steeldone.com/en/contact/	.	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Industry (other)
Industry (other)	private sector	Tapojarvi Oy	.	Nordic countries	Finland	.	.	http://www.tapojarvi.com/en/	tapojarvioy@tapojarvi.fi,	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Industry (other)
Industry (other)	semi public	Alcoa	.	Worldwide	United States	.	.	http://www.alcoa.com/	.	.	Industry (other)
Industry (other)	private sector	Neste Oil (refineries)	.	Worldwide	Finland	.	.	https://www.neste.com/en	.	.	Industry (other)
Industry (other)	private sector	Ferral Components Oy	tertiary	Finland	Finland	.	.	http://www.ferral.fi/en/	sales@ferral.fi	A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Industry (other)
Industry (other)	private sector	Outokumpu Stainless Oy	.	Finland	Finland	.	Pekka Harjuoja <pekka.harjuoja@outokumpu.com>	.	.	.	Industry (other)
Industry (other)	Industry (other)
Industry (other)	Industry (other)
Insurances	private sector	Charles Taylor	.	Worldwide	United Kingdom	.	.	http://www.ctplc.com/who-we-are/	.	A. Shipping Summit 15: Leanne O'Loughlin (Claims Director)	Insurances
Insurances	private sector	Lloyd's	.	Worldwide	International	.	.	http://www.lloyds.com/	enquiries@lloyds.com	A. Summit 14: Tom Bolt (director of performance) ; A. Circle 14: Tom Boardley (Lloyd's of London) on (Ant)A. activities;	Insurances
Insurances	private sector	Lloyd's Register	.	Worldwide	International	.	.	http://www.lr.org/en/	online form http://www.lr.org/en/contact-us/	A. Business 16: Rob Hindley (Lead specialist of Arctic Technology) [blogger for event];	Insurances
Insurances	NGO	ShareAction	.	Worldwide	unknown	.	.	http://www.shareaction.org/contact	info@shareaction.org	A. Summit 14: Louise Rouse (director of engagement) ;	Insurances
Insurances	private sector	Arctic Insurance	.	Circumpolar	Norway	.	.	http://www.arcticinsurance.no/en/	mail@arcticinsurance.no	.	Insurances
Insurances	private sector	XL Catlin	.	Worldwide	unknown	.	.	http://xlcatlin.com/	online form http://xlcatlin.com/reinsurance/contact-reinsurance-company/email-xl-reinsurance-company	.	Insurances
Insurances	private sector	Gard	.	Worldwide	Norway	.	.	http://www.gard.no/	companymail@gard.no	A. Shipping Forum 16: Malin P. Gustavi (lawyer)	Insurances
Insurances	private sector	Skuld	.	Worldwide	Norway	A. Business 16: Ståle Hansen (CEO)	Insurances
Insurances	Insurances

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Finance industry and (private) funding	private sector	Impax Asset Management	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	http://www.impaxam.com/	-	-	Finance industry and (private) funding
Finance industry and (private) funding	governmental fund	Nordic Environment Finance Corporation (NEFCO) (1)	-	Worldwide	Nordic countries	-	-	http://www.nefco.org/	info@nefco.fi	3rd Int. A. Forum: Amund Beytnes (chief investment manager) and Magnus Ristedt (managing dir.)	Finance industry and (private) funding
Finance industry and (private) funding	private sector	DNB Bank ASA	-	Worldwide	Norway	-	-	https://www.dnb.no/en/	-	A. Summit 15: Harald Serck-Hanssen (group executive vice-pr.)	Finance industry and (private) funding
Finance industry and (private) funding	international organisation	European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD)	-	Europe	Europe	-	-	http://www.ebrd.com/home	EdmondsT@ebrd.com	-	Finance industry and (private) funding
Finance industry and (private) funding	governmental fund	Nordic Investment Bank (NIB)	-	Nordic countries	Nordic countries	-	-	http://www.nib.int/	info@nib.int	-	Finance industry and (private) funding
Finance industry and (private) funding	private sector	Guggenheim Partners	-	Worldwide	United States	-	-	https://www.guggenheimpartners.com/	online form https://www.guggenheimpartners.com/contact	A. Circle 14, 15: Scott Miner (global chief investm. Officer); A. Futures 16: Michael Perkinson (A. Investment Protocol); A. Frontiers 16: idem Michael; The Alaskan Arctic 15: idem Scott; A. Energy Summit 15: idem Michael; A. Business 16: idem Scott.	Finance industry and (private) funding
Research	private sector	Tekes	-	Finland	Finland	-	-	https://www.tekes.fi/en/	-	-	Research
Finance industry and (private) funding	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Finance industry and (private) funding
Finance industry and (private) funding	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Finance industry and (private) funding
Finance industry and (private) funding	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Finance industry and (private) funding
Finance industry and (private) funding	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Finance industry and (private) funding
Tourism	association	Association of Arctic Expedition Cruise Operators (AECO)	-	Circumpolar	Norway	Frigg Jørgensen <frigg@aeco.no>	-	-	-	A. Circle 14: Ilja L. Lang (office manager); A. Circle 15: Ilja Leo Lang (office manager DK); A. Shipping Forum 16; ShipArc 15: idem Ilja; all AECO Cruise Conferences;	Tourism
Tourism	LINK	Link to AECO members: http://www.aeco.no/members/	-	Circumpolar	International	-	-	http://www.aeco.no/members/	-	-	Tourism
Tourism	association	International Association of Antarctica Tour Operators (IAATO)	-	Antarctic	International	-	-	http://iaato.org/	-	-	Tourism
Tourism	LINK	Link to IAATO members: http://apps.iaato.org/iaato/member/list.xhtml	-	Antarctic	International	-	-	http://apps.iaato.org/iaato/member/list.xhtml	online form http://iaato.org/es/contact-us	-	Tourism
Tourism	private sector	High Latitudes	-	Antarctic	UK	-	-	http://www.highlatitudes.com/	info@highlatitudes.com	-	Tourism
Tourism	association	Sustainable Arctic Tourism Association (SATA)	-	Circumpolar	International	-	-	-	-	-	Tourism
Tourism	association	Alaska Wilderness Recreation & Tourism Association (AWRTA)	-	United States	United States	-	-	-	-	-	Tourism
Tourism	private sector	Spaceport Sweden	-	Sweden	Sweden	-	-	-	-	A. Circle 15: Mining and Mineral Industry of the Future 16: Karin Nilsdottir (CEO)	Tourism
Tourism	semi public	Visit Greenland	-	Greenland	Greenland	-	-	www.visitgreenland.com	-	A. Forum 15: Anders Stenbakken (CEO); A. Futures 15: idem Anders; A. Cruise Conference 14: Anders la Cour Wahl (deputy director)	Tourism
Tourism	private sector	Northwest Territories Tourism	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://spectacularnwt.com/	info@spectacularnwt.com	AECO A. Cruise Conference 15	Tourism
Tourism	semi public	Nunavut Tourism	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://nunavuttourism.com/	info@nunavuttourism.com	-	Tourism
Tourism	semi public	Yukon Tourism	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.travel yukon.com/	vacation@gov.yk.ca	-	Tourism
Tourism	private sector	Unlimited Travel Group	tertiary	Worldwide	Sweden	-	-	http://unlimitedtravelgroup.se/	info@unlimitedtravelgroup.se	A. Summit 14: Richard Durlow (CEO);	Tourism
Tourism	semi public	Lapland Tourist Board	-	Finland	Finland	-	-	www.lme.fi	www.lme.fi	-	Tourism
Tourism	semi public	Swedish Lapland Visitors Board	-	Sweden	Sweden	-	-	http://www.swedishlaplandvisitorsboard.com/	annika.fredriksson@swedishlapland.com	-	Tourism
Tourism	semi public	Northern Norway Tourist Board	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	http://www.nordnorge.com/?id=412616041	post@nordnorge.com	A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Tourism
Tourism	private sector	Spitsbergen Travel	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	http://www.spitsbergentravel.com/start/	info@spitsbergentravel.no	A. Frontiers 16: Andresen Vebjørn [*]	Tourism
Tourism	private sector	Hurtigruten	-	Bipolar	Norway	-	-	https://www.hurtigruten.no/sider/om-hurtigruten/	booking@hurtigruten.com	High North Dialogue 15: Daniel Skjeldam (CEO)	Tourism
Tourism	private sector	Crystal Cruises	-	Worldwide	United States	-	-	http://www.crystalcruises.com/	CruiseQuestions@crystalcruises.com	A. Shipping Forum 16: Greg MacGarva (VP Marine operations)	Tourism
Tourism	private sector	Lindblad Expeditions	-	Worldwide	United States	-	-	http://www.expeditions.com/	explore@expeditions.com	-	Tourism
Tourism	private sector	Ocean Expeditions	-	Worldwide	unkown	-	-	http://ocean-expeditions.com/	ben@ocean-expeditions.com	-	Tourism
Tourism	private sector	Promote Iceland (2)	-	Worldwide	Iceland	-	-	www.islandsstofa.is/en	info@promoteiceland.is	see (1)	Tourism
Tourism	private sector	Cree Tourism	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.creetourism.ca/	online form http://www.creetourism.ca/contact-us/	-	Tourism
Tourism	private sector	Pinto Lopes Viagens	-	Antarctic	Portugal	-	-	http://www.pintolopesviagens.com/viagens/cruzeiro-na-antartida/	geral@pintolopesviagens.com	-	Tourism
Tourism	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Tourism
Tourism	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Tourism

Target group	Type	Specific stakeholder	Rank	Region of Interest	Base of operations	Confirmed EU-PolarNet contact person + email address	Possible EU-PolarNet contact person + email (need a double check!)	General home page	Generic email	"Polarness" - i.e. at which events was the stakeholder active? (key to abbreviations under the sheet)	Target group
Local communities	Political organization	Inuit Circumpolar Council	-	Circumpolar	International: Greenland, Canada, United States, Russian Federation	-	-	-	-	The Alaskan Arctic 15: James Stotts (pres.); A. Observing Summit 16: Okalik Eegeesiak and Eva Krummel;	Local communities
Local communities	Political organization	Russian Arctic Indigenous Peoples of the North (RAIPON)	-	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	-	-	-	-	-	Local communities
Local communities	Political organization	Saami Council (SC)	-	Barents Region	International	-	-	-	-	A. Futures 14: Åsa Larsson Blind (vice-pr.); A. Circle 14: Gunn-Britt Retter (member); A. Observing Summit 16: Jannie Staffansson;	Local communities
Local communities	Political organization	Arctic Athabaskan Council (AAC)	-	United States	United States	Jennine Jordan <jjordan@ganaayoo.com>	-	-	-	High North Dialogue 15: Terry Fenge;	Local communities
Local communities	Political organization	Aleut International Association (AIA)	-	United States	United States	-	-	-	-	A. Circle 14: Jim Gamble (executive dir.); A. Energy Summit 15: idem Jim; ShpArc 15: idem Jim	Local communities
Local communities	Political organization	Gwich'in Council International	-	United States	Canada	-	-	-	-	A. Frontiers 16	Local communities
Local communities	Political organization	Norwegian Saami Association (NSR)	-	Norway	Norway	[Kirsti Guvsam, politician leader, kirsti.guvsam@samediggi.no]	-	http://nsr.no/	-	-	Local communities
Local communities	government	Sámi Education Institute	-	Nordic countries	Finland	-	-	http://www.sogsakk.fi/index.php?lang=en	kanslia@sogsakk.fi	-	Local communities
Local communities	NGO	Gáldu Resource Centre for the Rights of Indigenous Peoples	-	Worldwide	Norway	-	-	-	-	-	Local communities
Local communities	NGO	Youth Arctic Coalition (YAC)	-	Circumpolar	unknown	-	-	http://youtharcticcoalition.org/	online form http://youtharcticcoalition.org/contact-2/	A. Encounter 16: Gert Wesselink (Executive Director)	Local communities
Local communities	regional corporation	Inuvialuit Regional Corporation	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.irc.inuvialuit.com/	info@inuvialuit.com	-	Local communities
Local communities	network	Alaska Native Knowledge Network	-	United States	United States	-	-	http://ankn.uaf.edu/index.html	fyankn@ankn.uaf.edu	-	Local communities
Local communities	NGO	Alaska Native Heritage Centre	-	United States	United States	-	-	http://www.alaskanative.net/en/	online form http://www.alaskanative.net/en/p-ara-nav/contact-us/	-	Local communities
Local communities	regional corporation	Makivik Corporation	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.makivik.org/	amoorhouse@makivik.org	A. Circle 14: Jobie Tukkiapik (president) ; A. Circle 15: Adamie Delisle Alaku (vice-pres.)	Local communities
Local communities	institute	Nunavut Research Institute (2)	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.nri.nu.ca/	Mosha.cote@arcticcollege.ca	-	Local communities
Local communities	NGO	Arctic Children and Youth Foundation	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.acyf.ca/	kylie@acyf.ca	-	Local communities
Local communities	NGO	Anisnabe Kekendazone Network Environment for Aboriginal Health Research (AK-NEAHR)	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://akneahr.ciet.org/	online form http://akneahr.ciet.org/contact/	-	Local communities
Local communities	association	Inuit Tapiriit Kanatami	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	https://www.itk.ca/	online form https://www.itk.ca/contact	A. Futures 14: Terry Audla (president); Canada's North Summit 13: Scot Nickels (director of Inuit Qaukisarvingat)	Local communities
Local communities	association	Nunavut Economic Developers Association (NEDA) (1)	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.nunavuteda.com/	exdir@nunavuteda.com	-	Local communities
Local communities	regional corporation	Arctic Slope Regional Corporation (ASRC)	secondary	United States	United States	-	-	http://www.asrc.com/	thardt@asrc.com	A. Encounter 16; A. Futures 15; A. Circle 15: Tara Sweeney (exec. Vice pres.); A. Energy Summit 15: Rex Rock (CEO); A. Energy Summit 15: Richard Glenn (Exec. Vice Pres.) and idem Tara	Local communities
Local communities	regional corporation	Ukpeavik Iñupiat Corporation	-	United States	United States	-	-	http://www.uicalaska.com/	online form http://www.uicalaska.com/contact-us/	A. Energy Summit 13 (also sponsor)	Local communities
Local communities	regional corporation	Qikiqtaaluk Corporation	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.qcorp.ca/	reception@qcorp.ca	-	Local communities
Local communities	association	Greenland Fishers and Hunters Association (KNAPK)	-	Greenland	Greenland	-	-	http://knapk.gl/index.php?id=7&L=1	knapk@knapk.gl	various speakers	Local communities
Local communities	private sector	Kawerak, Inc.	tertiary	United States	United States	-	-	http://www.kawerak.org/	contact@kawerak.org	-	Local communities
Local communities	council	Grand Council of the Crees: office of the Grand Chief	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.gcc.ca/	eagrandchief@gcc.ca	A. Circle 14: Matthew C. Come (Grand Chief) ;	Local communities
Local communities	regional corporation	Bering Straits Native Corporation	-	United States	United States	-	-	http://beringstraits.com/contact/	info@beringstraits.com	Eighth Polar Law Symposium 15: Matt Ganley; The Alaskan Arctic 15: Gail Schubert (CEO)	Local communities
Local communities	NGO	Food Secure Canada (Northern & Remote Food network)	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://foodsecurecanada.org/community-networks/northern-remote-food	online form http://foodsecurecanada.org/contact	-	Local communities
Local communities	event	Arctic Winter Games (AWG)	-	Circumpolar	International	-	-	http://www.arcticwintergames.org/	online form http://www.arcticwintergames.org/contact.htm	-	Local communities
Local communities	commission	Alaska Eskimo Whaling Commission (AEWC)	-	United States	United States	-	-	http://www.aewc-alaska.com/	online form http://www.aewc-alaska.com/Contact_Us.html	A. Open-water Meeting 13: George Noongwook (chairman);	Local communities
Local communities	museum	ARRAN Lulesamisk senter	-	Barents Region	Norway	-	-	http://www.arran.no/	poasta@arran.no	High North Dialogue 16: Sven Roald Nystø;	Local communities
Local communities	community	Dené Nation	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	-	-	Circumpolar Agricultural Conference 13: Bill Erasmus (national chief);	Local communities
Local communities	regional corporation	NANA Regional corporation	-	United States	United States	-	-	http://www.nana.com/	news@nana.com	A. Observing Summit 16: Liz Crvalho; various other events	Local communities
Local communities	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Local communities
Local communities	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Local communities
Local communities	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Local communities

Target group	Type	Specific stakeholder	Rank	Region of Interest	Base of operations	Confirmed EU-PolarNet contact person + email address	Possible EU-PolarNet contact person + email (need a double check!)	General home page	Generic email	"Polarness" - i.e. at which events was the stakeholder active? (key to abbreviations under the sheet)	Target group
Consultancy	private sector	Ecorys	.	Worldwide	Netherlands	Johan Gille -johan.gille@ecorys.com	.	http://www.ecorys.nl/	.	.	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	POLARISK Analytics	primary	Bipolar	unknown	A. Encounter 16: Miká Mered (CEO); A. Energy Summit 13: idem Miká; A. Circle 14: idem Miká; A. Business Forum 15: idem Miká; 6th/7th/8th A. Shipping Summit: idem Miká; A. Exchange 15: idem Miká	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	SASS Consulting	.	Worldwide	Switzerland	.	.	http://sass-consulting.eu/	.	A. Forum 15: Katja Liumatta (Senior Communications Consultant)	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	Northern Cadences Consulting	.	Circumpolar	Iceland	.	.	unknown	.	A. Forum 15: Stephen Perry (CEO)	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	SMRU Consulting (1)	.	Worldwide	International	.	.	http://www.smrucollaboration.com/	.	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	Parnassus Global Agency	.	Worldwide	United States	.	.	http://parnasusglobal.com/contact/	online form http://parnasusglobal.com/contact/	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	Pöyry	.	Worldwide	Finland	.	.	http://www.poyry.com/	.	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	Thomson Reuters	.	Worldwide	International	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	Elomatic	.	Worldwide	Finland	.	.	http://www.elomatic.com/en/	info@elomatic.com	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	Storvik & Co	.	Barents Region	Norway	.	.	http://www.storvik.com/	murmans@storvik.com	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	Matis	.	Iceland	Iceland	.	.	http://www.matis.is/english/	matismatis@matismatis.is	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	Offcode	.	Finland	Finland	.	.	http://www.offcode.fi/	info@offcode.fi	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	Mannvit (2)	.	Circumpolar	Iceland	.	.	http://www.mannvit.com/	mannvit@mannvit.com	.	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	Golder Associates	tertiary	Worldwide	International	.	.	http://www.golder.com/global/en/	online form http://www.golder.com/global/en/modules.php?name=Contact&menu_id=76#	.	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	Kaisa Consulting	tertiary	Circumpolar	Norway	.	.	http://kaisaconsulting.no/#projects	karn@kaisaconsulting.no	Eighth Polar Law Symposium 15: Karin Berentsen (CEO); A. Futures 16: idem Karin; A. Frontiers 16: idem Karin [*]; A. Energy Summit: idem Karin	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	IHS	A. Circle 15: Richard Clayton (chief analyst, IHS Maritime & Trade)	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	Marorka (nautical consultancy) (2)	.	Worldwide	Iceland	.	.	http://www.marorka.com/	marorka@marorka.com	see (1)	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	ConsultNorth	.	United States	United States	.	.	http://www.consultnorth.net/	josephdavis@consultnorth.net	A. Circle 15: Joseph Davis (vice-pres.)	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	Madison River Group science policy consultants	tertiary	United States	United States	.	.	http://www.madisonrivergroup.com/contact-us.html	tom@madisonrivergroup.com	A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	SALT coastal and marine consultants	tertiary	Norway	Norway	.	.	http://salt.nu/en/about-salt	post@salt.nu	A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	RAND Corporation	.	Worldwide	United States	.	.	http://www.rand.org/	unknown	A. Frontiers 16: various attendees	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	Gaia Consulting	.	Finland	Finland	.	.	http://www.gaia.fi/	info@gaia.fi	A. Energy Summit 15: Eero Hokkanen (team Arctic Finland)	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	Stratos Inc.	tertiary	Canada	Canada	.	.	http://www.stratos-sts.com/	mail@stratos-sts.com	Canada's North Summit 13: George Greene (founding chair)	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	Tyréns	.	Nordic countries	Sweden	.	.	http://www.tyrens.se/en/	info@tyrens.se	Mining and Mineral Industry of the Future 16: Mats Svensson (dr. Of technology)	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	Consultancy
Consultancy	private sector	Consultancy
International political organisation	Intergovernmental	Nordic Council (NC) (Norden)	.	Nordic countries	Nordic countries	.	.	http://www.norden.org/en/nordic-council	nordisk-rad@norden.org	.	International political organisation
International political organisation	Intergovernmental	Arctic Council (AC) Secretariat	.	Circumpolar	International	manfred.reinke@ats.aq	.	http://www.ats.aq/index_e.htm	ats@ats.aq	.	International political organisation
International political organisation	Intergovernmental	Antarctic Treaty System (ATS) Secretariat	.	Antarctic	International	International political organisation
International political organisation	Political organization	COMNAP Council of Managers of National Antarctic Programs	.	Antarctic	International	International political organisation
International political organisation	LINK	List of COMNAP members: https://www.comnap.aq/Members/SitePages/Home.aspx	.	Antarctic	International	.	.	https://www.comnap.aq/Members/SitePages/Home.aspx	.	.	International political organisation
International political organisation	Intergovernmental	West Nordic Council	.	Nordic countries	International	A. Circle 14: Unnur B. Konráðsdóttir (vice-chair (also MP)); A. Circle 15: idem Unnur; A. Energy Summit 15: idem Unnur	International political organisation
International political organisation	Political organization	Northern Forum (NF)	.	Circumpolar	International	.	.	http://www.northernforum.org/en/	.	A. Observing Summit 16: Mikhail Pogodaev;	International political organisation
International political organisation	council	The Nordic Council of Ministers	.	Nordic countries	Nordic countries	.	.	http://www.norden.org/en/nordic-council	nmr@norden.org	.	International political organisation
International political organisation	Intergovernmental	International Barents Secretariat (IBS)	.	Barents Region	Norway	.	.	http://www.beac.st/en/Contacts/International-Barents-Secretariat	ibs@beac.st	High North Dialogue 15: Claus Bergersen (advisor)	International political organisation
International political organisation	International political organisation

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Social interest groups	NGO	World Wildlife Fund (WWF) (2)	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	-	-	please see (1)	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	NGO	Protect Sápmi	-	Norway	International: Nordic Countries? Norway-only?	-	-	http://protectsapmi.com/norsk/home/	-	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	NGO	Prince Albert II of Monaco Foundation (1)	-	Worldwide	Monaco	-	-	http://www.fpa2.com/home.html	online form http://www.fpa2.com/contact.php	A. Frontier 15; A. Circle 14;	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	NGO	International Centre for Reindeer Husbandry (2)	-	Circumpolar	Norway	-	-	http://reindeerherding.org/	office@reindeercentre.org	see (1)	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	council	Inuvialuit Game Council	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.wmacns.ca/wmac/council/	wmacns@web.ca	A. Frontier 15; A. Energy Summit 13	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	NGO	Saa'mi Nuett ry	tertiary	Barents Region	Finland	-	-	http://www.saaminuett.fi/	-	-	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	committee	Canadian Arctic Resources Committee	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.carc.org/	davidg@carc.org	-	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	NGO	Center for Support of Indigenous Peoples of the North (CSIPN)	-	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	Rodion Суляндига <rodion@csipn.ru>;	-	http://www.csipn.ru/	-	-	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	NGO	Inuit Sila	-	Greenland	Denmark	-	-	http://inuitsila.org/	info@inuitsila.org	A. Futures 16: Ole Ørum (spokesperson)	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	association	Association of World Reindeer Herders	-	Circumpolar	International	-	Mikhail Pogodaev <pogodaev@gmail.com>;	http://reindeerherding.org/	office@reindeercentre.org	-	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	working group	International Working Group for Indigenous Affairs (IWGIA)	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	http://www.iwgia.org/	board@iwgia.org	-	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	NGO	Centre for Support of Indigenous Peoples of the North / Russian Indigenous Training Centre (CSIPN)	-	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	Rodion Sulyandiga <rodion@csipn.ru>;	-	-	-	-	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	NGO	Alternatives North (Northwest Territories)	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://alternativenorth-ca.web33.winsyr.net/	info@alternativenorth.ca	-	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	NGO	Arctic Peoples Alert	tertiary	Circumpolar	Netherlands	-	-	http://www.arcticpeoplesalert.nl/	arctica@planet.nl	-	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	NGO	Friends of the Earth	-	Worldwide	International	-	John Kaltenstein <J.Kaltenstein@foe.org>;	http://www.foei.org/	-	-	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	Intergovernmental	Arctic Council Indigenous Peoples' Secretariat	-	Circumpolar	International	-	Alona Yefimenko <alona.yefimenko@arcticpeoples.org>;	http://arcticpeoples.org/	-	-	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	institute	EALÁT UArctic Institute	-	Circumpolar	Finland	-	Svein Mathiesen <svein.d.mathiesen@gmail.com>;	http://reindeerherding.org/projects/uarctic-ealat-institute/	-	-	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Social interest groups
Social interest groups	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Social interest groups
Law firm	private sector	Walson Farley & Williams	-	Worldwide	United Kingdom	-	-	http://www.wfw.com/about-us/	-	A. Shipping Summit 15: Neil A. Quartaro (Coounsel)	Law firm
Law firm	private sector	Stewart McKelvey	-	Worldwide	Canada	-	-	http://www.stewartmckelvey.com/en/home/default.aspx#	-	A. Shipping Summit 15: William Moreira (Partner)	Law firm
Law firm	private sector	Borden Ladner Gervais	-	Worldwide	Canada	-	-	http://www.blg.com/en/Offices	-	A. Shipping Summit 15: Peter Pamel (Partner) ; A. Age 15: Adam Chamberlain (partner); Canada's North Summit 13: idem Adam;	Law firm
Law firm	private sector	Stikeman Elliott	-	Worldwide	Canada	-	-	http://www.stikeman.com/cps/rde/xchg/se-en/hs.xsl/992.htm	-	A. Shipping Summit 15: Peter Cullen (Partner); 6th A. Shipping Summit: idem Peter	Law firm
Law firm	private sector	Hjort law firm	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	http://hjort.no/frontpage	ADVOKATFIRMAET@HJORT.NO	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Law firm
Law firm	private sector	Crowell & Moring	-	Worldwide	United States	-	-	https://www.crowell.com/	online form https://www.crowell.com/Contact	A. Energy Summit 13; A. Observing Summit 16: Drue Pearce;	Law firm
Law firm	private sector	DWF	-	Worldwide	United Kingdom	-	-	http://www.dwf.law/about-us/	online form http://www.dwf.law/contact-us/	A. Circle 14: Michael Kingston (Associate Partner DWF Fishburns) ; A. Circle 15: idm Michael; A. Energy Summit 15: idem Michael; ShipArc 15: idem Michael; A. Exchange 15: idem Michael	Law firm
Law firm	private sector	BHM Penlaw	-	Worldwide	Germany	-	-	http://bhm-penlaw.com/	hamburg@bhm-penlaw.com	A. Circle 15: Philipp Hermes (founding & managing partner)	Law firm

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Law firm	private sector	Lindahl	-	Worldwide	Sweden	-	-	http://www.lindahl.se/en/about-us/	reception.stockholm@lindahl.se	A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Law firm
Law firm	private sector	Holman Fenwick Willand LLP	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	http://www.hfw.com/Home	online form https://www.hfw.com/Contact-Us	7th A. Shipping Summit: George Eddings	Law firm
Law firm	private sector	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Law firm
Law firm	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Law firm
Law firm	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Law firm
Law firm	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Law firm
Environmental protection	NGO	Bellona	-	Circumpolar	Norway	-	Sigurd Enge < sigurd@bellona.no >	http://www.bellona.org/	-	A. Forum 15: Lene Hodge (Adviser); Runa Haug Khoury (Senior Adviser); A. Frontiers 15 [*]; A. Futures 15: idem Runa; A. Futures 16: Frederic Hauge (head); A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	World Wildlife Fund (WWF) (1)	-	Worldwide	International	Alexander Shestakov < ashestakov@WWFCanada.org >	-	-	-	A. Forum 15: Rod Downie (UK Polar Policy and Progr. Officer); A. Frontiers 15, 16 [*]; A. Encounter 16; A. Circle 15: Carer Roberts (pres. And CEO); 8th A. Shipping Summit: David Miller (CEO Canada); A. Business 16: Nina Jensen (CEO WWF Norway) [blogger for event]; A. Observing Summit 16: Martin Sommerkorn;	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	WWF Arctic Programme	-	Circumpolar	International	Martin Sommerkorn < msommerkorn@wwf.no >	-	http://wwf.panda.org/what_we_do/where_we_work/arctic/contact/arctic_staff/	-	A. Summit 15: Alexander Shestakov (Global A. Programme) ; A. circle 14: idem Alexander; A. Circle 15; Martin Sommerkorn and Alexander Shestakov ; 3rd Int. A. Forum: idem Alexander	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	WWF Russia	-	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	-	-	-	-	3rd Int. A. Forum: Igor Chesin (director) and Victoria Elias (director of Russian office's programs) and Alexander Shkatov (dir. Of A. programs)	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Greenpeace	-	Worldwide	International	Faiza Oulahsen < Faiza.Oulahsen@greenpeace.org >	Truls Gulowsen < truls.gulowsen@greenpeace.org >	-	-	A. Frontiers 15, 16 [*]	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	BirdLife International	-	Worldwide	International	Marco Lambertini < Marco.Lambertini@birdlife.org >	-	-	-	-	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	BirdLife Europe	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	-	-	A. Forum 15: Lisa Benedetti (Science Editor)	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Coastal and Marine Union (EUCC)	-	Worldwide	International: Europe	-	-	-	-	A. Forum 15: magdalena Muir (Advisory Board Member, climate)	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	SMRU Consulting	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	http://www.smruc consulting.com/	-	-	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Prince Albert II of Monaco Foundation (2)	-	Worldwide	Monaco	-	-	http://www.fpa2.com/home.html	online form http://www.fpa2.com/contact.php	A. Frontier 15	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	private sector	SMRU Consulting (2)	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	http://www.smruc consulting.com/	-	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Oceana	-	Worldwide	International	-	Whit Sheard < whitsheard@yahoo.com >	http://oceana.org/	-	-	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Earth Justice	-	United States	United States	-	Erika Rosenthal < erosenthal@earthjustice.org >	http://earthjustice.org/	-	-	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	association	Arctic Alliance	-	Circumpolar	International	-	John Bennett < bennettandassoc@aol.com >	http://www.arcticalliance.net/	info@arcticalliance.net	-	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Naturvernforbund/Friends of the Earth Norway	-	Norway	Norway	-	Aase Refnes < aar@naturvernforbundet.no >	http://naturvernforbundet.no/?lang=en_GB	lh@naturvernforbundet.no	-	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Pacific Environment	-	Alaska, United States, Russian Federation, China, Japan	International	-	-	http://pacificenvironment.org/	info@pacificenvironment.org	-	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Ocean Conservancy	-	Worldwide	United States	-	Andrew Hartsig < ahartsig@oceanconservancy.org >	http://www.oceanconservancy.org/	-	-	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	semi public	Nordic Environment Finance Corporation (NEFCO) (2)	-	Worldwide	Nordic countries	-	-	http://www.nefco.org/	info@nefco.fi	please see (1)	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	The Pew Charitable Trust (2)	-	Worldwide	United States	-	-	http://www.pewtrusts.org/en	partnerships@pewtrusts.org	A. Observing Summit 16: Raychelle Aluaq Daniel; other evens as well	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Polar Bears International	-	Circumpolar	International	-	-	http://www.polarbearsinternational.org/	online form http://www.polarbearsinternational.org/contact-us	-	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	association	Antarctic Ocean Alliance (AOA)	-	Antarctic	International	-	-	http://antarcticocean.org/	-	-	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Antarctic and Southern Ocean Coalition (ASOC)	-	Antarctic	International	-	-	http://www.asoc.org/	secretariat@asoc.org	-	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Ocean Care	-	Worldwide	Germany	-	-	http://www.oceancare.org/	info@oceancare.org	-	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	WDC (Whale protection)	-	Worldwide	unknown	-	-	http://uk.whales.org/	info@wdcs.org	-	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Wilderness Society	tertiary	United States	United States	-	-	http://wilderness.org/	action@tw.org	-	Environmental protection

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Environmental protection	governmental agency	Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (2)	-	Sweden	Sweden	http://www.swedishepa.se/		registrator@swedishepa.se		see (1)	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Australian Marine Conservation Society	-	Worldwide	Australia			http://www.marineconservation.org.au/			Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	International Fund for Animal Welfare (IFAW)	-	Worldwide	International			http://www.ifaw.org/			Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Common Oceans	-	Worldwide	International			http://www.commonoceans.org/home/en/	Jacqueline.Alder@fao.org		Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Arctic Eider Society (SEA-AES)	-	Canada	Canada			https://arcticeider.com/en/about	https://arcticeider.com/en/contact	A. Circle 14: Joel Heath (exec.-dir.) [chair];	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	association	Arctic NGO Forum	-	Circumpolar	International			http://arcticngoforum.org/	john.crump@grida.no	A. Circle 14: organiser of breakout-session	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	LINK	List to Arctic NGO Forum partners: http://arcticngoforum.org/partners.aspx	-	Worldwide	International			http://arcticngoforum.org/partners.aspx			Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Global Ocean Trust	-	Worldwide	International			http://globaloceantrust.com/en/	globaloceantrust@gmail.com	A. Circle 15: Torsten Thiele (founder)	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	Intergovernmental	North Atlantic Marine Mammal Commission (NAMMCO)	-	Nordic countries	Nordic countries			http://www.nammco.no/	nammco-sec@nammco.no		Environmental protection
Environmental protection	Intergovernmental	International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN)	-	Worldwide	International			http://www.iucn.org/	mail@iucn.org		Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Advisory Committee on Protection of the Sea (ACOPS)	-	Worldwide	International			http://www.acops.org.uk/	acopsadmin@googlemail.com		Environmental protection
Environmental protection	association	Circumpolar Conservation Union (CCU)	-	Circumpolar	United States		<i>Whit Sheard</i> < whitsheard@yahoo.com >	http://circumpolar.org/	ivakaufman@gmail.com		Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Natur og Ungdom	-	Norway	Norway		<i>Ulrikke Kristoffersen</i> < nordland@nu.no >	http://nu.no/english/	info@nu.no	A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Alaska Clean Seas	tertiary	United States	United States			http://www.alaskacleanseas.org/	online form http://www.alaskacleanseas.org/contact-us/	A. Energy Summit 15: Craig B. Lloyd (general manager)	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	The Nature Conservancy	-	Worldwide	unknown			http://www.nature.org/	unknown	A. Energy Summit 15: Randall Hagestein	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	governmental agency	Parks Canada	tertiary ?	Canada	Canada			http://www.pc.gc.ca/eng/index.aspx		A. Cruise Conference 14: Don Marrin (exec. Dir.) and François Dudos (manager)	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	?	Antarctic Environments Portal	primary	Antarctic	International			https://www.environments.aq/	b.njaastad@antarcticnz.govt.nz		Environmental protection
Environmental protection	committee	Committee for Environmental Protection (CEP)	primary	Antarctic	International			http://www.ats.aq/e/cep.htm	ewan.mcivor@aad.gov.au		Environmental protection
Environmental protection	LINK	List of CEP members: http://www.ats.aq/devAS/cep_authorities.aspx	-	Antarctic	International			http://www.ats.aq/devAS/cep_authorities.aspx			Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Wetlands International	-	Worldwide	International		<i>Ward Hagemeyer</i> < ward.hagemeyer@wetlands.org >	http://www.wetlands.org/			Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	The Finnish Association for Nature Conservation	-	Finland	Finland		<i>Jouni Nissinen</i> < jouni.nissinen@sil.fi >	http://www.sil.fi/site-actions/english	risto.sulkava@sil.fi	tsotRP 13: Vesa Luhta	Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Icelandic Nature Conservation Association Loftslag	-	Iceland	Iceland		<i>Arni Finsson</i> < arnif@mmedia.is >	http://www.inca.is/	nsi@mmedia.is		Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Natur og Ungdom	-	Norway	Norway						Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	International Union for the Conservation of Nature	-	Worldwide	International		<i>Martha McConnell</i> < martha.mcconnell@iucn.org >	http://www.iucn.org			Environmental protection
Environmental protection	institute	Institute for Environmental Security	-	Worldwide	International		<i>Ronald Kingham</i> < rkingham@envirosecurity.org >	http://www.envirosecurity.org/			Environmental protection
Environmental protection	NGO	Sociedade Portuguesa para o Estudo das Aves (SPEA)	-	Worldwide	Portugal		<i>Luis Costa</i> (Executive Director)	http://www.spea.pt/en/	luis.costa@spea.pt		Environmental protection
Environmental protection											Environmental protection
Environmental protection											Environmental protection
Environmental protection											Environmental protection
Environmental protection											Environmental protection
Commerce (other)	council	Barents Euro-Arctic Council	-	Russian Federation	International: Nordic Countries, Russian Federation			http://www.beac.st/en			Commerce (other)

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Commerce (other)	council	Barents Regional Council	-	Russian Federation	International: Nordic Countries, Russian Federation	-	-	-	-	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	network	Russian Federation of Chambers of Commerce & Industry	-	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	-	-	-	-	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	council	Arctic Economic Council	-	Circumpolar	International	Bruce Harland <Bruce.Harland@crowley.com>, and Tero Vauraste <Tero.Vauraste@arctia.fi>;	-	-	-	A. Futures 15: Tara MacLean Sweeney (chair); High North Dialogue 16: Anu Fredrikson (Director of Secretariat); A. Observing Summit 16: idem Tara;	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	association	Arctic Business Forum (2)	-	Finland	Finland	-	-	-	-	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	network	Oulu Chamber of Commerce	-	Finland	Finland	-	-	-	-	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	network	Business Oulu	-	Finland	Finland	-	-	-	-	A. Frontiers 15, 16 [*]	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	network	Lapland Chamber of Commerce	-	Finland	Finland	-	-	-	-	A. Circle 14: Timo Rautajoki (president) ; A. Circle 15: idem Timo	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	governmental agency	Invest in Kainuu	-	Finland	Finland	-	-	-	-	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	governmental agency	Invest in Norrbotten	-	Sweden	Sweden	-	-	-	-	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	association	NHO Norway	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	https://www.nho.no/en/	firmapost@nho.no	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	governmental agency	Västerbotten Investment Agency (VIA)	-	Sweden	Sweden	-	-	-	-	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	governmental agency	Dvina Invest	-	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	-	-	-	-	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	governmental agency	Innovation Norway	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	http://www.innovasjon Norge.no/en/start-page/	post@innovasjon Norge.no	A. Frontiers 16: various attendees	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	network	Digipolis Technology centre	-	Finland	Finland	-	-	http://www.digipolis.fi/en/home/about.html	info@digipolis.fi	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	network	Norrbotten Chamber of commerce	-	Sweden	Sweden	-	-	http://www.north.cci.se/	info@norrbottenshandelskammar.se	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	private sector	Northwest Territories Business Development and Investment Corporation	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.bdic.ca/	online form http://www.bdic.ca/contact/	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	association	Nunavut Economic Developers Association (NEDA) (2)	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.nunavuteda.com/	exdir@nunavuteda.com	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	network	NWT Chamber of Commerce	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.nwtchamber.com/	online form http://www.nwtchamber.com/contact-us	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	network	Yukon Chamber of Commerce	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.yukonchamber.com/	office@yukonchamber.com	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	association	Icelandic-Arctic Chamber of Commerce	-	Iceland	Iceland	-	-	-	-	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	governmental agency	Vinnuhúsið House of Industry	-	Faroe Islands	Faroe Islands	-	-	http://www.vinnuhusid.fo/	industry@industry.fo	A. Circle 14: Niels Winther (advisor)	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	private sector	Siemens	-	Worldwide	Germany	-	-	unknown	unknown	A. Circle 15: Carsten Dahl-Uhrenfeldt (director Siemens Greenland)	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	private sector	Greenland Invest	-	Greenland	Greenland	-	-	http://www.greenlandinvest.com/	online form http://www.greenlandinvest.com/	A. Circle 15: Svend Hardenberg (founder, chairman)	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	association	Northern Chamber of Commerce and Industry, Murmansk region	-	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	-	-	http://www.ncci.ru/en/section/main/home?	ncci@ncci.ru	A. Business Forum 15: Anatoly Glushkov (president)	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	private sector	World Trade Center Winnipeg	tertiary ?	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.wtcwinnipeg.com/	info@wtcwinnipeg.com	A. Business Forum 15: Mariette Mulaire (CEO)	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	network	Greenlandic-Icelandic Chamber of Commerce	primary ?	Iceland, Greenland	Iceland, Greenland	-	-	http://www.glis.is/	huldab@chamber.is	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	network	Icelandic Chamber of Commerce	-	Iceland	Iceland	-	-	http://chamber.is/	mottaka@vi.is	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	private sector	Promote Iceland (1)	-	Worldwide	Iceland	-	-	www.islandsstofa.is/en	info@promoteiceland.is	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	network	Norwegian-Russian Chamber of Commerce (NRCC)	-	Barents Region	Norway, Russian Federation	-	-	http://www.nrcc.no	info@nrcc.no	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	network	Kamchatka Chamber of Commerce and Industry	-	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	-	-	none	tppkam@mail.kamchatka.ru	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	network	Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Yamalo-Nenets Autonomous Okrug	-	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	-	-	http://www.tpp89.org	tpp@tpp.salekhard.ru	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	network	Sakha Republic Chamber of Commerce	-	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	-	-	http://sakha.tpprf.ru/ru/contact/	tpp14@mail.ru	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	network	Baffin Regional Chamber of Commerce	tertiary ?	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.baffinchamber.ca/about-us	online form http://www.baffinchamber.ca/contact-us	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	network	Alaska Chamber (of commerce)	-	United States	United States	-	-	http://www.alaskachamber.com/	info@alaskachamber.com	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	private sector	Adoptblue_unipessoal,lda (Theo Kakaw)	-	Worldwide	Portugal	-	-	http://www.theokakaw.pt	theokakaw@gmail.com	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	private sector	ZENRELAX LDA	-	Worldwide	Nordic countries, Russian Federation	-	-	www.hydrosport.pt	cesar.zenrelax@gmail.com	-	Commerce (other)
Commerce (other)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Commerce (other)

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Miscellaneous	international organisation	International Polar Foundation (IPF)	-	Bipolar	Belgium		Thierry Touchais <thierry.touchais@polarfoundation.org>				Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	network	University of the Arctic (UArctic)	-	Circumpolar	International	Outi Snellman <outi.snellman@ulapland.fi>		www.uarctic.org			Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	network	Uarctic Geopolitics thematic network	-	Circumpolar	International		Lassi Heininen	www.uarctic.org		Circumpolar Agricultural Conference 13: Lassi Heininen (lead)	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	network	Uarctic Arctic Health thematic network	-	Circumpolar	International		Arja Rautio	www.uarctic.org		Circumpolar Agricultural Conference 13: Arja Rautio (lead)	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	network	Uarctic Northern small enterprises thematic network	-	Circumpolar	International			www.uarctic.org		Circumpolar Agricultural Conference 13: Svein Johansen (lead)	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	LINK	List of UArctic thematic networks: http://www.uarctic.org/thematic_networks/	-	Circumpolar	International			http://www.uarctic.org/thematic_networks/			Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	LINK	List of UArctic members: http://www.uarctic.org/about-uarctic/members-list/	-	Circumpolar	International			http://www.uarctic.org/about-uarctic/members-list/			Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	private sector	Aerospace and Maritime International (AMIWX)	-					http://www.amix.com/#		A. Shipping Summit 15: Frank Boman (Director)	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	association	Russian Geographical Society	-	Bipolar	Russian Federation			http://www.rgo.ru/en	rgo@rgo.ru	3rd Int. A. Forum: Gennaday Oleinik (general executive dir.); A. Summit 15: Artur Chilingarov (vice-president)	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	association	Royal Geographical Society	-	Bipolar	United Kingdom			-			Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	database	Arctic Stat	-	Circumpolar	Canada			http://www.arcticstat.org/	online form http://www.arcticstat.org/Contact-us.aspx		Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	institute	Alaska Center for Unmanned Aircraft Systems Integration, University of Fairbanks	-	United States	United States			http://acuasi.alaska.edu/	cfcahill@alaska.edu	A. Encounter 16; A. Observing Summit 16: Cathy Cahill (researcher);	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	NGO	EU Arctic Forum Foundation	-	Circumpolar	International			http://eu-arctic-forum.org/	steffen.weber@eu-arctic-forum.org	3rd Int. A. Forum: Steffen Weber (secretary general); Poles Apart 13: idem Steffen;	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	private sector	Project Delta Group	-	Worldwide	Netherlands	Geert Greving <geert.greving@gasterra.nl>		http://projectdeltagroup.com/en			Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	governmental agency	Icelandic / Norwegian / Swedish / US / Canadian Coast Guard	-	Circumpolar	International					A. Circle 14: US, Icelandic, Danish Coast Guard	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	governmental agency	US Coast Guard	-	United States	United States					The Alaskan Arctic 15: various speakers; ShipArc 15: various speakers; A. Dialogue 14: Karin Messenger;	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	governmental agency	Canadian Coastguard	-	Canada	Canada					5th A. Shipping Summit: Pierre D'Arcy (manager ice breaker progr.)	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	governmental agency	Norwegian Coast Guard (Kystvakt)	-	Norway	Norway			http://www.kystvakt.no		various	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	think tank	Brookings Institution Energy Security Initiative	-	Worldwide	United States			http://www.brookings.edu/	development@brookings.edu	A. Circle 14: Charles Ebinger (director) ; A. Circle 15: idem Charles	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	unknown	Nordforsk	-	Nordic countries	Nordic countries			http://www.nordforsk.org/en/about-nordforsk	nordforsk@nordforsk.org	A. Circle 14: Marianne Røgeberg (head of A. Affairs) ;	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	association	Rotary International	-	Worldwide	International			https://www.rotary.org/	online form https://www.rotary.org/en/contact	A. Circle 14: organiser of breakout-session	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	association	Rotary (in Alaska)	-	United States	United States					A. Circle 15: Joseph Davis (Anchorage) and Sandra Medearis (Nome)	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	private sector	Gordon Foundation - Munk-Gordon Arctic Security Program	-	Canada	Canada			http://gordonfoundation.ca/about-us/foundation	info@gordonfn.org	A. Circle 15: Tom Axworthy (CEO); A. Energy Summit 15: idem Tom	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	NGO	European Climate Foundation	tertiary	Europe	Europe			http://europeandclimate.org	info@europeandclimate.org	A. Circle 15: Christoph Wolff (managing director)	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	private sector	Kings Bay AS	-	Norway	Norway			http://kingsbay.no/	firmapost@kingsbay.no	A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	private sector	Pt Capital	-	Circumpolar	United States			http://ptcapital.com/	info@ptcapital.com	The Alaskan Arctic 15: Hugh Short (CEO) and Mead Treadwell (pres.)	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	private sector	Actua North	maybe secondary?	Canada	Canada			http://north.actua.ca/	online form http://north.actua.ca/contact/	Canada's North Summit 13: Jennifer Flanagan (CEO)	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	association	International Polar Heritage Committee (IPHC)	-	Bipolar	International			http://www.polarheritage.com/	info@nzaht.org	IPHC Conference 14: various speakers	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	?	Students on Ice	secondary	Bipolar	International			http://studentsonice.com/			Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	NGO	ShareAction	-	Worldwide	UK			http://shareaction.org/	expedition@studentsonice.com	A. Summit 20???: Louise Rouse (director of engagement);	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	private sector	Boeing	-	Worldwide	United States				info@shareaction.org	High North Dialogue 16: some representative, unnamed;	Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous	NGO	British Antarctic Heritage Trust (UKAHT)	-	Antarctic	UK			http://www.ukaht.org/	info@ukaht.org		Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous											Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous											Miscellaneous
Miscellaneous											Miscellaneous
Data and Technology	private sector	Google	-	Worldwide	United States			unknown	unknown	A. Circle 14: Michael Jons (chief technology advocate)	Data and Technology
Data and Technology	private sector	Planet Labs ('Arctic from Space')	-	Worldwide	unknown			multiple (?): https://www.planet.com/ and http://www.ikonscience.com/	hello@planet.com; info@ikonscience.com	A. Circle 14: Robbie Schingler (president) and Martyn M. Hargrave (CEO) ;	Data and Technology
Data and Technology	private sector	UAS Iceland (Unmanned Aerial Systems)	-	Worldwide	Iceland			http://uasiceland.com/	online form http://uasiceland.com/#contact-us	A. Circle 14, 15: Sigurdur Hrafnsson (Director) ;	Data and Technology
Data and Technology	institute	Norwegian Institute of Defense Studies (1)	-	Norway	Norway			https://forsvaret.no/fts/en	info@ifs.mil.no	A. Circle 14: Kristine Offerdal (acting director) and others	Data and Technology

Target group	Type	Specific stakeholder	Rank	Region of Interest	Base of operations	Confirmed EU-PolarNet contact person + email address	Possible EU-PolarNet contact person + email (need a double check!)	General home page	Generic email	"Polarness" - i.e. at which events was the stakeholder active? (key to abbreviations under the sheet)	Target group
Data and Technology	private sector	Verne Global - the smart data center solution	-	Worldwide	Germany	-	-	http://www.verneglobal.com/	online form http://www.verneglobal.com/about-us/contact-us	A. Circle 15: Dominic Ward (exec. Director)	Data and Technology
Data and Technology	private sector	BMT Defence Services Ltd	-	Worldwide	United Kingdom	-	-	http://www.bmtdsl.co.uk/	info@bmtdsl.co.uk	A. Circle 15: John Buckingham (chief mech. Engineer)	Data and Technology
Data and Technology	private sector	LeoSat	?	Worldwide	Netherlands	-	-	http://www.leosat.com/	unknown	A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Data and Technology
Data and Technology	private sector	KNL Networks	-	Worldwide	Finland	-	-	http://www.kynnel.net/	info@kynnel.net	A. Shipping Forum 16: Toni Linden (CEO)	Data and Technology
Data and Technology	private sector	GE Canada	tertiary	Worldwide	Canada	-	-	http://www.ge.com/	unknown	Canada's North Summit 13: Kim Warburton (vice-pres.)	Data and Technology
Data and Technology	private sector	GeoForum	-	Sweden	Sweden	-	-	http://www.uli.se/om-oss	info@uli-geoforum.se	Mining and Mineral Industry of the Future 16: Susanne Nellemann Ek (CEO)	Data and Technology
Data and Technology	private sector	Arctic Fibre	-	Circumpolar	Canada	-	-	http://arcticfibre.com/	info@arcticfibre.com	-	Data and Technology
Data and Technology	private sector	TelePost Greenland	-	Greenland	Greenland	-	-	http://tele.gl/	tele@telepost.gl	-	Data and Technology
Data and Technology	private sector	Kongsberg Group (2)	-	Worldwide	Norway	-	-	http://www.kongsberg.com/	office@kongsberg.com	see (1)	Data and Technology
Data and Technology	private sector	Polar View	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	http://www.polarview.org/	uk@polarview.org	A. Observing Summit 16: David Arthurs (managing dir.);	Data and Technology
Data and Technology	research centre	CIRFA – Centre for integrated remote sensing and forecasting for arctic operations	-	Circumpolar	Norway	-	Torbjørn Eltoft <torbjorn.eltoft@uit.no>	http://cirfa.uit.no/	torbjorn.eltoft@uit.no	A. Observing Summit 16: Torbjørn Eltoft (centre leader)	Data and Technology
Data and Technology	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Data and Technology
Data and Technology	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Data and Technology
Media	semi public	CAIJING Magazine	-	Worldwide	China	-	-	http://english.caijing.com.cn/aboutus/	newsroom@caijing.com.cn	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Media
Media	private sector	Nordlys	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	http://www.nordlys.no/	-	A. Frontiers 15, 16 [*]	Media
Media	private sector	High North News	-	Circumpolar	Norway	-	-	-	-	A. Frontiers 15, 16 [*]	Media
Media	semi public	YLE broadcasting corporation	tertiary	Finland	Finland	-	-	http://yle.fi/uutiset/news/	-	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Media
Media	semi public	Xinhua News Agency	-	Worldwide	China	-	-	http://www.xinhuanet.com/english/	unknown	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Media
Media	semi public	Norwegian Broadcasting Corporation (NRK)	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	http://www.nrk.no/	info@nrk.no	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Media
Media	semi public	NRK Sápmi	-	Norway	Norway	-	Ann-Irene Buljo <samivaktsjef@nrk.no>	http://www.nrk.no/	sapmi@nrk.no	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Media
Media	private sector	Svenska Dagbladet	-	Sweden	Sweden	-	-	http://www.svd.se/	-	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Media
Media	semi public	Caixin Media	-	Worldwide	China	-	-	http://english.caixin.com/	yuqianwang@caixin.com	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Media
Media	private sector	The Economist	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	http://www.economist.com/	-	A. Frontiers 15 [*]; organised the A. Summit 15; A. Circle 15: Matthew Bishop (editor) [chair of sessions]	Media
Media	private sector	Ritzau	-	Worldwide	Denmark	-	-	https://www.ritzau.dk/en	ritzau@ritzau.dk	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Media
Media	private sector	RIA Novosty	-	Worldwide	Russian Federation	-	-	http://ria.ru/	unknown	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Media
Media	semi public	People's Daily	-	Worldwide	China	-	-	http://en.people.cn/	en@people.cn	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Media
Media	semi public	Sputnik News	-	Worldwide	Russian Federation	-	-	http://sputniknews.com/russia/	online form http://sputniknews.com/docs/about/feedback.html	-	Media
Media	private sector	Sermitsiaq AG	-	Greenland	Greenland	-	-	http://www.sermitsiaq.ag	administration@sermitsiaq.ag	A. Circle 15: Kevin McGwin (journalist)	Media
Media	private sector	Arctic Journal	-	Circumpolar	Greenland	-	-	http://arcticjournal.com/	online form http://arcticjournal.com/contact-us	see Sermitsiaq AG	Media
Media	semi public	Inuit Broadcasting Corporation (IBC)	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.inuitbroadcasting.ca/index.php	-	-	Media
Media	private sector	The Barents Observer	-	Barents Region	unknown	-	-	http://barentsobserver.com/en	-	-	Media
Media	private sector	The Independent Barents Observer	-	Barents Region	unknown	-	-	http://thebarentsobserver.com/	-	-	Media
Media	private sector	Portnews (2)	-	Worldwide	Russian Federation	-	-	http://en.portnews.ru/about/	snitko@portnews.ru	-	Media
Media	private sector	Alaska Dispatch News	-	United States	United States	-	-	http://www.adn.com/	newstips@alaskadispatch.com	A. Circle 14: Alice Rogoff (publisher) [chair of disc.]; A. Circle 15: idem Alice [chair of various sessions]; The Alaskan Arctic 15: idem Alice [speaker]	Media
Media	association	National Geographic	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	http://www.nationalgeographic.com/	-	-	Media
Media	network	Network for Journalists in Norden	-	Nordic countries	Nordic countries	-	-	http://njc.dk/	-	-	Media
Media	private sector	Mediehuset iTromsø AS	tertiary ?	Norway	Norway	-	-	http://www.itromso.no/#navClose	tips@itromso.no	A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Media
Media	private sector	Kalaallit Nunaata Radioa (KNR)	-	Greenland	Greenland	-	-	http://knr.gl/kl	kundeservice@telepost.gl	A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Media
Media	private sector	Lloyd's List (2)	-	Worldwide	United Kingdom	-	-	http://www.lloydslist.com/ll/	clientservices@informa.com	A. Shipping Forum 16: Craig Eason (chief editor)	Media

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Research	private sector	Akvaplan-Niva (1)	-	Bipolar	Norway	-	-	http://www.akvaplan.niva.no/en/	-	A. Forum 15: Salve Dahle (Director); A. Frontiers 15 [*]; 3rd Int. A. Forum: Alexei Bambulyak (general director, Russian dep.)	Research
Research	institute	Institute for Advanced Sustainability Studies (IASS)	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	-	-	-	Research
Research	semi public	Northern Research Institute (NORUT)	-	Nordic countries	Norway	-	-	http://norut.no/en	post@norut.no	various	Research
Research	research centre	Arctic Research Centre, Umeå (Arcum)	-	Circumpolar	Sweden	Peter Sköld <peter.skold@umu.se	-	peter.skold@umu.se	-	6th A. Shipping Summit: Peter Sköld (head)	Research
Research	research centre	Arctic Research Centre, Aarhus (ARC)	-	Circumpolar	Denmark	Søren Rysgaard <rysgaard@bios.au.dk>	-	-	-	-	Research
Research	institute	Arctic Centre of University of Lapland, Rovaniemi	-	Circumpolar	Finland	-	-	http://www.arcticcentre.org/en/	arcticcentre@ulapland.fi	-	Research
Research	institute	Thule Institute of University of Oulu, Oulu	-	Circumpolar	Finland	Kirsi Latola <kirsi.latola@oulu.fi>	-	http://www.oulu.fi/thuleinstitute/	-	-	Research
Research	institute	Finnish Meteorological Institute	-	Finland	Finland	-	Juha Karvonen <juha.karvonen@fmi.fi>	http://en.ilmatieteenlaitos.fi/	-	A. Circle 14: petteri Taalas (dir.-general); A. Circle 15; ITsotRP 13: Mikko Alestalo (director);	Research
Research	institute	Norwegian Meteorological Institute	-	Norway	Norway	-	Helge Tangen <helgaet@met.no>	-	-	-	Research
Research	institute	Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI)	-	Norway	Faroe Islands, Greenland, Denmark	-	Keld Hansen <kqh@DMI.dk>	-	-	5th A. Shipping Summit: Keld Qvistgaard (head of Ice Operations)	Research
Research	institute	Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute	-	Sweden	Sweden	-	Anette Jönsson <Anette.Jonsson@smhi.se>	http://www.smhi.se/en	-	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Research
Research	institute	National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC)	-	Circumpolar	United States	-	-	http://nsidc.org/	nsidc@nsidc.org	A. Observing Summit 16: Matthew Druckenmiller and Peter Pulsifer; other events as well	Research
Research	research centre	Norwegian Space Centre	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	-	-	Task Force on Telecommunications Infrastructure in the Arctic (TFTIA)	Research
Research	institute	DTU Space	-	Denmark	Denmark	-	-	-	-	Task Force on Telecommunications Infrastructure in the Arctic (TFTIA)	Research
Research	research centre	German Aerospace Centre	-	Germany	Germany	-	-	-	-	Task Force on Telecommunications Infrastructure in the Arctic (TFTIA)	Research
Research	private sector	Iridium Satellite	-	Worldwide	unknown	-	-	https://www.iridium.com/company/contact/contactform	online form https://www.iridium.com/company/contact/contactform	Task Force on Telecommunications Infrastructure in the Arctic (TFTIA)	Research
Research	institute	Natural Resources Institute Finland	-	Finland	Finland	-	-	https://www.luke.fi/en/	-	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Research
Research	institute	Korea Maritime Institute	-	Worldwide	South Korea	-	-	-	-	A. Frontiers 15 [*]	Research
Research	institute	Icelandic Met Office	-	Iceland	Iceland	-	-	http://en.vedur.is/	online form http://en.vedur.is/	-	Research
Research	network	International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic (INTERACT)	-	Circumpolar	International	Hannele Savela <hannele.savela@oulu.fi>	Terry Gallagher <terry_gallagher@btinternet.com>	http://www.eu-interact.org/	terry_gallagher@btinternet.com	-	Research
Research	network	PolarForum	-	Circumpolar	Sweden	Ulf Jonsell <ulf.jonsell@polar.se>	-	http://polar.se/en/forskning/96C3%86f-forskare/polarforum/	-	-	Research
Research	institute	Norwegian Polar Institute	-	Bipolar	Norway	-	-	http://www.npolar.no/no/	-	A. Business 16: Jan Gunnar Winther (Director); High North Dialogue 16: idem Jan;	Research
Research	association	Willem Barentsz Polar Institute	-	Bipolar	Netherlands	Annette Scheepstra <a.j.m.scheepstra@rug.nl>	-	http://wbpi.webhosting.rug.nl/	-	-	Research
Research	institute	Fram Centre	-	Circumpolar	Norway	-	-	http://www.framsenteret.no/english.150370.no.html#Vp5DOZdWVAM	post@framsenteret.no	-	Research
Research	institute	Norwegian Institute for Cultural Heritage Research (NIKU)	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	http://niku.no/en/	post@niku.no	-	Research
Research	institute	Nunavut Research Institute (1)	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	http://www.nri.nu.ca/	Mosha.cote@arcticcollege.ca	-	Research
Research	institute	Nordregio Nordic Centre for Spatial Development	-	Circumpolar	Sweden	-	-	http://www.nordregio.se/	nordregio@nordregio.se	-	Research
Research	institute	Arctic Institute - Centre for Circumpolar Security Studies	-	Circumpolar	Norway	-	-	http://www.thearcticinstitute.org/	info@thearcticinstitute.org	-	Research
Research	network	Svalbard Science Forum (SSF)	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	http://www.forskningsradet.no/prognett-ssf/Home_page/1253969737234	-	-	Research
Research	institute	Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center	-	Worldwide	Norway	-	-	https://www.nersc.no/	admin@nersc.no	-	Research
Research	institute	National Institute of Polar Research Japan	-	Bipolar	Japan	-	-	http://www.nipr.ac.jp/english/index.html	kokusai@nipr.ac.jp	A. Observing Summit 16: Hiroyuki Enomoto; other events as well	Research
Research	network	Icelandic Arctic Cooperation Network	-	Iceland	Iceland	Embla Eir Oddsdóttir <embla@arcticiceland.is>	-	-	-	A. Energy Summit 13: Embla E. Oddsdóttir	Research
Research	institute	Institute of the Industrial Ecology Problems of the North (INEP)	-	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	-	-	http://www.kolasc.net.ru/ksc/inform/inep.html	nikolay@inep.ksc.ru	3rd Int. A. Forum: Vladimir Masloboev (director)	Research
Research	institute	Institute of Economic Problems, KSC RAS (IEP)	-	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	-	-	http://www.kolasc.net.ru/ksc/ekon/inform/iep.html	iep@iep.kolasc.net.ru	-	Research
Research	institute	Korean Polar Institute	-	Bipolar	South Korea	-	-	http://www.kopri.re.kr/exclude/userIndex/engIndex.do	unknown	A. Summit 14: Hyoung Chul Shin (head of IR dep.); A. Observing Summit 16: Seong-Joong Kim (researcher);	Research
Research	network	Dutch Arctic Circle	-	Circumpolar	Netherlands	Wouter-Jan Strietman <wouterjan.strietman@wur.nl>	-	https://www.wageningenur.nl/en/project/Dutch-Arctic-Circle.htm	-	-	Research
Research	network	Circumpolar Health Research Network	-	Circumpolar	International	-	-	http://circhnet.org/	-	-	Research

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Research	institute	Chilean Antarctic Institute (INACH)	-	Antarctic	Chile	-	-	http://www.inach.cl/inach/?lang=en	-	-	Research
Research	network	Polarpol (members-only email discussion group)	-	Bipolar	International	-	-	http://lists.canterbury.ac.nz/mailman/listinfo/polarpol	polarpol@lists.canterbury.ac.nz	-	Research
Research	institute	IFREMER French Research Institute for Exploitation of the Sea	-	Worldwide	France	-	-	http://www.ifremer.fr/institut_eng/	-	-	Research
Research	institute	GRID Arendal	-	Worldwide	Norway	-	-	www.grida.no	-	-	Research
Research	institute	China Nordic Arctic Research Centre (CNARC)	-	Nordic countries	China	-	-	http://www.cnarc.info/	egillnielsson@pric.gov.cn	A. Circle 14: Egill P. Nielsson (executive secr.) and others; A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Research
Research	network	Icelandic Cooperation Network	-	Iceland	Iceland	-	-	-	-	-	Research
Research	institute	Vermont Law School	-	Worldwide	United States	-	-	-	-	Eighth Polar Law Symposium 15: Betsy Baker	Research
Research	university	Durham University	-	Bipolar	United Kingdom	-	-	-	-	A. Circle 14: various speakers	Research
Research	institute	International Institute for Sustainable Development (IISD)	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	http://www.iisd.org/	info@iisd.org	A. Circle 14: organiser of breakout-session	Research
Research	institute	Norwegian Institute of Defense Studies (2)	-	Norway	Norway	-	-	https://forsvaret.no/ifs/en	info@ifs.mil.no	see (1)	Research
Research	institute	Institute of Oil and Gas Problems	-	Russian Federation	Russian Federation	-	-	http://www.ipng.ru/	director@ipng.ru	A. Circle 14: Anatoly Zolotukhin (research director)	Research
Research	research centre	Faroe Islands Geological Survey (Jardfeingi)	-	Faroe Islands	Faroe Islands	-	-	http://www.jardfeingi.fo/Default.aspx?sectionid=116	jardfeingi@jardfeingi.fo	-	Research
Research	research centre	Nordic Centre for Welfare and Social Issues	-	Nordic countries	Nordic countries	-	-	http://www.nordicwelfare.org/	info@nordicwelfare.org	-	Research
Research	institute	Brazilian National Institute for Cryospheric Sciences	-	Bipolar	Brazil	-	-	http://www.inpe.gov.br/pt-br/assessoria/About-us/	-	-	Research
Research	funding agency	RANNIS / RANNIS	-	Iceland	Iceland	Thorsteinn Gunnarsson <thorsteinn.gunnarsson@rannis.is>	-	https://en.rannis.is/	rannis@rannis.is	A. Circle 15: Thorsteinn Gunnarsson (member) [chair]	Research
Research	university	Tufts University	-	Circumpolar	United States	-	-	-	-	A. Circle 14, 15: various speakers	Research
Research	institute	Arctic Institute of North America (AINA)	-	Circumpolar	International: United States and Canada	-	-	http://arctic.ucalgary.ca/	arctic@ucalgary.ca	ItSotRP 13: Mary Simon	Research
Research	research centre	Center for Northern Studies / Centre d'Études Nordiques	-	Circumpolar	Canada	Christine Barnard <christine.barnard@cen.ulaval.ca>	-	-	-	-	Research
Research	governmental agency	Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology (JAMSTEC)	-	Worldwide	Japan	-	-	http://www.jamstec.go.jp/e/	www-admin@jamstec.go.jp	A. Frontiers 15, 16: various attendees	Research
Research	network	Polar Knowledge Canada (POLAR-POLAIRE)	-	Canada	Canada	Jeanette Menzies <jeanette.menzies@polar.gc.ca>	-	https://www.canada.ca/en/polar-knowledge/index.html	mail@polar-polaire.gc.ca	A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Research
Research	research centre	Cold Climate Innovation (CCI), Yukon Research Centre	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	https://www.yukoncollege.yk.ca/research/programs/cold_climate_innovation	smooney@yukoncollege.yk.ca	Canada's North Summit 13: Stephen Mooney (director)	Research
Research	institute	Geological Survey of Sweden	-	Sweden	Sweden	-	-	http://sgu.se/	sgu@sgu.se	Mining and Mineral Industry of the Future 16: Lena Söderberg (general dir.)	Research
Research	institute	Geological Survey of Finland	-	Finland	Finland	-	-	http://en.gtk.fi/	gtk@gtk.fi	-	Research
Research	institute	Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland (GEUS)	-	Greenland	Denmark, Greenland	-	-	http://www.geus.dk/UK/Pages/default.aspx	geus@geus.dk	-	Research
Research	committee	Ny-Ålesund Science Managers Committee (NySMAC)	-	Norway	Norway	Nick Cox <nc@bas.ac.uk>	-	http://nysmac.npolar.no/	nysmac@npolar.no	-	Research
Research	committee	Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR)	-	Antarctic	International	Jenny Baeseman <jbaeseman@gmail.com	-	http://scar.org/	-	See http://www.scar.org/scar_media/documents/science/SubsidGroups_2014_Feb15.pdf	Research
Research	expert group	SCAR History of the Institutionalisation of Antarctic Research expert group	-	Antarctic	International	-	Cornelia Luedecke <C.Luedecke@lrz.uni-muenchen.de>	http://www.scar.org/othergroups/humanities/historygroup	C.Luedecke@lrz.uni-muenchen.de	-	Research
Research	expert group	SCAR Humanities and Social Sciences Expert Group (HASSEG)	-	Antarctic	International	Daniela Liggett <daniela.liggett@canterbury.ac.nz>	-	http://antarctica-ssag.org/	online form http://antarctica-ssag.org/contact/	-	Research
Research	expert group	SCAR CBET Capacity Building, Education and Training Advisory Group (CBET)	-	Antarctic	International	-	Karin Lochte	-	-	-	Research
Research	expert group	SCAR ACCE Antarctic Climate Change and the Environment (ACCE) expert group	-	Antarctic	International	-	John Turner <jtu@bas.ac.uk>	http://acce.scar.org/wiki/Antarctic_Climate_Change_and_the_Environment	jt@bas.ac.uk	-	Research
Research	committee	SCAR Standing Committee on Antarctic Data Management	-	Antarctic	International	-	Anton van de Putte <antonarctica@gmail.com>	http://www.scar.org/scadm	antonarctica@gmail.com	-	Research
Research	committee	SCAR Standing Committee on Antarctic Geographic Information	-	Antarctic	International	-	Jean-Yves Pirlot <jean-yves.pirlot@ign.be>	http://www.scar.org/data-products/scagi	ajfo@bas.ac.uk	-	Research
Research	committee	SCAR Standing Committee on the Antarctic Treaty System	-	Antarctic	International	-	Aleks Terauds <Aleks.Terauds@aad.gov.au>	http://www.scar.org/antarctic-treaty-system/scats	Aleks.Terauds@aad.gov.au	-	Research
Research	expert group	SCAR Standing Scientific Group on Life Sciences (SSG-LS)	-	Antarctic	International	-	Graham Hosie <graham.hosie@iinet.net.au>	http://www.scar.org/ssg/life-sciences	graham.hosie@iinet.net.au	-	Research

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Research	expert group	SCAR Standing Scientific Group on GeoSciences (SSG-GS)	.	Antarctic	International	.	W Berry Lyons <lyons.142@osu.edu>;	http://www.scar.org/ssg/geosciences	lyons.142@osu.edu	.	Research
Research	expert group	SCAR Standing Scientific Group on Physical Sciences (SSG-PS)	.	Antarctic	International	.	David Bromwich <bromwich.1@osu.edu>;	http://www.scar.org/ssg/physical-sciences	bromwich.1@osu.edu	.	Research
Research	LINK	SCAR National Committees: http://www.scar.org/members-and-officers/national-committees	.	Antarctic	NA	.	.	http://www.scar.org/members-and-officers/national-committees	.	.	Research
Research	expert group	Gateway Antarctica	.	Antarctic	New Zealand	Daniela Liggett <daniela.liggett@canterbury.ac.nz>;	Research
Research	committee	International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)	.	Circumpolar	International	.	.	http://iasc.info/	info@iasc.org	.	Research
Research	working group	IASC Atmosphere Working Group	.	Circumpolar	International	.	Yoo Kyung Lee <yoo.kyung.lee@iasc.info>;	http://iasc.info/working-groups/atmosphere	yoo.kyung.lee@iasc.info	.	Research
Research	working group	IASC Cryosphere Working Group	.	Circumpolar	International	.	Tetsuo Sueyoshi <sueyoshi.tetsuo@nipr.ac.jp>;	http://iasc.info/working-groups/cryosphere	sueyoshi.tetsuo@nipr.ac.jp	.	Research
Research	working group	IASC Terrestrial Working Group	.	Circumpolar	International	.	Yoo Kyung Lee <yoo.kyung.lee@iasc.info>;	http://iasc.info/working-groups/terrestrial	yoo.kyung.lee@iasc.info	.	Research
Research	working group	IASC Marine Working Group	.	Circumpolar	International	.	Yoo Kyung Lee <yoo.kyung.lee@iasc.info>;	iasc.info/working-groups/marine	yoo.kyung.lee@iasc.info	.	Research
Research	working group	IASC Social & Human Working Group	.	Circumpolar	International	.	Susan File <susan.file@polarcom.bc.ca>;	http://iasc.info/working-groups/social-human	susan.file@polarcom.gc.ca	.	Research
Research	committee	US National Science Foundation (NSF)	.	Worldwide	International	.	.	www.nsf.gov/	.	.	Research
Research	institute	Fridtjof Nansen Institute	.	Bipolar	Norway	Svein Vigeland Rottem	Research
Research	committee	Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR)	.	Worldwide	International	John Turner <jtu@hsg.ac.uk>;	.	www.scor-int.org/	secretariat@scor-int.org	.	Research
Research	committee	European Polar Board (EPB)	.	Bipolar	Europe	Renuka Badhe <Renuka.badhe@scar.org>;	.	http://www.europeanpolarboard.org/	.	.	Research
Research	LINK	List of members: http://www.europeanpolarboard.org/organisation/membership/	.	Bipolar	Europe	.	.	http://www.europeanpolarboard.org/organisation/membership/	.	.	Research
Research	council	International Council for the Exploration of the Sea	.	Worldwide	International	.	.	http://www.ices.dk/Pages/default.aspx	info@ices.dk	.	Research
Research	council	Council of Managers of National Antarctic Program (COMNAP)	.	Antarctic	International	.	.	https://www.comnap.aq/SitePages/Home.aspx	info@comnap.aq	.	Research
Research	expert group	COMNAP Expert group Air	.	Antarctic	International	.	Giuseppe di Rossi <giuseppe.derossi@enea.it>; Brian Stone <bstone@nsf.gov>;	https://www.comnap.aq/Groups/SitePages/Home.aspx	.	.	Research
Research	expert group	COMNAP Expert group Energy & Technology	.	Antarctic	International	.	Felix Bartsch <fbartsch@inach.cz>; Pavel Kapler <kapler@sci.muni.cz>;	https://www.comnap.aq/Groups/SitePages/Home.aspx	.	.	Research
Research	expert group	COMNAP Expert group Environment	.	Antarctic	International	.	Anoop Tiwari <anoopktiwari@gmail.com>;	https://www.comnap.aq/Groups/SitePages/Home.aspx	.	.	Research
Research	expert group	COMNAP Expert group Medical	.	Antarctic	International	.	Jeff Ayton <jeff.ayton@aad.gov.au>;	https://www.comnap.aq/Groups/SitePages/Home.aspx	.	.	Research
Research	expert group	COMNAP Expert group Safety	.	Antarctic	International	.	Henrik Tornberg <henrik.tornberg@polar.se>;	https://www.comnap.aq/Groups/SitePages/Home.aspx	.	.	Research
Research	expert group	COMNAP Expert group Science	.	Antarctic	International	.	Robb Clifton <robb.clifton@aad.gov.au>;	https://www.comnap.aq/Groups/SitePages/Home.aspx	.	.	Research
Research	expert group	COMNAP Expert group Shipping	.	Antarctic	International	.	Miguel Ojeda <maojeda@cmima.csic.es>;	https://www.comnap.aq/Groups/SitePages/Home.aspx	.	.	Research
Research	expert group	COMNAP Expert group Training	.	Antarctic	International	.	Veronica Vlasich <veronicavlasich@hotmail.com>;	https://www.comnap.aq/Groups/SitePages/Home.aspx	.	.	Research
Research	expert group	COMNAP Expert group Education and Outreach	.	Antarctic	International	.	Dragomir Mateev <dragomir.mateev@gmail.com>;	https://www.comnap.aq/Groups/SitePages/Home.aspx	.	.	Research
Research	working group	ICES/CAFF/PAME Working Group on Integrated Ecosystem Assessment (IEA) for the Central Arctic Ocean	.	Circumpolar	International	.	Hein Rune Skjoldal <hein.rune.skjoldal@imr.no>; and John Bengtson <john.bengtson@noaa.gov>;	.	.	.	Research
Research	programme	Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS)	.	Antarctic	International	Louise Newman <lnewman@soos.aq>;	.	.	.	A. Futures 15: Jon L. Fuglestad (Deputy Exec. Secretary)	Research

Target group	Type	Specific stakeholder	Rank	Region of Interest	Base of operations	Confirmed EU-PolarNet contact person + email address	Possible EU-PolarNet contact person + email (need a double check!)	General home page	Generic email	"Polarness" - i.e. at which events was the stakeholder active? (key to abbreviations under the sheet)	Target group
Research	network	Sustainable Development Working Group (SDWG)	-	Circumpolar	International	-	-	http://sdwg.org	-	A. Observing Summit 16: Roberta Burns; other events as well	Research
Research	programme	Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP)	-	Circumpolar	International	Janet Pawlak <jpawlak@dahm.dk>;	-	-	-	A. Futures 15: Jon L. Fuglestad (Deputy Exec. Secretary); A. Observing Summit 16: Martin Forsius (chair) and Thomas Armstrong (AACA);	Research
Research	programme	Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna (CAFF)	-	Circumpolar	International	Tom Barry <tom@caff.is>;	-	-	-	A. Energy Summit 13: Tom Caff; A. Circle 14: idem Tom; A. Observing Summit 16: Ulrik Westman (chair) and Gilbert Castellanos;	Research
Research	programme	Arctic Contaminants Acton Program (ACAP)	-	Circumpolar	International	-	Wiesława Misiak <wieslawa.misiak@aca.p.az>;	-	-	3rd Int. A. Forum: Jaakko Henttonen (chairman); A. Observing Summit 16: Reidar Hindrum (chair)	Research
Research	programme	Protection of the Arctic Marine Environment (PAME)	-	Circumpolar	International	-	-	http://www.pame.is/	pame@pame.is	A. Circle 14: Soffia Guðmundsdóttir (exec. Secretary) [sp]; A. Observing Summit 16: Renée Sauve (chair)	Research
Research	working group	Emergency Prevention, Preparedness and Response (EPPR)	-	Circumpolar	International	-	-	-	-	A. Encounter 16; A. Observing Summit 16: Amy Merten (chair);	Research
Research	committee	Arctic Portal	-	Circumpolar	Iceland	Halldor Johannsson <halldor@arcticportal.org>;	-	http://arcticportal.org/	-	A. Shipping Summit 15: Halldór Johannsson (General Manager) ; A. Circle 14: idem Halldór; 5th/6th/8th A. Shipping Summit: idem Halldór	Research
Research	committee	Commission for the Conservation of Antarctic Marine Living Resources (CCAMLR)	-	Antarctic	International	-	-	https://www.ccamlr.org/en	ccamlr@ccamlr.org	-	Research
Research	agency	European Environment Agency (EEA)	-	Europe	Europe	Nikolaj Bock <Nikolaj.Bock@eea.europa.eu>;	-	http://www.eea.europa.eu	-	-	Research
Research	private sector	Canatec	-	Circumpolar	Canada	-	-	http://www.canatec.ca/	online form http://www.canatec.ca/index.php/the-company/history/contact/	-	Research
Research	unknown	BarentsWatch	-	North Atlantic	Norway	-	-	https://www.barentswatch.no/en/about/	geir.schulstad@barentswatch.no	A. Frontiers 16 [*]	Research
Research	governmental agency	Canadian Ice Service	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	https://www.ec.gc.ca/glaces-ice/	ec.enviroinfo.ec@canada.ca	5th A. Shipping Summit: David Jackson (director)	Research
Research	programme	European Climate Research Alliance, Arctic Programme (Arctic ECRA)	-	Circumpolar	Europe	Tina Swierczynski <tina.swierczynski@ecra-climate.eu>;	-	-	-	-	Research
Research	association	Asian Forum of Polar Sciences (AFOPS)	-	Bipolar	International	-	-	http://www.afops.org/	jj@kopri.re.kr	-	Research
Research	unknown	Polar Research and Policy Initiative (Polar Connection)	-	Bipolar	unknown	-	-	http://polarconnection.org/	info@polarconnection.org	-	Research
Research	institute	Swedish Polar Research Secretariat (Polarforskningssektariatet)	-	Bipolar	Sweden	Ulf Jonsell <ulf.jonsell@polar.se>;	-	http://polar.se/	office@polar.se	-	Research
Research	programme	Centre for Polar Ecology	-	Bipolar	Czech Republic	-	-	http://polar.prf.jcu.cz/	czechpolar@gmail.com	-	Research
Research	university	Masaryk University	-	Antarctic	Czech Republic	-	-	http://polar.sci.muni.cz/en/home	http://polar.sci.muni.cz/en/home	-	Research
Research	association	Association of Canadian Universities for Northern Studies	-	Arctic	Canada	-	-	http://acuns.ca/en/	-	-	Research
Research	-	Arctic Science Partnership (ASP)	-	Circumpolar	Canada, Denmark, Greenland	-	-	http://www.asp-net.org/	-	-	Research
Research	association	International Permafrost Association (IPA)	-	Worldwide	International	-	-	http://ipa.arcticportal.org/	-	-	Research
Research	association	Academy of Finland	-	Finland	Finland	-	-	http://www.aka.fi/en/	-	-	Research
Research	institute	Canadian Institute of Mining, Metallurgy and Petroleum (CIM)	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	https://www.cim.org/	cim@cim.org	-	Research
Research	research centre	Yukon Cold Climate Innovation Centre	-	Circumpolar	Canada	-	-	https://www.yukoncollege.yk.ca/research	smooney@yukoncollege.yk.ca	-	Research
Research	institute	Austrian Polar Research Institute (APRI)	-	Bipolar	Austria	-	-	http://www.polarresearch.at/	office@polarresearch.at	-	Research
Research	working group	Working Group Arctic and Subarctic (AAS), Austrian Polar Research Institute	-	Circumpolar	Austria	-	-	http://www.sub-arctic.ac.at/	miguel.roncero@outlook.com	-	Research
Research	programme	PACES air Pollution in the Arctic: Climate Environment and Societies	-	Circumpolar	International	-	-	http://www.igacproject.org/PACES	info@igacproject.org	-	Research
Research	programme	World Climate Research Programme	-	Worldwide	International	Mike Sparrow <mssparrow@wmo.int>;	-	http://www.wcrp-climate.org/	wcrp@wmo.int	-	Research
Research	association	Cluster Polaire / Polar Cluster	-	Bipolar	France	Miká Mered <contact@clusterpolaire.fr>;	-	-	-	-	Research
Research	university	Design School, Université du Québec à Montréal (UQAM)	secondary?	Canada	Canada	-	Patrick Evans <evans.patrick@uqam.ca>;	http://www.design.uqam.ca/	ecole.design@uqam.ca	does many projects in Nunavik	Research
Research	institute	Aurora Research Institute	-	Canada	Canada	Jolie Gareis <jgareis@auroracollege.net.ca>;	-	http://nwtresearch.com/	-	-	Research
Research	research centre	CICERO Center for International Climate and Environmental Research - Oslo	-	Worldwide	Norway	Marianne Tronstad Lund <m.t.lund@cicero.oslo.no>;	-	http://www.cicero.uio.no/en	post@cicero.oslo.no	A. Dialogue: Grete Hovelsrud	Research
Research	programme	International Cryosphere Climate Initiative (ICCI)	-	Worldwide	International	Pam Pearson <pam@iccinet.org>;	-	-	-	-	Research

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Research	LINK	Arctic research projects funded by EU, List (page 8-11): http://ec.europa.eu/research/bioeconomy/pdf/arctic_research_funded_by_the_research_and_innovation_eu_en.pdf	.	Circumpolar	Europe	.	.	http://ec.europa.eu/research/bioeconomy/pdf/arctic_research_funded_by_the_research_and_innovation_eu_en.pdf	.	.	Research
Research	commission	US Arctic Research Commission of the United States	.	Circumpolar	United States	.	Lawson W. Brigham <lwhbrigham@alaska.edu>	https://www.arctic.gov/	.	A. Observing Summit 16: John Farrell (exec. Director); many other events	Research
Research	committee	Swiss Committee on Polar and High Altitude Research	.	Bipolar	Switzerland	.	Christoph Kull <christoph.kull@scnat.ch>	http://www.polar-research.ch/e/index.php	christoph.kull@scnat.ch	.	Research
Research	institute	Luzin Institute for Economic Studies, Kola Science Centre of Russian Academy of Sciences	.	Circumpolar	Russian Federation	.	Fedor D Larichkin <fd@iep.kolasc.net.ru>	.	.	.	Research
Research	institute	Finnish Forest Research Institute	.	Finland	Finland	.	Martti Varmola <martti.varmola@metla.fi>	.	.	.	Research
Research	institute	Multidimensional Tourism Institute, Lapland	.	Finland	Finland	.	Johan Edelheim <johan.edelheim@ulogland.fi>	http://matkailu.luc.fi/In-English/About-us	.	.	Research
Research	institute	Finnish Game and Fisheries Research Institute (FGFRI)	.	Finland	Finland	.	Eero Niemela <eero.niemela@rktl.fi>	http://www.rktl.fi	.	.	Research
Research	institute	Finnish Forest Research Institute METLA	.	Finland	Finland	.	.	http://www.metla.fi/index-en.html	kirjaamo@luke.fi	.	Research
Research	association	Exposed (marine technology)	.	Worldwide	Norway	.	.	http://exposedaquaculture.no/en/	hans.bjelland@sintef.no	.	Research
Research	LINK	List of partners: http://exposedaquaculture.no/en/	.	Worldwide	Norway	.	.	http://exposedaquaculture.no/en/	.	.	Research
Research	institute	International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES)	.	Worldwide	International	.	.	http://www.ices.dk/	info@ices.dk	.	Research
Research	institute	Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia (LNEG)	.	Worldwide	Portugal	.	.	www.lneg.pt	info_geral@lneg.pt	.	Research
Research	institute	Instituto Tecnológico e Nuclear (ITN)	.	Worldwide	Portugal	.	.	http://www.itn.pt/	Secretaria do da Direcção@ctn.ist.utl.pt	.	Research
Research	association	Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) - Portugal	.	Bipolar	Portugal	.	.	http://apecsportugal.wix.com/a-pecsportugal	apecsportugal@gmail.com	.	Research
Research	research centre	Centro de Estudos Geográficos, Instituto de Geografia e Ordenamento do Território, Lisboa University	.	Antarctic	Portugal	.	.	www.ceg.ul.pt	ceg@campus.ul.pt	.	Research
Research	research centre	Centro de Química Estrutural, Instituto Superior Técnico, Lisbon University	.	Antarctic	Portugal	.	.	http://cqe.ist.utl.pt	pombeiro@tecnico.ulisboa.pt	.	Research
Research	research centre	Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre, MARE, Coimbra University	.	Antarctic	Portugal	.	.	http://www1.ci.uc.pt/imar/unit/	imar@ci.uc.pt	.	Research
Research	research centre	Centro Interdisciplinar de Investigação Marinha e Ambiental, Porto University	.	Antarctic	Portugal	.	.	http://www.ciimar.up.pt	secretariado@ciimar.up.pt	.	Research
Research	institute	Instituto Superior de Ciências Sociais e Políticas, Lisbon University	.	Circumpolar	Portugal	.	.	http://www.iscsp.ulisboa.pt	pedroabreu@iscsp.ulisboa.pt	.	Research
Research	research centre	Departamento de Engenharia Civil, Instituto Superior Técnico - Universidade de Lisboa	.	Antarctic	Portugal	.	mcguedes@civil.ist.utl.pt	https://fenix.tecnico.ulisboa.pt/departamentos/decivil	secretariado@civil.tecnico.ulisboa.pt	.	Research
Research	research centre	Centre of Marine Sciences (CCMAR)	.	Antarctic	Portugal	.	.	http://www.ccmarmar.pt/	ccmar@ualg.pt	.	Research
Research	research centre	Centro de Recursos Naturais e Ambiente (CERENA), Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa	.	Antarctic	Portugal	.	.	http://cerena.ist.utl.pt/	juliar@ist.utl.pt	.	Research
Research	research centre	Centro de Ciências do Mar e do Ambiente (MARE)	.	Circumpolar	Portugal	.	.	http://www.mare-centre.pt/	mare@mare-centre.pt	.	Research
Research	research centre	CESAM - Centre for environmental and marine studies, University of Aveiro	.	Antarctic	Portugal	.	.	http://www.cesam.ua.pt/index.php?language=eng	cesam@dao.ua.pt	.	Research
Research	research centre	University of Beira Interior	.	Circumpolar	Portugal	.	.	http://www.ubi.pt/	geral@ubi.pt	.	Research
Research	private sector	Arctic Conservation Science Team, Pew Charitable Trust	.	Circumpolar	International	.	Raychelle Aluaq Daniel	http://www.pewtrusts.org/en/projects/protecting-life-in-the-arctic/arctic-science/arctic-conservation-science-team	rteichroeb@pewtrusts.org	A. Observing Summit 16: Raychelle Aluaq Daniel (Pew Char.);	Research
Research	network	Future Earth	.	Worldwide	International	.	.	http://www.futureearth.org/	contact@futureearth.org	A. Observing Summit 16: Donald Forbes (Coasts section);	Research
Research	network	Pacific Arctic Group	.	Circumpolar	International	.	.	http://pag.arcticportal.org/	shkang@kopri.re.kr	.	Research
Research	Research
Research	Research
Research	Research
Research	Research
Government(s)	governmental agency	European Union (EU)	.	Worldwide	Europe	Government(s)

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Government(a)s	governmental agency	Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (1)	.	Sweden	Sweden	.	Lotten Sjölander <lotten.sjolander@nat.unardsverket.se>; Eva Smith <eva.smith@naturvardverket.se>	http://www.swedishepa.se/	registrator@swedishepa.se	A. Observing Summit 16: Ulrik Westman (chair)	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	governmental agency	Norwegian Environmental Agency - Miljødirektoratet	.	Norway	Norway	.	.	http://www.miljodirektoratet.no/no/Om-Miljodirektoratet/Norwegian-Environment-Agency/	post@miljodir.no	A. Frontiers 16 [*]; A. Observing Summit 16: Reidar Hindrum;	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	governmental agency	Faroe Islands Environmental Agency (Umhvørvisstovan)	.	Faroe Islands	Faroe Islands	.	.	http://www.us.fo/Default.aspx?ID=13804	us@us.fo	.	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	governmental agency	Environmental Agency of Iceland (Umhverfisstofnun)	.	Iceland	Iceland	.	.	http://www.ust.is/the-environment-agency-of-iceland/	ust@ust.is	.	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	governmental agency	Finnish Environment Institute SYKE	.	Finland	Finland	.	Sari Kauppi <sari.kauppi@ymparisto.fi>	http://www.ymparisto.fi/en-US	kirjaamo.syke@ymparisto.fi	A. Shipping Forum 16: Jorma Rytönen (R&D manager); A. Observing Summit 16: Martin Forsius (chair)	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	governmental agency	Scottish Environmental Protection Agency	.	Scotland	United Kingdom	.	.	http://www.sepa.org.uk/	online form http://www.sepa.org.uk/contact/contact-us-via-email/	.	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	governmental agency	Finland Energy Authority (Energi Avirasto)	.	Finland	Finland	.	.	https://www.energiavirasto.fi/web/energy-authority/energy-authority	kirjaamo@energiavirasto.fi	.	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	governmental agency	Swedish Energy Agency (Energimyndigheten)	.	Sweden	Sweden	.	.	http://www.energimyndigheten.se/en/	registrator@energimyndigheten.se	A. Energy Summit 15: Lars Andersson (head of wind power unit)	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	governmental agency	National Energy Authority (NEA) of Iceland (Orkustofnan)	.	Iceland	Iceland	.	.	http://www.nea.is/	os@os.is	A. Energy Summit 13 (also sponsor); A. Circle 15: Guðni A. Jóhannesson	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	governmental agency	Alaska Energy Authority	.	United States	United States	.	.	http://www.akenergyauthority.org/	sfisher@goad@aldea.org	A. Energy Summit 15: various speakers	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	semi public	Greenland Energy Company and authority (Nukisiorfiit)	.	Greenland	Greenland	.	.	https://www.nukisiorfiit.gl/	kundeservice@nukisiorfiit.gl	.	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	governmental agency	Norwegian Road Administration (Statens Vegvesen)	.	Norway	Norway	.	.	http://www.vegvesen.no/en/Ho-me	online form http://www.vegvesen.no/om+statens+vegvesen/Kontakt+oss/Kontakttskiema/Kontakt+oss	.	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	governmental agency	Swedish Transport Agency (Transportstyrelsen)	.	Sweden	Sweden	.	.	https://transportstyrelsen.se/en/	kontakt@transportstyrelsen.se	Mining and Mineral Industry of the Future 16: Arnold Vonkavaara (regional manager)	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	governmental agency	Finnish Transport Agency (Liikennevirasto)	.	Finland	Finland	.	.	http://www.liikennevirasto.fi/web/en	kirjaamo@liikennevirasto.fi	A. Shipping Forum 16: Jarkko Toivola (chief maritime specialist, winter navigation)	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	governmental agency	Icelandic Road and Coastal Administration (IRCA) (Vegagerðin)	.	Iceland	Iceland	.	.	http://www.road.is/	vegagerdin@vegagerdin.is	.	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	association	Association of Finnish Local and Regional Authorities	.	Finland	Finland	.	.	http://www.localfinland.fi/en/Pages/default.aspx	.	A. Forum 15: Heli Niemelä-Farrer (EU Affairs Officer)	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	research centre	Canadian International Arctic Centre	.	Circumpolar	Canada	.	.	http://www.international.gc.ca/arctic-arctique/arctic-centre-arctique.aspx?lang=eng	.	A. Forum 15: Bob Paquin (Head)	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	governmental agency	European External Action Service (EEAS)	.	Bipolar	International: Europe	A. Forum 15: Maroula Sfondyla (Canada co-desk)	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	government	National governments of Arctic countries	.	Circumpolar	NA	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	government	National governments of Arctic Council observers	.	Circumpolar	NA	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	government	National governments of Antarctic Treaty System signatories	.	Antarctic	NA	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	government	Ministry X of country X	.	NA	NA	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	government	Regional governments of Iceland, Norway, Sweden, Finland, Russian Federation, Alaska, Canada (incl. Nfl-Labrador)	.	NA	NA	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	government	Regional governments of southern Chile, Argentina	.	Antarctic	Argentina, Chile	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	government	Local governments of key regions in the Arctic (Tramsø, Oulu, Murmansk, Svalbard, Anchorage)?	.	NA	NA	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	government	Norwegian Sámi Parliament	.	Norway	Norway	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	government	Swedish Sámi Parliament	.	Sweden	Sweden	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	government	Finnish Sámi Parliament	.	Finland	Finland	.	.	http://www.samediggi.fi/index.php?lang=english	info@samediggi.fi	.	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	governmental agency	Canadian Northern Economic Development Agency (CanNor)	.	Canada	Canada	.	.	http://www.cannor.gc.ca/eng/1351104567432/1351104589057#	ytinfo@cannor.gc.ca; ecdevnwt@cannor.gc.ca; ecdevnunavut@cannor.gc.ca	A.Age 15: Mitch Bloom (Vice president); A. Summit 15: Janet King (president); Canada's North Summit 13: Sandra LaFortune (dir. general)	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	ministry	Northwest Territories Industry, Tourism and Investment	.	Canada	Canada	.	.	http://www.iti.gov.nt.ca/	online form http://www.iti.gov.nt.ca/content/contact	.	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	ministry	Nunavut Department of Economic Development and Transportation	.	Canada	Canada	.	.	http://www.gov.nu.ca/edt/	edt@gov.nu.ca	.	Government(a)s
Government(a)s	government	EU DG MARE Directorate General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries	.	Europe	Europe	.	.	http://ec.europa.eu/dgs/maritimeaffairs_fisheries/index_en.htm	.	Changing Realities 10; A. Dialogue 14: Stijn Billiet	Government(a)s

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Event: general	event	Arctic Forum (annual)	-	Circumpolar	unknown	-	-	-	-	checked 2015 programme	Event: general
Event: general	event	Arctic Futures (annual)	-	Circumpolar	unknown	-	-	-	-	checked 2014, 2015, 2016 programme	Event: general
Event: shipping	event	Arctic Shipping Summit, Montréal (annual) (previously Polar Shipping Summit)	-	Circumpolar	unknown	-	-	-	-	checked 5th (2014; Arctic-Polar), 6th (2015), 7th (2015), 8th Summit (2016) programme	Event: shipping
Event: shipping	event	Arctic Shipping Forum	-	Circumpolar	Finland	-	-	-	-	checked 2016 programme	Event: shipping
Event: mining	event	Arctic Mining Summit (annual)	-	Circumpolar	unknown	-	-	-	-	checked 2015 programme	Event: mining
Event: business	event	Northern Forum (NF) (annual)	-	Circumpolar	unknown	-	Vladimir Vasiliev <Vladimir.vasiliev@rambler.ru>	-	-	NA	Event: business
Event: sustainable development	event	Arctic Frontiers (annual), Tromsø	-	Circumpolar	Norway	-	-	-	-	checked 2015, 2016 programme	Event: sustainable development
Event: energy	event	Arctic Energy Summit (annual)	-	Circumpolar	unknown	-	-	-	-	checked 2013 programme	Event: energy
Event: general	event	International Arctic Forum, Russian Geographical Society, 3rd in 2013, Salekhard	-	Circumpolar	Russian Federation	-	-	http://arctic.ru/	-	checked 2013 programme	Event: general
Event: science	event	Arctic Science Summit Weak (annual)	-	Circumpolar	Japan	-	-	-	-	NA (irrelevant, only academia)	Event: science
Event: general	event	ArcticAge 2015, Ottawa	-	Circumpolar	Canada	-	-	-	-	checked 2015 programme	Event: general
Event: sustainable development	event	Arctic Encounter 2016, Paris	-	Circumpolar	United States	-	-	-	-	checked 2016 programme	Event: sustainable development
Event: general	event	Arctic Summit 2015 (The Economist)	-	Circumpolar	United States	-	-	http://www.economistinsights.com/sustainability-resources/event/arctic-summit-2015	-	checked 2014, 2015 programme	Event: general
Event: tourism	event	AECO's Arctic Cruise Conference	-	Circumpolar	Denmark	-	-	-	-	checked 2014, 2015 programme	Event: tourism
Event: science	event	Indigenous and local knowledge use in natural resource management 2013, Copenhagen	-	Circumpolar	Denmark	-	-	-	-	checked 2013 programme	Event: science
Event: policy and science	event	Antarctic Treaty Summit 2009 (regular, non-annual)	-	Antarctic	unknown	-	-	-	-	checked 2009 programme	Event: policy and science
Event: law	event	Eight Polar Law Symposium 2015, Fairbanks	-	Circumpolar	United States	-	-	-	-	checked 2015 programme	Event: law
Event: business	event	Arctic Business Forum (1)	-	Circumpolar	Finland	-	-	-	-	checked 2015 programme	Event: business
Event: business	event	Arctic Business 2016, Bodø	-	Circumpolar	Norway	-	-	-	-	checked 2016 bloggers (no programme available)	Event: business
Event: general	event	International Forum: Arctic: Today and Future, St Petersburg 2015	-	Circumpolar	Russian Federation	-	-	-	-	NA	Event: general
Event: general	event	High North Dialogue, Bodø	-	Circumpolar	Norway	-	-	-	-	checked 2015, 2016 programme	Event: general
Event: general	event	The Alaskan Arctic, 2015, Anchorage	-	United States	United States	-	-	-	-	checked 2015 programme	Event: general
Event: shipping	event	ShipArc 2015, Malmö	-	Circumpolar	Sweden	-	-	-	-	checked 2015 programme	Event: shipping
Event: general	event	Arctic Exchange 2015	-	Circumpolar	Sweden	-	-	-	-	checked 2015 programme	Event: general
Event: energy	event	Arctic Oil and Gas Symposium	-	Circumpolar	Canada	-	-	-	-	checked (partly) 2015 programme	Event: energy
Event: technology	event	Arctic Technology Conference	-	Circumpolar	unknown	-	-	-	-	NA (irrelevant, too technical, too many)	Event: technology
Event: policy	event	Arctic Patrol and Reconnaissance, Copenhagen	-	Circumpolar	Denmark	-	-	-	-	NA (only military forces, space agencies, coast guards)	Event: policy
Event: general	event	Canada's North Summit 2013, Whitehorse	-	Canada	Canada	-	-	-	-	checked 2013 programme	Event: general
Event: food and agriculture	event	Circumpolar Agricultural Conference, Girdwood AK	-	Circumpolar	United States	-	-	-	-	checked 2013 programme	Event: food and agriculture
Event: general	event	Reindeer husbandry as a resource for the society - seminar, Uppsala, 2012	-	Circumpolar	Sweden	-	-	-	-	NA (checked 2012 programme, no private sector stakeholders)	Event: general
Event: general	event	Mining and Mineral Industry of the Future	-	Nordic countries	Sweden	-	-	-	-	checked 2016 programme	Event: general
Event: general	event	International Forum on the Sub-Antarctic	-	Antarctic	International	-	-	-	-	checked 2011 programme	Event: general
Event: general	event	IPHC Conference 2014: The future of polar heritage	-	Bipolar	Denmark	-	-	http://polesapartconference.org.uk/index.php/conference-programme	-	NA (checked 2014 programme, no private sector stakeholders)	Event: general
Event: general	event	Poles Apart 2013	-	Bipolar	UK	-	-	-	-	checked 2015 programme	Event: general
Event: general	event	Brussels Townhall meeting 2015 ECRA	-	Bipolar	Europe	-	-	-	-	checked 2015 attendee list	Event: general
Event: general	event	Arctic Cities, Global Processes and Local Realities, Rovaniemi 2013	-	Circumpolar	Finland	-	-	-	-	checked 2013 programme	Event: general
Event: general	event	Arctic Design Week	-	Circumpolar	Finland	-	-	-	-	NA (none available)	Event: general
Event: general	event	ISotRP: In the Spirit of the Rovaniemi Process - Arctic Cities, Global Processes and Local Realities; Rovaniemi 2013	-	Circumpolar	Finland	-	-	-	-	checked 2013 programme	Event: general
Event: general	event	International Conference on Urbanisation in the Arctic, Nuuk, 2012	-	Circumpolar	Greenland	-	-	-	-	checked 2012 programme (though only research stakeholders took part)	Event: general
Event: general	event	International Arctic Fisheries Symposium 2009, Anchorage	-	Circumpolar	United States	-	-	-	-	checked 2009 programme (though mainly research stakeholders)	Event: general
Event: general	event	Arctic Dialogue, Bodø	-	Circumpolar	Norway	-	-	-	-	checked 2013, 2014 programme	Event: general
Event: general	event	Arctic Open-water Meeting, Anchorage	-	Circumpolar	United States	-	-	-	-	checked 2013 programme	Event: general
Event: general	event	Arctic Observing Summit, Fairbanks	-	Circumpolar	United States	-	-	-	-	checked 2016 programme	Event: general
Event: general	event	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Event: general
Event: general	event	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Event: general
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Key of abbreviations and codes
A. Arctic
14/15/16 2014/2015/2016

Annex 3: Existing Stakeholder Consultations / Reports

Organisation	Name of Project	Type of Activity	Period	Geographical Scope	Institutions and Partners Involved	Disciplines Involved	Outcome (Report/Link Web)	Availability of outcome	Sources
International Permafrost Association (IPA)	Permafrost Research Priorities (PRP) - A Roadmap for the Future	Online questionnaire, benchmark publication	2014-2015	Online, Various	<p>Individuals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hugues Lantuit (AWI, Germany, Chair) Michel Allard (Université Laval, Canada) Mauro Guglielmin (Insubria University, Italy) Margareta Johansson (Lund University, Sweden) Gleb Kravtsov (Centre for Forest Ecology and Productivity, Russian Federation) Michael Krautblatter (Technical University of Munich, Germany) Gerhard Krinner (LGGE Grenoble, France) Edward A. G. Schuur (Northern Arizona University, USA) Ylva Sjöberg (CIIC Fellow, Stockholm University, Sweden) Jenny Baeseman (CIIC Director, Ex-Officio) Karina Schöllán (IPA Executive Director, Ex-Officio) <p>Organisations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consultation Process organized by the International Permafrost Association (IPA), Climate and Cryosphere Project (CIIC) <p>Endorsed by</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR) IASC Cryosphere WG Permafrost Young Researcher Network (PYRN) Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) 	Arctic, Mountain, Antarctic, Planetary, Sub-sea permafrost, Carbon cycle, Ecology, Ground thermal regime	All submitted questions can be found at http://www.climatecryosphere.org/media-gallery/1288-2014-10-06-prp-questions The outcomes of the PRP project will be communicated widely, with specific focus on the target audiences. The PRP products will include a high level, but short benchmark publication that lists and puts into context research priorities for 2015 to 2025.	Webpage Link does not work	http://icarp.iasc.info/themes#summary
IASC Network Arctic Freshwater Synthesis (AFS)	Arctic Freshwater Synthesis	International Assessment	2013-2015	Global	<p>Individuals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Terry Prowse, University of Victoria Johanna Mård Karlsson, Stockholm University Arvid Bring, University of New Hampshire <p>Sponsors</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate and the Cryosphere (CIIC) Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP) International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) <p>Additional Funders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Norwegian Ministry of Foreign Affairs Norwegian Ministry of the Environment 	Arctic, Ocean, Freshwater flow, Terrestrial hydrology, Terrestrial ecology, Resources components, Global climate, Atmosphere, Environment	Special Issue and Layman Report	coming soon	http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/AFS_RT.pdf
IASC Action Group on Geosciences	Geology of the Arctic-A new synthesis	IASC Workshop (report)	NA	NA	<p>Main organiser</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organised by IASC Action Group on Geosciences Bernard Cookley (University of Alaska Fairbanks) <p>Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> IASC Marine, Terrestrial and Social & Human WGs Carlo Barbante (University of Venice) Peter Jordan (University of Groningen) Victoria Pease (University of Stockholm) Carsten Piepjohn (Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe) 	Arctic, Ice sheets, Arctic environment, Circumpolar mineral resources, Arctic Archaeology, Arctic mineral resources, Arctic geoscience	Publication Emerging Questions in Arctic Geoscience by the Geological Society of London		http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/Emerging_Geoscience_Questions_RT.pdf
IASC Atmosphere WG	Linkage between Arctic Change and Mid-latitude Weather Extremes	Workshops/Journal	2013-2015	Iceland, Seattle	<p>Organiser</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> IASC Atmospheric Working Group <p>Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> IASC Marine Cryosphere and Terrestrial WGs CIIC Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) WWRP Polar Prediction Program (PPP) 	Arctic, Climate, Weather, Arctic science, Temperature	Linkage paper	0	http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/Linkages_RT.pdf
INTERACT IASC Terrestrial WG	Arctic winter snow changes: Recent Developments and a Roadmap for Observing, Modeling and Determining Impacts	Workshop	2014	European Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IASC Cross-cutting activity arranged primarily through the Terrestrial WG 	Arctic, Winter, Snow, Arctic community			http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/Snow_RT.pdf
		Multi-author paper	on-going	N/A					
		Session at ISAR-4/IC	2015	Japan					
IASC Atmosphere WG	Planning for MOSAIC – the Multidisciplinary drifting Observatory for the Study of Arctic Climate	Coordination	on-going	Various	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Matthew Shupe, University of Colorado/NOAA, USA Klaus Dethloff, Alfred Wegener Institute, Germany 	Arctic, Ice-ocean-biosphere, Arctic Basin, Arctic weather, Climate			http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/MOSAIC_RT.pdf
IASC Network PAST Gateways	Palaeo-Arctic Spatial and Temporal Gateways (PAST Gateways): a multidisciplinary, pan-Arctic network researching Arctic palaeoclimate	Conference and workshop	2012 - on-going (six year programme)	Various locations (Workshop held in Russia, Italy, Germany)	<p>Organiser</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> IASC Network PAST Gateways Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale (OGS) - 2014 <p>Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> IASC Marine, Cryosphere, Terrestrial and Atmosphere WGs University of the Arctic Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) 	Arctic environmental change, Arctic, Arctic Ice Sheets, Arctic sea-ice and ocean changes, Non-glaciated Arctic environments, Holocene Arctic environment, Permafrost change	Reports: http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/PastGateways_Report_and_Agenda.pdf , http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/PAST_Gateways_2015_conference_report.pdf	0	
IASC Marine WG	Towards a seasonally ice covered Arctic Ocean	workshop	2014	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institute (WHOI)	<p>Bert Rudels FMI & MWG/AOSB of IASC</p> <p>Additional supporter</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> WHOI FMI EU project NAACLIM 	Arctic ocean ice cover			http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/Seasonal_Ice_Cover_RTdocx.pdf
IASC Marine WG	Greenland Ice Sheet/Ocean Interaction (GROCE)	workshop	2014	Greenland (workshop)	<p>Organiser</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> IASC Marine WG <p>Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> IASC Cryosphere and Atmosphere WGs, Ice Sheet Mass Balance and Sea Level (ISMSS) 	Greenland, Arctic, Ice sheet, Ocean	Report	0	http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/Greenland_Ice_Sheet_Workshop_Report.pdf

Organisation	Name of Project	Type of Activity	Period	Geographical Scope	Institutions and Partners Involved	Disciplines Involved	Outcome (Report/Link Web)	Availability of outcome	Sources
IASC Network Arctic in Rapid Transition (ART)	Second ART workshop: Integrating spatial and temporal scales in the changing Arctic System: towards future research priorities	Workshop	2014	France	Organiser ► IASC Network Arctic in Rapid Transition (ART) Partners ► All IASC WGs ► Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) ► Permafrost Young Researchers Network (PYRN) ► European Institute for Marine Science (IUEM)	Arctic, Arctic marine, Coastal system, Biological and physical oceanography, sea ice, marine biodiversity, land-ocean interactions, paleo-reconstruction, biological archives, law, economics			http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/ISTAS_RT.pdf
IASC / ICARP	Quantifying Albedo Feedbacks and Their Role in the Mass Balance of the Arctic Terrestrial Cryosphere	Workshop	2014	UK	Organisers ► Martin Sharp (University of Alberta) ► Martyn Tranter (University of Bristol) Individual participants	Climate, Snow, Greenland ice sheet, Arctic glaciers, Albedo, Permafrost, Climate, High latitude terrestrial ecosystems, Terrestrial cryosphere	Report	0	http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/IASC_Albedo_Report.pdf
European Marine Board / European Polar Board (EMB/EPB)	4th European Marine Board Forum Arctic 2050 – Toward ecosystem-based management in a changing Arctic Ocean	Forum	2014	Belgium	Symposium organiser ► European Marine Board / European Polar Board (EMB/EPB) Spanning industry ► Shell, GDF Suez, OGP and Total) Policy ► European Commission and national governments) Academia ► research performing and research funding organizations NGOs and consultancies	Arctic ocean, Arctic resources, biodiversity, Ecological management, Maritime trade, Tourism, Transportation, Infrastructure, nature, Arctic ice, climate change	Symposium report	0	http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/4thEMBForumMessage_Arctic2050_March2014.pdf
ISAC	Technology and Innovation Session at Arctic Observing Summit	Session	2014	Finland	Session organiser ► Forum of Arctic Research Operators (FARO) Collaborators ► European Polar Board (EPB) ► IASC Contributors ► AOS ► ICARP III	Polar technology, Policy support, Financial			http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/Report_AOS_2014.pdf
ESA (European Space Agency) / CliC (Climate and Cryosphere Project)	ESA-CliC Earth Observation and Arctic Science Priorities	workshop	2015	Norway	Organisers ► European Space Agency (ESA) ► CliC	Arctic, Ice sheet, Arctic science, Earth			
Ny-Ålesund Science Managers Committee (NySMAC)	Collaboration and coordination within the Ny-Ålesund Atmosphere Flagship Programme	workshop	2014	Germany	Organisers ► Ny-Ålesund Science Managers Committee (NySMAC) Partners ► Christina A. Pedersen (Norwegian Polar Institute) ► Roland Neuber (Alfred Wegener Institute)	Greenland, Atmosphere, Meteorology	Report		http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/NyAlesundFlagship_RT.pdf
Ny-Ålesund Science Managers Committee (NySMAC)	Towards a coordinated Research and Monitoring Program for Ny-Ålesund	workshop	2015	Norway	Organisers ► Ny-Ålesund Science Managers Committee (NySMAC) Partners ► Geir W. Gabrielsen (Norwegian Polar Institute) ► Christina A. Pedersen (Norwegian Polar Institute)	Atlantic Ocean, Marine biology, terrestrial ecology, glaciology, atmospheric science			http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/NyAlesundMonitoring_RT.pdf
Pacific Arctic Group (PAG)	The Pacific Arctic Group Climate Observing System: An international effort to understand the causes and consequences of sea ice loss in the 'Hot Spot' of the Arctic Ocean	Pacific Arctic Group ICARP III initiative	2014	USA	Organisers ► K. Crane (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), USA) ► K. Shimada (Tokyo University of Marine Science and Technology (TUMST), Japan) ► K.-H. Cho (Korea Polar Research Institute (KOPRI), Korea) ► J. Grebmeier (University of Maryland, Center for Environmental Science (UMCES), USA) ► J. He (Polar Research Institute of China (PRIC), China) ► S.-H. Kang (Korea Polar Research Institute (KOPRI), Korea) ► T. Kikuchi (Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology (JAMSTEC), Japan) ► J.-H. Kim (Korea Polar Research Institute (KOPRI), Korea) ► H. Melling (Fisheries and Oceans Canada (DFO), Canada) ► A. Ostrovsky (Alliance Group LLC, Russia) ► R. Pickart (Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI), USA) ► G. Panteleev (International Arctic Research Center, University of Alaska at Fairbanks (IARC), USA) ► I. Polyakov (International Arctic Research Center, University of Alaska at Fairbanks (IARC), USA) ► T. Ural (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), USA) ► J. Wang (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), USA) ► W. Williams (Fisheries and Oceans Canada (DFO), Canada) ► H. Yamaguchi (Ocean University of China (OUC), China) ► E.-J. Yang (Korea Polar Research Institute (KOPRI), Korea) ► J.P. Zhao (Ocean University of China (OUC), China)	Pacific Arctic, Arctic ocean, Atlantic water, Pacific water, summer sea ice, ecosystem, Pacific arctic ocean, Northern hemisphere, climate	www.pag.arcticportal.org	x	http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/PAG_Climate_Observing_System_RT.pdf
International Study of Arctic Change (ISAC)	Arctic Observing Summit	Summit	2013	Canada	Sustaining Arctic Observing Network (SAON) International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) Arctic Science Summit Week (ASSW) World Meteorological Association (WMO) Arctic Institute of North America, University of Calgary	1. the status of the current observing system including goals, objectives, capabilities, challenges, and sustainability 2. observing system design and coordination (including inter-operability, integration and implementation) 3. stakeholder perspectives on observing system design and integration 4. mechanisms for coordination of support, implementation and operation of a sustained and relevant Arctic observing system.	http://arctic.journalhosting.ucalgary.ca/arctic/index.php/arctic/issue/view/281	0	http://www.arcticobservingsummit.org/

Organisation	Name of Project	Type of Activity	Period	Geographical Scope	Institutions and Partners Involved	Disciplines Involved	Outcome (Report/Link Web)	Availability of outcome	Sources
			2014	Finland	International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) Arctic Science Summit Week (ASSW) Finnish Meteorological Institute Thule Institute	1. Stakeholder engagement 2. Coordination and international cooperation 3. Technology and innovation 4. Remote sensing solutions 5. Data management, accessibility, and interoperability			http://www.arcticobservingsummit.org/ https://www.arctichub.net/groups/aos2014 http://www.assw2014.fi/
			016- ongoing	USA		1. International and national strategies for sustained support of long-term Arctic observing 2. Technology and innovation for sustained Arctic observations 3. Contributions of the Private Sector and Industry to sustained Arctic observations 4. Actor and Stakeholder engagement and needs in sustained Arctic observations 5. Arctic Observations in the context of Global Observing initiatives 6. Interfacing Traditional Knowledge, Community-based Monitoring and Scientific Methods for sustained Arctic observations			http://www.arcticobservingsummit.org/aos-2016-themes-and-important-announcements
IASC Social & Human WG	Permafrost Dynamics and Indigenous Land Use	Workshop	2014	Finland	IASC Cryosphere and Terrestrial WGs Arctic Science Summit Week 2014	Indigenous land, permafrost ecosystems, climate change, thermokarst, human activity	Report	0	
IASC Network Arctic Coastal Dynamics (ACD)	Circumpolar Arctic Coastal Communities Observatory Network (CACCON)	workshop	2014	Denmark	► Dr. Donald Forbes, Bedford Institute of Oceanography, Dartmouth, NS, Canada ► Dr. Joan Nymand Larsen, Stefansson Arctic Institute, Akureyri, Iceland ► Dr. Trevor Bell, Memorial University of Newfoundland, St. John's, NL, Canada ► Dr. Paul Overduin, Alfred Wegener Institute, Potsdam, Germany ► Dr. Rasmus Ole Rasmussen, Nordregio, Stockholm, Sweden ► Dr. Tatiana Vlasova, Russian Academy of Sciences, Moscow, Russian Federation ► Prof. Andrey Petrov, University of Northern Iowa, Cedar Falls, IA, USA ► Prof. Peter Schweitzer, University of Vienna, Vienna, Austria ► Dr. Gleb Kravov, Russian Academy of Sciences, Moscow, Russian Federation ► Dr. Nicole Couture, Geological Survey of Canada, Ottawa, Canada ► Prof. David Atkinson, University of Victoria, Victoria, BC, Canada ► Dr. Helene Amundsen, CICERO, Oslo, Norway ► Dr. Elizabeth Marino, Oregon State University - Cascades, Bend, OR, USA ► Dr. Shari Gearheard, University of Colorado, Clyde River, NU, Canada Additional partners: IASC, Future Earth Coasts (formerly LOICZ), ArcticNet, MEOPAR, Nordregio, IAASSA, Arctic-FROST, IPA, ACD, SLICA, ASI, ArcticSTAR, ELOKA, Shishmaref Erosion and Relocation Coalition (Alaska, USA), Government of Nunatsiavut (Labrador, Canada), Arviat Wellness Centre (Arviat, Nunavut, Canada), Municipality of Clyde River and Ittaq (Baffin Island, Nunavut, Canada), Kommune Kujalleq (Greenland).	Arctic coast, Coastal community, human settlements, indigenous knowledge, the North	Report	0	http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/CACCON_RT.pdf http://caccon.org/
Northern Research Forum (NRF)	Arctic Science in Globalization: Beyond IPY 2007-2008	Session	2014, 2015	Iceland, Japan	Session at Arctic Circle Conference organized by Northern Research Forum (NRF)	Arctic region, Earth, Environment, climate change, globalisation, Non-arctic nation, Politics, Business, state and civil society, circumpolar North, Polar science, global economy, Political economic system, Arctic security,	Report	0	
Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna (CAFF)	Arctic Biodiversity Congress	Congress	2014	Norway	CAFF, Arctic Council	Arctic, Arctic biodiversity, conservation and sustainable	ABA report	0	http://www.arcticbiodiversity.is/congress
IASC Social and Human WG	Culture and Arctic Climate Change - Integrating Long-Term Perspectives from Archaeology and the Environmental Sciences	workshops	2014	USA	AGU Conference Session organized by IASC Social and Human WG Partners All IASC WGs IASC Polar Archeology Network Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) Professor Max Friesen (Chair, Polar Archaeology Network (PAN) / Department of Anthropology, University of Toronto) Professor Peter Jordan (*lead contact *) (Arctic Centre, University of Groningen) Dr. Mary-Louise Timmermans (Yale University). American Geophysical Union (AGU) Canadian Archaeological Association (CAA)	Climate, oceans, cryosphere, biosphere, arctic, arctic archaeology, arctic environment, arctic science, climate change,	Report	0	

Organisation	Name of Project	Type of Activity	Period	Geographical Scope	Institutions and Partners Involved	Disciplines Involved	Outcome (Report/Link Web)	Availability of outcome	Sources
IASC Terrestrial WG	Rapid Arctic Transitions due to Infrastructure and Climate Change (RATIC)	Workshops	2014-2015	Canada (Arctic Change 2014 Conference) Japan (Meetings during ASSW 2015)	IASC Cryosphere and Social & Human WGs Case Study 1 D.A. Walker (University of Alaska Fairbanks), Gary Kofinas (University of Alaska Fairbanks), Martha Raynolds (University of Alaska Fairbanks), Mikhail Kanevskiy (University of Alaska Fairbanks), Yuri Shur (University of Alaska Fairbanks), Ken Ambrosius (Quantum Spatial Co., Anchorage), Marcel Buchhorn (University of Alaska Fairbanks), George Matayshak (Lomonosov Moscow State University), Vladimir Romanovsky (University of Alaska Fairbanks), Lisa Wirth (University of Alaska Fairbanks) Case Study 2 Timo Kumpula (University of Eastern Finland), Bruce Forbes (Arctic Centre, Rovaniemi), Artem Khumotov (Earth Cryosphere Institute, Siberia Branch), Marina Leibman (Earth Cryosphere Institute, Siberia Branch), Olga Khitun (Komarov Botanical Institute) Case Study 3 Mickael Lemay (Université Laval), Michel Allard (Université Laval), Scott Lamoureux (Queens University, Kingston, Ontario), Trevor Bell (Memorial University, St. John's, Newfoundland, Canada), Donald Forbes (Geological Survey of Canada), Warwick Vincent (Université Laval) Case Study 4 Elena Kuznetsova (Norwegian University of Science and Technology) Case Study 5	Arctic infrastructure, climate change, Permafrost, Indigenous reindeer herders	White Paper	0	
University of the Arctic	Community Consultation on Arctic Research Priorities	Consultation	2014-2015		University of the Arctic, ICARP III, Canadian Polar Commission, the Indigenous Peoples Secretariat of the Arctic Council	Arctic people, Arctic communities, Arctic science, Indigenous people			Questionnaire: www.research.net/s/UAArctic-Giving_Northerners_a_say
International Arctic Social Sciences Association (IASSA)	Understanding Sustainability in the Arctic	Transdisciplinary workshop	2015	USA	IASC's Social and Human WG, the International Arctic Social Association, the US NSF's Research Coordination Network ArcticFrost Andrey Petrov (University of Northern Iowa, USA), Gail Fondahl (UNBC, Canada), Peter Schweitzer (University of Vienna, Austria)	Arctic, Economic development, indigenous consideration, social-ecological change, arctic sustainability	Workshop report	0	
International Study of Arctic Change (ISAC)	ArcticSTAR: Solution-oriented, Transdisciplinary Research for a Sustainable Arctic	Project	2014-2015	Pan-Arctic	 ► Prof. V. Faye McNeill (Columbia University, USA) ► Prof. Ilan Chabay (Institute for Advanced Sustainability Studies, Germany) ► Dr. Donald Forbes (Bedford Institute of Oceanography, Dartmouth, Canada) ► Prof. Trevor Bell (Memorial University of Newfoundland, Canada) ► Dr. Kathrin Keil (Institute for Advanced Sustainability Studies, Germany) ► Dr. Paty Matrai (Bigelow Laboratory for Ocean Sciences, USA) ► Prof. Maribeth Murray (Arctic Institute of North America, Canada) ► Prof. Peter Schlosser (Columbia University, USA) Additional partners ISAC, CACCION, OASIS/AICI, HiT, BEPSII, ASP, ArcticNET, AINA, CRAICC, PEEK, SVALB, DEFROST, NORDFROST, CIC, CLIVAR, DBO, SEARCH, Future Earth Coasts (formerly LOICZ), IASC, IASSA, AACA, IPA, ACD, IASS, KISC, ESG	Arctic, Geography, Physics, Biology, Socioeconomics, sociocultural study			http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/ArcticSTAR_RT.pdf
International Study of Arctic Change (ISAC)	Responding to Change Activities	Workshops and scoping	2012, 2014	Canada, Norway	Main Organizers: Jean Claude Gascard (ACCESS/ISAC) Peter Schlosser (ISAC/Columbia University) Maribeth Murray (ISAC/AINA, University of Calgary) Lize Marie van der Watt (ISAC) Michael Karcher (ACCESS) Additional Partners: Oran Young (Bren School, UCSB) Janet Pawlak (ARCRISK) Lawson Brigham (AMSA) Phillip Loring (USASK) Jeremy Wilkinson (ICE-ARC) Martin Fortier (ArcticNet) Morten Skovgaard Olsen (AMAP) Paula Kakaana'aa (EU Arctic Information Center/University of Lapland) Martin Sommerkorn (WWF International) Nikolaj Bock (IEA) Hajo Eicken (SEARCH) Johanna Wandel (ISAC) Karen Pletnikoff (SEARCH) Hiroyuki Enomoto (NIPR)	Arctic, Stakeholders engagement, Health science, Arctic change, Education, Economics, Policy	Results will be reported through the ISAC Program Office.		http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/ISAC_Response_to_Arctic_Change_RT.pdf
International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES)	Arctic Ecosystems Integrated Assessments	Developing the observing/survey systems needed to collate the data for an IEA in the Arctic ocean/LME's	2015-2016	Norway	ICES, AMAP, PAME, CAFF	Arctic ocean, ecosystem, geology, Barents sea, Bering strait, Chukchi sea			http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/ICES_Arctic_Ecosystems_Integrated_Assessments_RT.pdf
IASC, ICARP III	Arctic Science Summit Week: Common Day ASSW 2014	Symposium	2014	Finland	ICARP III Partner Organizations	Arctic, Climate, Arctic society and ecosystem, marine-geophysics, ice sheets			http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/ICARPIII_Symposium_ASSW_2014_Program.pdf

Organisation	Name of Project	Type of Activity	Period	Geographical Scope	Institutions and Partners Involved	Disciplines Involved	Outcome (Report/Link Web)	Availability of outcome	Sources
International Association of Social Sciences (IASSA)	Townhall at 8th International Congress of Arctic Social Sciences	Congress	2014	Canada	International Arctic Science Committee's Social & Human Sciences Working Group (IASC S&HWG)	Arctic, Greenland, Sustainable development, Strategic environment, Northern music, Tourism, economics, Polar art, culture, education, climate change, governance, health, well-being, international relations, law, renewable resources, urban and community sustainability			http://resweb.res.uncb.ca/icass2014/icarp%20townhall.htm
Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS)	APECS - CIIC – Where are they now?	Report	2014-2015	Norway, Online	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Sanna Majaneva, University of Helsinki ▶ Jenny Baeseman, Climate and Cryosphere (CIIC) ▶ Gerlis Fugmann, Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) ▶ Maja Lisowska, Polish Centre for Polar Research and the Polish Polar Consortium ▶ Christie Logvinova, Clark University ▶ Gwen Hamon, Climate and Cryosphere (CIIC) <p>Additional partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) ▶ Climate and Cryosphere (CIIC) 	Arctic, Polar sciences, Arctic science, Policy, education, management,	Report	Results will be written into peer-reviewed paper which is to be ready and submitted by early 2015.	
Permafrost Young Researchers Network (PYRN)	Permafrost Young Researchers Workshop	workshop	2014	Portugal	<p>Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) ▶ International Permafrost Association (IPA) ▶ Climate and Cryosphere (CIIC) 	Permafrost, Arctic, Climate	<p>PYRN paper http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/PYRN_Paper_-_The_Cryosphere.pdf</p> <p>Workshop report http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/PYRN2014_report.pdf</p>	0	
International Permafrost Association (IPA)	Townhall at 4th European Conference on Permafrost (EUCOP4)	Conference	2014	Portugal	http://www.eucop4.org/people.html	Permafrost, Arctic, Climate, geomorphology, microbiology, topography, earth science, volcanic mountain, history	Book of abstracts	0	https://dl.dropboxusercontent.com/u/4653594/EUCOP4/1%20Programme%20Guide_22JUN.pdf
the Climate and Cryosphere (CIIC)	ICARP III FrostBytes - Soundbytes of Cool Research	Soundbite	2014/2015	various	Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS), Permafrost Young Researchers Network (PYRN), Arctic Development and Adaptation to Permafrost in Transition (ADAPT), Changing permafrost in the Arctic and its Global Effects in the 21st Century (PAGE21), IASC	Arctic, climate, permafrost, global effects	http://www.climate-cryosphere.org/albums/icarp3-frostbytes	0	
Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS)	Goals of ICARP III – the future of Arctic research from the early career researchers' point of view	Survey-report workshop	2015	Online Japan	<p>Partners</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ All IASC WGs ▶ IASC Network Arctic in Rapid Transition (ART) ▶ Permafrost Young Researchers Network (PYRN) <p>▶ Sanna Majaneva (University of Helsinki)</p> <p>▶ Gerlis Fugmann (Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) / UIT The Arctic University of Norway)</p>	Arctic, Europe, Russia, North America, Geology, Earth science, Biology, Biomedical sciences, Marine science	Preliminary results of the survey	0	
the Arctic Research Consortium of the United States	ARCUS Outreach and Communication	Outreach and capacity building activities	on-going	Virtual support	Sarah Bartholow, Betsy Turner-Bogren, Judy Fahnestock, Helen Wiggins Arctic Research Consortium of the United States	Arctic, arctic science, arctic climate change, national policy			http://icarp.iasc.info/images/articles/Themes/ARCUS_RT.pdf
Polar Educators International (PEI)	Arctic major future tasks in terms of polar education & outreach	Survey	2014	Online	Polar Educators International (PEI)	Polar region, polar science			
British Aantartic Survey	<p>ICE-ARC - EU FP7 project</p> <p>Work Package 1 Improving observational capabilities and reducing uncertainties</p> <p>Work Package 2 Improving modelling capabilities and reducing uncertainties</p> <p>Work Package 3 Identifying socio/economic vulnerabilities within the Arctic region</p> <p>Work Package 4 Modelling socio/economic vulnerabilities</p>	Projects - Work Pack	2014-2017	Various locations	<p>European Union's 7th Framework Programme (Funding support)</p> <p>British Antarctic Survey Ecorys Nederland BV Greenland Climate Research Centre Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland Danish Meteorological Institute Alfred-Wegener-Institut für Polar- und Meeresforschung Ocean Atmosphere Systems GmbH SINTEF Fiskeriolag havbruk Norsk Polarinstittutt Université Pierre et Marie Curie Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique European Commission Joint Research Council Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas Danmarks Tekniske Universitet Cambridge Polar Consultants Norwegian Meteorological Institute Polar Scientific Ltd Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche Mercator Océan Arctic Marine Exploration University of Cambridge</p>	Arctic marine environment, Arctic Shelf, Ocean, Sea ice, Arctic climate change, Freshwater, Greenland, Remote coastal communities, Food security, Indigenous people, Sociology, Economic, Politics, Hunting, Archaeology, History, Human migration, Culture, Global economy, Climate change, Carbon	http://www.ice-arc.eu/data/	0	http://www.ice-arc.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/22/2015/02/ICE-ARC-brochure-pages-format.pdf
ACAP	Feasibility Study for ACAP Demonstration Project on improved system for collection, storage, transport and treatment of mercurycontaining waste (MCW) in NW Region of the Russian Federation	Project	2010	Russia	Danish Ministry of the Environment Danish Environmental Protection Agency	Mercury, Arctic, Air pollution, North American region, Mining, Russia, Arctic 8 countries	Report	0	https://oaarchive.arctic-council.org/handle/11374/17
ACAP	Reduction of Black Carbon Emissions from Residential Wood Combustion in the Arctic – Black Carbon Inventory, Abatement Instruments and Measures	Project	2010-2012	Norway Finland Sweden Denmark Canada USA	SINTEF, Norsk Energi, Arctic Council	Arctic, Black carbon, Residential wood combustion	Report	0	
ACAP	Arctic Black Carbon: Reduction of Black Carbon from Diesel Sources	Project	2015	Russia	Arctic Council, Murmansk AvtoTRANS	Arctic, Black carbon, diesel	Bus Fleet	0	

Organisation	Name of Project	Type of Activity	Period	Geographical Scope	Institutions and Partners Involved	Disciplines Involved	Outcome (Report/Link Web)	Availability of outcome	Sources
AMAP	Snow, Water, Ice, Permafrost in the Arctic (SWIPA)	Assessment	2011-2012		IASC, WMO/CIC, IASSA	Snow, Water, Ice, Permafrost, Arctic, Climate change, Arctic policies, Languages, Arctic cryosphere	<p>Reports</p> <p>1. ARCTIC CLIMATE ISSUES 2011: CHANGES IN ARCTIC SNOW, WATER, ICE AND PERMAFROST (http://www.amap.no/documents/doc/arctic-climate-issues-2011-changes-in-arctic-snow-water-ice-and-permafrost/129)</p> <p>2. SNOW, WATER, ICE AND PERMAFROST IN THE ARCTIC (SWIPA): CLIMATE CHANGE AND THE CRYOSPHERE (http://www.amap.no/documents/doc/snow-water-ice-and-permafrost-in-the-arctic-swipa-climate-change-and-the-cryosphere/743)</p> <p>3. SWIPA 2011 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY: SNOW, WATER, ICE AND PERMAFROST IN THE ARCTIC (http://www.amap.no/documents/doc/swipa-2011-executive-summary-snow-water-ice-and-permafrost-in-the-arctic/744)</p> <p>4. CLIMATE CHANGE IN THE ARCTIC - A HOT TOPIC (http://www.amap.no/documents/doc/climate-change-in-the-arctic-a-hot-topic/101)</p>	O	http://www.amap.no/swipa
AMAP	ArcRisk Work Package 1 Management of the ArcRisk project Work Package 2 Modelling the impacts of climate change on pollutant transport and fate Work Package 3 Processes studies of contaminant transfer in the Arctic Work Package 4 Human Health effects of contaminants and the influence of climate change Work Package 5 Policy implications and synthesis Work Package 6 Communication and dissemination of ArcRisk results	Project (supported under the Seventh Framework Programme of the European Community for research, technological development and demonstration activities)	2009-2013	Arctic area and seas	http://project.arcrisk.eu/page/consortium-partners/9	Arctic, Climate change, human health, human population, policy development	http://project.arcrisk.eu/public-documents	O	http://project.arcrisk.eu/
AMAP	Adaptation Actions for a Changing Arctic - Part C (AAC)	Project (Workshops,	on-going (2011-until 2017)	three pilot regions: 1) Barents Region, 2) Saffin Bay and Davis Strait Region, and 3) Bering, Beaufort, and Chukchi Region (map: http://www.amap.no/adaptation-actions-for-a-changing-arctic-part-c)	http://www.amap.no/uploads/images/AACA%20Integration%20Team.jpg	Arctic, Climate change, Fisheries, Tourism, Global Transportation, Arctic Marine area, Arctic environment	Brochure http://www.amap.no/documents/doc/aaca-information-brochure/1067	Final report will be published in 2017	http://www.amap.no/adaptation-actions-for-a-changing-arctic-part-c
AMAP, IASC	Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (SAON)	Workshops, Reports,	2007 - on-going	various Arctic area	Arctic Council http://www.arcticobserving.org/networks http://portal.int-arcticobserving.org/background/saon-initiating-group	Arctic, Climate change, Biodiversity, Physical environment,	Publication http://www.arcticobserving.org/publications Report http://www.arcticobserving.org/reports	O	http://www.arcticobserving.org/
	The Circumpolar Biodiversity Monitoring Programme (CBMP) - Marine Ecosystem			Arctic Marine Biodiversity Monitoring Plan published in 2011	Arctic Marine monitoring area http://www.caff.is/images/Organized/Monitoring/Marine/Arctic/MarineAreas.JPG Marine Steering Group members http://www.caff.is/marine/marine-steering-group	Arctic Marine environment, Climate change, Harvest, Industrial development, Contaminants, Introduced alien species, Tourism, Disease and parasites, Scientific research, Shipping	Marine Biodiversity Monitoring Plan http://www.caff.is/marine/marine-monitoring-plan Marine Monitoring Publications http://www.caff.is/marine/marine-monitoring-publications	O	http://www.caff.is/marine
	The Circumpolar Biodiversity Monitoring Programme (CBMP) - Freshwater Ecosystem			Arctic Freshwater Monitoring Plan published	Arctic Freshwater monitoring area http://caff.is/images/Organized/Monitoring/Freshwater/ABA_with_CAFF_bou Freshwater Steering Group http://www.caff.is/freshwater/freshwater-steering-committee	Arctic Freshwater ecosystem, Climate change, UV radiation exposure, Resource development, Alien species	Freshwater Monitoring Plan	O	http://www.caff.is/freshwater

Organisation	Name of Project	Type of Activity	Period	Geographical Scope	Institutions and Partners Involved	Disciplines Involved	Outcome (Report/Link Web)	Availability of outcome	Sources
CAFF	The Circumpolar Biodiversity Monitoring Programme (CBMP) - Terrestrial Ecosystem	monitoring	In 2013, Arctic Biodiversity Monitoring Plan published	Monitoring area http://www.caff.is/images/organized/Monitoring/Terrestrial/cavm_all_sites_EDIT_web.jpg http://abds.is/index.php/cbmp-terrestrial	Terrestrial Steering Group http://www.caff.is/terrestrial/terrestrial-steering-group	Arctic terrestrial ecosystem, Climate change, Agriculture, Air traffic, invasive species, habitat fragmentation, regional development such as oil, gas and mineral exploration and production, Urbanization, Competition from the movement of more southerly species	Arctic Terrestrial Biodiversity Monitoring Plan http://www.caff.is/terrestrial/terrestrial-monitoring-publications/256-arctic-terrestrial-biodiversity-monitoring-plan Terrestrial Monitoring Publications http://www.caff.is/terrestrial/terrestrial-monitoring-publications	O	http://www.caff.is/terrestrial
	The Circumpolar Biodiversity Monitoring Programme (CBMP) - Coastal Ecosystem		In 2016, Arctic Coastal Biodiversity Monitoring Plan, anticipated to be released	Coastal expert monitoring Group http://www.caff.is/coastal/coastal-expert-monitoring-group	Climate change, Arctic coastal ecosystems, erosion, resource development, pollution	Publications of Community Based Monitoring	O	http://www.caff.is/community-based-monitoring	
	Community Based Monitoring		X09 - on-going	Arctic area		Arctic inhabitants, Arctic indigenous people, Resource management, Traditional knowledge and community, Arctic biodiversity	Community Based Monitoring Publications	O	http://www.caff.is/community-based-monitoring
Emergency Prevention Preparedness and Response (EPPR)	Use of Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UAS)	Workshop, Research	2014	Alaska, Singapore, Bering Sea, Chukchi Sea, Aleutian Islands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ National Marine Mammal Laboratory, Alaska Fisheries Science Center, NMFS ▶ United States Coast Guard, Research & Development Center ▶ NOAA (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration), National Ocean Service, Office of Response and Restoration ▶ California Department of Fish & Wildlife ▶ U.S Fish & Wildlife Service ▶ ACUASI ▶ Geophysical Institute, University of Alaska Fairbanks ▶ Norut (Northern Research Institute, Tromsø) ▶ NTNU (Norwegian University of Science and Thechnology) ▶ MPA Singapore ▶ TULUGAQ 	Arctic environments, Oil spill response activities, UAS technologies	Presentations	O	http://arctic-council.org/eppr/current-activities-projects/current-projects/
	Arctic Rescue	Project	004- ongoing	Russian Federation (Murmansk, Dikson, and	Lead by EMERCOM of Russia	Arctic seas, Oil pipeline	http://arctic-council.org/eppr/completed-work/auto-draft/arctic-rescue-background/	O	http://arctic-council.org/eppr/current-activities-projects/current-projects/
	Arctic Guide	Guide plan	Ongoing/ updated annually	Circumpolar	http://arctic-council.org/eppr/completed-work/oil-and-gas-products/arctic-guide/#sharing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Heads of delegations/EPPR ▶ EPPR secretary ▶ SAO:s ▶ National Contact Points ▶ Chairmen of Working Groups ▶ Secretariats for other Working Groups ▶ Observers to the Arctic Councils 	Emergency system work, Arctic			http://arctic-council.org/eppr/completed-work/oil-and-gas-products/arctic-guide/
	Updating the Environmental Risk Assessment	Assessment	ongoing	Circumpolar	Project Funding: Secretariat and member countries	Arctic Environmental risk, Natural disaster			http://arctic-council.org/eppr/current-activities-projects/current-projects/
	Behavior of Oil and Other Hazardous and noxious Substances (HNS) spilled in Arctic Waters (BoHASA)	Report	2011	Alaska Arctic (offshore and onshore), the Amerasian Basin (offshore north of the Beaufort Sea) and in West and East Greenland (offshore) the West Siberian Basin (Yamal Peninsula and offshore in the Kara Sea), the East Barents Basin (location of the Russian Federation's giant offshore Shtokman field) and the Alaska Arctic (offshore and onshore)	Authors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Ivar Singaas (SINTEF) ▶ Alun Lewis, Oil Spill Consultant Client Norwegian Coastal Administration	Arctic Environment, HNS and Oil, Risk, Response	Final Report	O	http://arctic-council.org/eppr/current-activities-projects/current-projects/
Protection of the Arctic Marine Environment (PAME)	Arctic Marine Tourism Project (AMTP)	Project	2014 -2015	Central Arctic C	The Association of Arctic Expedition Cruise Operators (AECO)	Arctic tourism, arctic environment, Socio-culture, Economic benefits	http://www.pame.is/images/03_Projects/Arctic_Marine_Shipping/Arctic_Marine_Tourism_Project/AMTP_Best_Practice_Guidelines.pdf	O	http://www.pame.is/index.php/projects/arctic-marine-shipment/arctic-marine-tourism-project-amtp-workshop-report/arctic-marine-tourism-project-amtp

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PAME	Specially Designated Marine Areas in the Arctic High Seas	Report	2014	Arctic High seas	Norwegian Environment Agency, Environment and energy efficiency	High seas, Arctic Ocean, international shipping activities, Arctic ocean coastal states, Arctic environment, Ship traffic	Report	0	http://www.pame.is/index.php/projects/arctic-marine-shipment/specially-designated-marine-areas-in-the-arctic
PAME	Heavy Fuel in the Arctic	Report	2013-2014	Arctic ice-covered	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Norwegian Environment Agency BDL Environment and Operations Norwegian Ministry of Foreign Affairs (Financial support) 	Arctic Marine environment, Ship movement, Arctic Region, Oil spill	Report 1 Report 2 Report 3	0	http://www.pame.is/index.php/projects/arctic-marine-shipment/heavy-fuel-in-the-arctic-phase-i
PAME	Voluntary Observing Ship (VOS) Scheme	Scheme	2012-	Arctic Council's	Port Meteorological Officers, National Meteorological Services, Ship Observation Team (SOT), Joint WMO/IOC Technical Commission for Oceanography and Marine Meteorology (IUCOMM), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) of UNESCO, National Oceanic and atmospheric administration (NOAA)	Marine Meteorology, Ship observation in the Arctic, Fisheries			http://www.pame.is/images/03_Projects/Arctic_Marine_Shipping/Voluntary_Observing_Ship_Scheme/US_Report_on_the_VOS_Scheme_2012.pdf , http://www.pame.is/index.php/projects/arctic-marine-shipment/voluntary-observing-ship-vos-scheme
PAME	Shiparc 2015 Conference on Arctic Shipping	Conference	2015	Conference was	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The International Maritime Organization (IMO) World Maritime University (WМУ) 	Arctic Marine Environment, Arctic shipping, Maritime trade routes, Mining, Oil & gas, Fisheries, Climate change			http://www.pame.is/index.php/projects/arctic-marine-shipment/shiparc-2015-conference-on-arctic-shipment
International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)	Lunar Photometry Workshop	Workshop	2015	Workshop (Spain) / Program (Alaska, Svalbard, Nunavut, Norway)	GOA group of Valladolid University, Spain	Climatology, Arctic, Lunar photometry, shipping, black carbon, Polar regions	http://iasc.info/images/working-groups/atmosphere/activities/lunar_photometry_report_25_09_2015.pdf		http://iasc.info/working-groups/atmosphere/activities#scientific-highlights-2
International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)	Arctic Climate Change and Mid-Latitude Weather Phenomena	Workshops	2015	Workshop (Austria) Research areas (Northern America and Europe such as on the west coast of the USA, the southwest USA, in the eastern Mediterranean, on the Arctic amplification)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Halldór Björnsson, Icelandic Meteorological Office AWG organizers and sponsors, 2015 European Geosciences Union General Assembly 	Arctic climate change, Mid-latitude weather, Arctic sea ice, Geosciences, Northern hemisphere, atmospheric circulation			http://iasc.info/working-groups/atmosphere/activities#scientific-highlights-3
International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)	Workshop on Dynamics of Atmosphere-Ice-Ocean Interactions in High Latitudes	Workshop	2015	Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> John Cassano (CIRES) Session themes and invited speakers: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> The Polar Climate: large scale circulation and interaction with mid-latitudes: Jennifer Francis, James Screen, Sharon Stammerjohn The Coupled Atmosphere-Ocean-Ice System: John Cassano, Chris Fairall, Andrew Roberts, Michael Tjernström, Timo Vihma Extreme Events in the Polar Regions: Günther Heinemann, Ian Renfrew, Thomas Spengler Polar Predictability: state of the art and challenges ahead: Jim Doyle, Jun Inoue, Thomas Jung, Jørn Kristiansen Organizing Committee: Thomas Spengler, Univ. of Bergen Ian Renfrew, Univ. of East Anglia John Cassano, Univ. of Colorado, Paul Hezel, Univ. of Bergen 	Arctic, Polar atmosphere, ice ocean, high latitude atmosphere, theoretical research, climate dynamics, polar region	https://highlatdynamics.b.uib.no/workshop-details/		https://highlatdynamics.b.uib.no/
International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)	Arctic Air Pollution Workshop	Workshop	2015	US (Colorado)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lead organizers: Kathy Law (LATMOS/CNRS, France), Sandy Starkweather (NOAA/CIRES, USA) Organizing committee: Steve Arnold (U. Leeds, UK), K. von Salzen (Env. Canada), J. Thomas 	Arctic air pollution, global change, arctic communities	Workshop summary		http://iasc.info/working-groups/atmosphere/activities#scientific-highlights-5
International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)	Atmospheric chemistry workshop: Local sources of Arctic pollution and their impacts	Workshop	2013	US (San Francisco)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Kathy Law (LATMOS) American Geophysical Union 	Arctic pollution (ozone, aerosols), climate change, Economic development, ecosystem			http://iasc.info/working-groups/atmosphere/activities#scientific-highlights-5
International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)	Northern Hemisphere Polar Jet Stream and Links with Arctic Climate Change Workshop	Workshop	2013	Iceland	CLIC, WCRP, ICARP II, James Overland (NOAA)	Northern Hemisphere polar jet stream change, Arctic oscillation			http://iasc.info/working-groups/atmosphere/activities#scientific-highlights-6
International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)	MOSAIC Science Plan Writing Workshop	Workshop	2013	Workshop (Gerr)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Host: the Alfred Wegener Institute Science plan writing team: M. Shupe, K. Dethloff, O. Persson, M. Tjernström, S. Gerland, D. Barber, J. Inoue, C. Lee, B. Loose, A. Makshtas, W. Maslowski, W. Meier, M. Nicolaus, D. Notz, I. Peeken, D. Perovich, J. Schmale, T. Vihma and J. Zhao 	atmosphere, ocean, Arctic clouds, Biology, Chemistry, high arctic sea ice, climate, ecosystem	Report		http://iasc.info/working-groups/atmosphere/activities#scientific-highlights-6
International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)	IASOA Workshop	Workshop	2013	Workshop (Canada)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Two International Arctic systems for Observing the Atmosphere (IASOA) working groups (Black Carbon and Surface Radiation) Arctic Observing Summit (AOS) NSF NOAA 	Arctic atmosphere, black carbon, surface radiation	Outcomes from First Synthesis Workshops for Black Carbon and surface radiation working groups		http://iasc.info/working-groups/atmosphere/activities#scientific-highlights-9

Organisation	Name of Project	Type of Activity	Period	Geographical Scope	Institutions and Partners Involved	Disciplines Involved	Outcome (Report/Link Web)	Availability of outcome	Sources
International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)	Third Polar Prediction Workshop	Workshop	2013	Workshop (Japan)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ► Organizers: Jim Overland, USA (Chair), Hiroshi Tanaka, Japan (Vice-chair), Michael Tjernström, Sweden (Vice-chair), Sara Bowden, Yoo Kyung Lee (Executive Officer), IASC (International Arctic Science Committee) ► Participants Manabu Abe (NIPR, Japan) Vladimir Alexeev (International Arctic Research Centre, UAF, USA) Hirokazu Endo (Meteorological Research Institute, Japan) Moto Iieda (Hokkaido University, Japan) Seong-joong Kim (Korea Polar Research Institute, Korea) Atsushi Koshiba (Open Air University, Japan) Yoo Kyung Lee (IASC) Wieslaw Maslowski (Naval Postgraduate School, Canada) Kent Moore (University of Toronto, Canada) Yuta Nagato (University of Tsukuba, Japan) Mototaka Nakamura (JAMSTEC, Japan) Toru Nozawa (National Institute for Environmental Studies, Japan) Atsumu Ohmura (Institute Atmosphere and Climate, E.T.H. Zurich, Swiss) Stephen Outtter (Nansen Environmental & Remote Sensing Centre, Norway) Hiroshi Tanaka (University of Tsukuba, Japan) Volker Raddold (IASC) John Walsh (International Arctic Research Centre, UAF, USA) Xiangdong Zhang (University of Alaska Fairbanks, USA) 	Arctic climate change, Polar predictability, Arctic amplification, Linkage to global process, Arctic warming, Arctic Oscillation, Arctic sea ice	Report	0	http://iasc.info/working-groups/atmosphere/activities#scientific-highlights-9
International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)	Arctic Climate Predictions Workshop	Workshop	2012	Canada	NOAA, World Climate Research Programme (WCRP), AMAP	Loss of sea ice, Global change, Marine access, Species impacts, Coastal Communities, Arctic climate change, Polar prediction	Workshop report	0	http://iasc.info/working-groups/atmosphere/activities#scientific-highlights-9
International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)	The International Arctic Systems for Observing the Atmosphere (IASOA)	Meeting	2012	Canada	AMAP	Standard meteorology, greenhouse gases, atmospheric radiation, clouds, pollutants, chemistry, aerosols, and surface energy balances	Workshop Report	0	http://iasc.info/working-groups/atmosphere/activities#scientific-highlights-9
International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)	Multi-disciplinary drifting Observatory for the Study of the Arctic Climate (MOSAIC): Planning Activities and Workshops for organizing and defining the scientific need and producing science and implementation plans	Workshop	2012	USA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ► CIRES, NOAA ► Presenters, John Walsh, Michael Tjernström, Don Perovich, Sebastian Gerland, Craig Lee, Jinping Zhao, Carin Ashjian, Brice Loose, Jeff Bowman ► Participants - Appendix A - Workshop summary paper 		Workshop summary	0	http://iasc.info/working-groups/atmosphere/activities#scientific-highlights-13
International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)	Perceptions and Representations of Polar (Climate) Science	Conference	2012	Canada (IPY 2011)	Lead Convenors: James Overland (NOAA), Peter Schweitzer (University of Alaska Fairbanks)	Arctic climate, History, Polar climate science, Social science	Session summary		http://iasc.info/working-groups/atmosphere/activities#scientific-highlights-13